

Promoting and Protecting Indigenous African Cultural Heritage Aligning to the UN Sustainable Development Goals

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ABSTRACT

The study utilized autoethnography as the core methodology to examine the experience of a San ethnic group continuous forced relocation in South Africa and the impact that had on their ability to protect and promote their tangible and intangible cultural heritage. The study found that some indigenous people are being badly treated and abused in many ways. This was supported by key evidence from the literature review that some African Governments, in collaboration with other nations and International Organizations, are using development as a pretext to drive some of the world's most endangered people away from the lands and animals that they have lived with for generations. The study adopted a critical theory approach from the perspective of cultural diplomacy (British Council, 2020; Horkheimer, 1982; Nye, 2017; Portland, 2016; Nye, 2017; ICD, 2017; Said, 1978; ICCROM, 2018; UNESCO-Courier, 2017; UNDP, 2015; OHCHR, 2012; UNESCO World Heritage Centre, 1992-2017) to aid the emancipation of some forced-relocated indigenous people from the San ethnic group in South Africa. The selection of the study target groups was aimed at a collective resource mobilization to build diverse capital for the targeted San people and to promote cultural tourism for the nation. This then gave a direction to collaborate and work with various authorities and stakeholders - researchers, policymakers, traditional leaders, industry, policy implementers and some NGOs as a way to promote the San heritage as well as the UN-SDGs policies. Convergent parallel mixed-methods were used to conduct the study interviews. Survey questionnaires were used to collect data in the quantitative phase. Policymakers were interviewed to assess their awareness about the importance of cultural research linked to indigenous cultural heritage and the governments use of cultural heritage protection as a soft power tool. A need-based survey was also conducted among the targeted San People. Adapted Go-Along interviews were used in the qualitative phase which formed the main part of the study. The two data sets were then analyzed to find out sustainable and effective ways to align the San Cultural Heritage and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

The study result showed a disconnect between the affected San people and policymakers. It also emerged from the study that the multiple forced re-locations of the

targeted San people have eroded significant aspects of their intangible heritage. The evidence-based findings in the study were translated from the autoethnographic perspective to serve as a guide for the responsible authorities and stakeholders to realize that the San heritage promotion is an enhancement of cultural diplomacy for national development; making it possible for the study outcome to bridge the gap between policymakers and the affected San people and then reconnected the San people to their heritage.

Global and local policy and practice as well as the UN-SDGs policy development were also discussed and investigated, and the key areas outlined as the study original contribution to knowledge were the significant addition to areas of theoretical development that promote indigenous heritage linked to the UN-SDGs.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

Background to the study

Sustainable development including biodiversity conservation has become a global issue and many organizations are collaborating with governments to protect natural habitats and safeguard biodiversity (Espeso & Carlisle, 2017; Conservation International, 2017). However, campaigners argue that governments are using development as a pretext to drive the world's most endangered people away from the lands and animals they have lived with for generations (MRG, 2016; Vidal, 2016; Conservation International, 2017; Mongabay, 2016; Survival, 2017). Perhaps it was for this reason that Victoria Tauli-Corpuz, UN special rapporteur on the rights of indigenous people, warned that tribal people in Botswana, South Africa, and many other countries are paying the price for some developmental projects (Vidal, 2016).

For example, the World Bank's International Development Association (IDA) has been one of the largest sources of assistance for the world's poorest countries, of which most of them are in Africa (World Bank, 2014). For instance, the World Bank Group's through IDA granted financial support to the implementation of the Government of Mozambique's Conservation Areas for Biodiversity and Development Project, known as Mozbio (World Bank, 2014). Besides the developmental assistance to developing countries, the World Bank plays a role in safeguarding and minorities indigenous communities through its funded projects (MRG, 2016). The World Bank believes that it does not matter where Indigenous people live, they "face distinct pressures, including being among the poorest and most marginalized in their societies," (World Bank, 2016, para. 1). However, the *Minority Rights Group International* (MRG) believed that the "World Bank-funded programmes have had disastrous consequences for many minority and indigenous communities; the Sengwer who have suffered forced removals in Kenya are just one of many recent examples" (MRG, 2016, p.25). A leaked draft of the World Bank's proposed new 'safeguard policies' suggested that "environmental and social protection will be gutted to allow logging and mining in even the most ecologically sensitive areas, and that indigenous people will not have to be consulted before major projects" go ahead on lands which they traditionally occupy for decades (Vidal, 2014, para. 2). The United Nations

High Commissioner for Human Rights also believes that “in some countries, governments and multinational corporations continue to construct hydroelectric dams and roads, and conduct mining and logging activities, that threaten to harm the land’s fragile ecosystems and damage large areas of land inhabited by indigenous people” (OHCHR, 2012 p.2). It was also argued that in some parts of Africa, some indigenous people’s houses were being burnt by law enforcement bodies as a way to relocate them and meanwhile, big game trophy hunters were encouraged at the same areas (Renton, 2009; Survival, 2017; The East African, 2015; Survival 2014). Indigenous people are usually accused of poaching, even though they are hunting to feed their families as their natural way of survival (Survival, 2017; Conservation Watch, 2017). It then makes sense when Conservation Watch (2017) and The East African (2015) argued that in the name of developmental projects, indigenous people are being evicted from their ancestral lands.

After the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development-*Earth Summit Conference* in Rio de Janeiro in June 1992, at which the importance of indigenous people and their communities in managing and developing the environment was recognized (OHCHR, 2012), further study commissioned by the *Working Group on Indigenous Populations* on land rights and indigenous people in 1997 “confirmed that access to land and resources is crucial for the survival of indigenous people” and therefore, recommended to “governments to consult with indigenous people in the management of land and resources,” (OHCHR, 2012, p.2). However, after the recommendations were made to the governments, a study about the pygmy tribes in Africa by *Minority Rights Group International* stated that “the states of Burundi, Democratic Republic of Congo, Rwanda and Uganda, by virtue of their ratification and acceptance of international human rights standards, have taken on the obligation to treat their citizens equally and to uphold their rights and freedoms. Yet, they have failed to discharge this obligation, and the international community has equally failed in its duty to defend the vulnerable” as the pygmy tribes were being maltreated (MRG, 2000, p. 3).

Further, the United Nation report on State of The World’s Indigenous people noted that with “all-encompassing nature of indigenous cultures that makes them unique and so different from the cultures of those groups that hold the political, economic and social

power in the nation-states in which they live,” yet indigenous people “have been excluded from the decision-making and policy frameworks of the nation-states in which they live” (UN, 2009, p.53). As a result, indigenous people have been subjected to processes of domination and discrimination and their cultures have been viewed as being “inferior, primitive, irrelevant, something to be eradicated or transformed” (UN, 2009, p.53). The report added that “indigenous cultures today are threatened with extinction in many parts of the world” as they have continued to experience the loss of access to lands, territories and natural resources (UN, 2009, p.53). According to UN (2009), although indigenous communities have demonstrated that their close relationship with the environment also makes them its best guardians, the strong environmental movement that emerged after World War II made no reference to indigenous people. This could be the result of what a recent study MRG (2016) noted that indigenous cultures have not always enjoyed the attention and respect they deserve as the cultures and lifestyles of indigenous people are often undervalued or misunderstood, resulting in norms and rules that may not always be appropriate or can even lead to assimilatory policies.

It then makes sense when the International Work Group for Indigenous Affairs (IWGIA, 2006, P. 7) expressed that although it may be a big generalization, “it is fair to say that most UN and national programmes fighting poverty do not take full cognizance of the value systems of Indigenous Africans”. It was further argued that although many people living in the region of Southern Africa fall within the internationally accepted criteria for indigenous people, many governments in the African continent still “deny that some of their citizens meet the criteria used by the UN and the international community to characterise indigenous people” (IWGIA, 2006, P.47). As a result, indigenous issues are, in most contexts, ignored, (Bolaane & Saugestad, 2011; MRG, 2000; IWGIA, 2006). This may be suggesting that when it comes to the use of natural resources for development, States and other stakeholders give little attention to the local tribes who live on the lands in question and are often forced out of their only means of survival.

Therefore, vocal groups of campaigners, academics and environmentalists claim that indigenous people are being awfully treated and abused, all in the name of a conservation philosophy that carries a heavy human cost, (Vidal, 2016).

Although some conservationists in some cases may engage indigenous groups in a dialogue or partnership (Mongabay, 2016), the director of Survival International, Stephen Corry, seems to disagree as he maintained that 'the big conservation organizations really must start listening to these tribal people,' (Survival, 2016, para. 10). The Corry statement followed the failed mediation talks between Survival International and the World Wildlife Fund (WWF) over breaches of OECD guidelines for multinational corporations over the issue of tribal people' consent (Survival, 2017: September 5). In solidarity to indigenous people, Corry (2017) stressed on the need for multinationals to take responsibility for the consequences of their actions and should not hide behind some states' failure to uphold human rights.

As Human Rights activists are calling on parties involved in international development programs to resort to pragmatic and sustainable ways of dealing with developmental issues, perhaps Cultural Diplomacy linked to Indigenous Cultural Heritage and the Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UN-SDGs) could positively influence global public opinion and the ideology of individuals, communities, cultures or nations on the values of African Indigenous Cultural Heritage (Owiny et al., 2014; UNESCO, 2003). This then led me to the brief introduction to the study, the literature review, my research aims and objectives and the research methodology outlined in the below sections.

1.1 Background: Academic and grey literature

1.2 Indigenous Cultural Heritage

The UN Permanent Forum on Indigenous Issues stated in its *Indigenous people and the 2030 Agenda* that there is an estimated 370 million persons belonging to indigenous people, making up 5% of the world's population, but 15% of the poorest, (World Bank, 2016; UN Indigenous people and the 2030 Agenda, 2016.) The reports stated that Indigenous people lag behind on virtually every social and economic indicator. The Minority Rights Group International and others may then be close to finding the reason behind such poverty as it reports that although indigenous people have an extraordinarily rich and diverse cultural heritage of sacred spaces, ancestral lands and traditional knowledge, their cultural expressions have not always received adequate recognition or protection (MRG, 2016; Espeso & Carlisle, 2017). In addition to the geographical importance of indigenous people, OHCHR (2012) notes that many of the areas of highest biological diversity on Earth are occupied by indigenous people. The report also believes that the “nations that are home to more than two-thirds of the Earth's biological resources” including some African nations, “are the traditional territories of most of the world's indigenous people” (OHCHR, 2012, p.1).

The former Director General of UNESCO, Frederico Mayor, emphasized the importance of Indigenous people wisdom that, “the indigenous people of the world possess an immense knowledge of their environments, based on centuries of living close to nature,” (UNESCO, 2001, p.5/50). It was further argued that “in rural communities in developing countries, locally occurring species are relied on for many - sometimes all - foods, medicines, fuel, building materials and other products. Equally, people's knowledge and perceptions of the environment, and their relationships with it, are often important elements of cultural identity” (UNESCO, 2001, p.5/50). The variety of complex ecosystems and the related richness that indigenous people live in make them understand the properties of plants and animals, the functioning of ecosystems and the techniques for using and managing them in a very unique way (UNESCO, 2001; MRG,

2016). The link between culture and environment is understandable among indigenous people as they share their way of life - spiritual, cultural, social and livelihood with their traditional lands (UN, 2009; OHCHR, 2012). In other words, both the cultural and physical survival of indigenous lives depend on the protection of their immediate environment (Espeso & Carlisle, 2017; UN, 2009).

In the African context, The African Commission on Human and People ' Rights (ACHPR) and the International Work Group for Indigenous Affairs (IWGIA) believed that natives who define themselves as indigenous people in Africa are mainly nomadic/semi nomadic pastoralists and those with hunting-gathering background including the Pygmies of Central Africa, the San/Bushmen of Southern Africa, the Hadzabe and Akie of Tanzania (ACHPR & IWGIA, 2006). ACHPR & IWGIA (2006) believed that almost all African states host a rich variety of different ethnic groups, some of which are dominant and some of which are in subordinate positions. Although all of these groups are indigenous to Africa, some are in a structurally subordinate position to the dominant groups and the states, and this leads to marginalization and discrimination (World Bank, 2016; Mowforth, 2014; ACHPR & IWGIA, 2006). In Africa, indigenous people have almost universally suffered injustices and discrimination in terms of their basic rights to life, property, languages, culture and citizenship, which all add up to make them the poorest and most neglected populations in the world (ACHPR & IWGIA, 2006; Paiement, 2007; Mowforth, 2014; World Bank, 2016).

On sustainable environmental management in relation to indigenous knowledge, key organizers of the Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro in 1992 and special advisors to the Secretary-General of the United Nations believe that “indigenous knowledge is not only important in its own right” but also “important for the benefits it brings to the indigenous people who own and live it” and a range of other people “who can learn lessons for living sustainably from it,” (UNESCO, 2001, p.10/50). Maurice Strong added that the Earth could be treated more carefully if indigenous knowledge and values were followed more widely.

As indigenous cultural heritage represents both inherited traditions from the past and contemporary rural and urban practices in which diverse cultural groups take part

(UNESCO, 2003), it is very important for Africans to preserve their memories, to provide access to information for future times, defend our intellectual property rights, and make indigenous cultural collections, in paper or electronic form sustainable. The rapidly increasing use of telecommunications, especially social media and access to mobile devices and technologies create opportunities for African countries to form local and international partnerships that can facilitate the process of creating, managing, preserving, and sharing of knowledge and skills that are unique to communities in Africa and beyond (Owiny et al., 2014; Carlisle et al. 2021). With the power of Digital Media, Cultural Diplomacy linked to Indigenous Cultural Heritage could positively influence global public opinion and the ideology of individuals, communities, cultures or nations on the values of African Indigenous Cultural Heritage (Owiny et al., 2014; UNESCO, 2003).

1.3 The role of Cultural and Digital Diplomacy

A recent study (Carlisle et al., 2021) and others (Portland, 2016; Nye, 2017; Rivera, 2015; Cull et al., 2015; British Council, 2018; ICD, 2017; Collins & Khan, 2016) noted that the transmission of information through digital technologies have provided various possibilities for mutual cultural exchange and interactions to change mindsets and enlighten one another. According to the Institute for Cultural Diplomacy (ICD), Cultural Diplomacy “derives its importance from the worldwide need for exchange and dialogue between cultures, which is vital to ensuring and fostering peace and stability across the globe” (ICD, 2014, p.2-3). In an increasingly globalized and interdependent world, “in which the proliferation of mass communication technology ensures we all have greater access to each other than ever before, the significance for Cultural Diplomacy” and Cultural Heritage have never been greater (ICD, 2014, p.2-3). For example, not only does the British Council through its Cultural and Creative Economy Programme (CCEP) strengthens the Council’s ability to involve high profile creative economy professionals in all aspects of the Council’s work and at the same time maintains its strong reputation in the sector, but the programme has also benefited several thousands of Nigerians after the programme was implemented in Nigeria to boost economic development in the digital

age, (British Council & Nesta, 2016; CAJ, 2013; Joffe, 2013; United Nations/UNDP/UNESCO, 2013).

In comparison to Africa, the rich African indigenous cultural heritage which has formed the backbone of Africa's unique establishments such as political systems, religious beliefs, language structure and indigenous technological practices could make Africa a strong global intercultural player in all aspects of development (Africa Ceremonies, 2013). Unfortunately, elements of these unique African Traditions are in danger of disappearing as the indigenous tribes and their cultures are facing tough times in maintaining their cultural heritage and identity, (Africa Ceremonies, 2013; Owiny et al., 2014). Therefore, creating possibilities and platforms for people to keep in touch with one another, making it possible for them to explain what they want from each other, could be a good starting point for Africa's cultural development beyond its borders (Carlisle et al., 2021; British Council & Russia, 2017; Africa Ceremonies, 2013; Owiny et al., 2014). This then highlighted the importance of Cultural Diplomacy and the new communications technologies for a strategic cultural development policy for African Nations.

1.4 Research Aim and Objectives

Globalization has made it possible for information to become one of the most strategic resource of our times (Ditchley, 2012; Owiny et al., 2014; River Path, 2013). This has put Africa in a better position than the days that natural resources like gold, diamond etc. were the economic drivers for some nations (Ditchley, 2012; Owiny et al., 2014). However, in the African context, one may wonder in which way would this concept, as a Cultural Diplomacy agenda, protect and at the same time promote the Indigenous African Cultural Heritage beyond national and continental African borders.

It was also argued that the high rate of illiteracy "in rural Africa and the exclusion of indigenous knowledge from Western education add to the information gap experienced in rural Africa," adding that the other challenges facing oral cultures are the disappearance of traditional knowledge and skills due to deliberate or inadvertent destruction of indigenous knowledge, memory loss or death of elders (Owiny et al., 2014,

p.2/15). Information flow across cultures may be very fast, but may not necessarily make it possible for people to get new inspirations across cultures, (Ditchley, 2012; Owiny et al., 2014). In other words, Globalization might have made it possible for minorities to gain a sense of belonging in the sense that one can be updated on what is happening around the globe, but digital communication may not always be a good substitute for coming into contact with and experience of different indigenous cultures and new artistic forms of expressions (Umeogu, 2013; Pew Research Center, 2015; Ditchley, 2012; Owiny et al., 2014). Technology may become even more important, and dominant, in the future as affordable and easy access to digital and communication devices have made it possible for many Africans, for example in South Africa, Ghana and Nigeria, to get online, (Pew Research Center, 2015). However, the digital development alone may not necessarily mean that the internet can assist in creating real empathy across cultural boundaries if efforts are not made to promote human movement, for example Arts or Sports Diplomacy across cultures, (Ditchley, 2012; Ditchley, 2012; Owiny et al., 2014). In particular to this study, although digital diplomacy and digital inclusion could play an important role in protecting and promoting indigenous cultural heritage, I noticed at the very beginning of the field work that the digital element was out of the reach of the target groups.

Therefore, I had to change my methodology to concentrate more on the alignment of Cultural Heritage and the UN-SDGs rather than digital diplomacy and digital inclusion. The research aim is to investigate and explore sustainable and effective ways that could enhance a two-way approach - Cultural Diplomacy linked to Indigenous Cultural Heritage promotion. The objectives include:

- 1) To investigate how the San Cultural Heritage can be aligned with the UN-SDGs, especially SDG 11, to protect their Heritage and used as a form of Cultural Diplomacy by the Nation.
- 2) To investigate the awareness, by policy makers and stakeholders of the San cultural heritage as both tangible and intangible assets for promotion and protection by government.
- 3) To contribute to a growing body of theory that demonstrates the role of cultural heritage protection and promotion as a form of cultural diplomacy.

CHAPTER 2: CULTURAL HERITAGE AND IDENTITY FORMATION

2.1 Why Indigenous Cultural Heritage and Identity?

This section of the literature review focuses on analyzing the importance of indigenous way of life, the relations between indigenous people and their natural environment and the potential benefits of indigenous knowledge beyond indigenous borders.

Promoting cultural diversity through community-based research would not only help to better know and understand given situations and developments in the communities but it would also help to build bridges between cultural differences (The South African National Heritage Council, 2017; Capurro, 2010). UNESCO guidebook for African Local Governments, defines heritage as “a collective property which tells the history of a people, a city, or a territory, and is transmitted from one generation to the next. Heritage makes it possible for the present generations to understand their place in history and to better cope with the constant mutations in society: it is an element of stability in a rapidly changing world” (France-UNESCO, 2006, p.26). The Latin American Post (2016) believes that Indigenous people with their rich heritage are the agents of the biggest amount of cultural diversity worldwide. The South African National Heritage Council (2017) also believes that heritage is what creates a sense of identity and assures rootedness and continuity. In other words, heritage is an important component of life which makes it possible for a people to show its talents in unique ways that are based on its original understanding of the relationship between creation and the community that it identifies itself with (France-UNESCO, 2006; Ndoro et al, 2008; Sithole, 2011; UNESCO Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity, 2001 referenced in Ndoro et al, 2008; Sithole, 2011). In the same belief, the Latin American Post (2016) maintained that Indigenous people do not only account for most of the world’s cultural diversity but also their unique ways of life vary from one geographical location to another. Statistically, the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, OHCHR (2012), noted that between 4,000 and 5,000

of the estimated 6,000 cultures in the world are indigenous. It was also noted that most of the world's languages are spoken by Indigenous people (The Latin American Post, 2016).

However, OHCHR noted that, “the relationship between indigenous people and their environment has been eroded because of dispossession or forced removal from traditional lands and sacred sites” as the result of development projects (OHCHR, 2012, p.2). After the establishments of reputable organizations like the United Nations Permanent Forum on Indigenous Issues (UNPFII), the Assembly of First Nations, Survival International, the World Council of Indigenous People, Indigenous Environmental Network and many national organisations along with a host of declarations on indigenous issues by UN agencies and international groups, one would say that indigenous people have been recognized (Mowforth, 2014). However, legal recognition may not necessarily mean that indigenous people rights, territories, resources and cultures are respected, (Mowforth, 2014; OHCHR, 2012). Although it was argued that “the current mass extinction of both languages and species has given rise to a vibrant, interdisciplinary movement with the goal of maintaining and revitalizing linguistic, cultural, and biological diversity on the only planet we will ever call home,” (Stringer (2016, p.14), others (Communicaid, 2019; Johnson, 2016) believed that Languages spoken by indigenous and traditional people are rapidly disappearing.

Specifically, on Africa, the importance of the African Cultural Heritage was expressed by UNESCO Assistant Director-General for Africa, Nouréini Tidjani-Serpos, that African territories, whether urban or rural, “form the true essence of the African cultural identity. They illustrate the social, spiritual, cultural, and economical exchanges that have taken place with the passing time, and that have given birth to cultural elements that are unique in the world. These elements, tangible and intangible, contribute every day to the quality of life of the African communities,” (UNESCO, 2006, p.6). Therefore, Nouréini Tidjani-Serpos called for a need to enhance such cultural and heritage values as that would undoubtedly improve the living conditions of the African populations; adding that, “all civilizations, some of them prestigious, that existed throughout the African continent, have

left many legacies to today's world" ranging from "manufacturing techniques to urban planning methods," (UNESCO, 2006, p.8).

In an effort to give recognition to Africa's contribution to the world's cultural heritage, in an artistic way, UNESCO set up the Slave Route Project in 1994 (UNESCO, 1994-2014; UNESCO Learning to Live Together, 2017). The project could be seen as a strategic way of "contributing to a better understanding of cultural traditions, forms of ingenuity, technical and scientific knowledge, skills and spirituality which were transferred from Africa to the Americas, the Caribbean, Asia, the Indian Ocean and the Arab-Muslim world. It draws attention to the major imprint of African cultures on the formation of the world's identities, cultures and civilizations, the African contribution to the world's rich diversity as expressed through Creole cultures, languages, religions, music and dance," (UNESCO World Report, 2009, p.56/420). The report noted that, cultural exchanges can be seen as the many collective developments at the origin of most human achievements and tend to invalidate claims to exclusivity for any one civilization. The African cultural wisdom has produced important results in various areas such as household objects and objects of worship, furniture making, medicine preparation as well as the making of clothing (UNESCO Africa 2009 Programme). The originality of the African cultural wisdom is also expressed in their understanding and management of their natural territorial resources, organizing the habitat, conceiving rich and diverse architectures and finally establishing relationships and resolving conflicts between communities or ethnic groups (UNESCO, 2006). Hence the *UNESCO Africa 2009 Programme and the Global Strategy of the UNESCO World Heritage* Centre believed that collectively, the rich diversity of African heritage contributes a unique wealth to World Heritage as the mosques of Timbuktu, the ruins of Great Zimbabwe, the Osun Osogbo Sacred Grove, the Swahili towns of Zanzibar and Lamu or the Island of Gorée show some examples of Africa's specific identity and diversity, creativity and ingenuity as part of the world's cultural heritage (UNESCO Africa 2009 Programme).

In recent years, the UNESCO New Inscribed Properties 2017 included the rich African heritage such as Asmara: a Modernist City of Africa in Eritrea, the Khomani Cultural

Landscape in South Africa and W-Arly-Pendjari Complex: the transnational extension (Benin, Burkina Faso) to the W National Park of Niger, inscribed in 1996 on the World Heritage List, (UNESCO World Heritage Centre 1992-2017). This might have also inspired the European Union (EU) in recent years to recognized cultural heritage as an important part of cultural diversity that deserves protection at continental level, and thereby provides training, skills development and knowledge transfer activities to partner countries in order to safeguard cultural heritage (EU, 2017).

In terms of indigenous people contribution to economic development, the UNESCO guide for *Teaching and Learning for a Sustainable Future*, UNESCO (2001) noted that nearly 75% of 121 plant-derived prescription drugs used worldwide were discovered following leads from indigenous medicine and some scientists now believe that, in their efforts to discover important new cures for diseases such as AIDS and cancer, indigenous knowledge may be helpful. As the potential for local medicine has gone beyond local communities, so is the role played by indigenous people as custodians of the world's genetic heritage (UNESCO, 2001). On the other hand, in terms of poverty alleviation, Maila & Loubser (2003) noted that critics have labeled indigenous knowledge as not being efficient in poverty alleviation and improving living standard among indigenous communities. Perhaps that is the reason why indigenous knowledge has been accorded low status because it belongs to a particular ethnic group which often, it is assumed, lacks the necessary scientific basis (Mutekwe, 2015). However, a recent study, Mawere (2017) argued that the status of indigenous knowledge has changed following the landmark 1997 Global Knowledge Conference in Toronto, which highlighted the urgent need to protect and promote indigenous knowledge. Mutekwe (2015) also noted that with all the negative perceptions, Indigenous Knowledge is gaining grounds as part of the global heritage and a national resource. The National Cancer Institute of the US National Institutes of Health believed that 'Traditional knowledge is as threatened and is as valuable as biological diversity' and 'both resources deserve respect and must be conserved,' (OHCHR, 2012, p. 2). A such, promoting heritage could be necessary in preserving the cultural elements that support sustainable existence of a society and its development.

In relations to Africa, however, one would wonder whether the values of the African heritage have always been recognized (UNESCO, 2006; Jopela, 2011). For instance, Jopela (2011) believes that formal heritage management systems have failed to protect archaeological sites in many parts of southern Africa. This is in line with UNESCO Assistant Director-General for Africa, Nouréini Tidjani-Serpos, remarks that for a long time, the African heritage “was deprecated, and its owners and holders were sometimes even encouraged to forsake it. Thus, entire portions of African heritage were lost, and those which have been jealously safeguarded are often threatened by the impact of natural forces (the rain, the wind, vegetation...) as well as the fact that the physical and social conditions of its protection and maintenance changed, often drastically (respect of taboos, know-how, availability of the materials...) creating adverse conditions,” (France-UNESCO, 2006, p.8). In addition to the fundamental importance of heritage and cultural promotion in community development, Vincent Négri in an article, *Introduction to heritage law in Africa* (ICCROM, 2008, p.19/129) believes that “when culture is closely linked to politics, cultural heritage becomes a vehicle for transformation of society” through cultural values especially, in nation branding. Therefore, heritage preservation could be what would represent the core of the African common identity and transformation of the African Society (ICCROM, 2008).

2.2 The Tangible and Intangible Forms of Heritage

Earlier studies (France-UNESCO, 2006; UNESCO, 2010; Franchi, 2014) noted that the concept of cultural heritage has gradually grown to include all evidence of human creativity and expression: photographs, documents, books and manuscripts, and instruments, etc. either as individual objects or as collections. France-UNESCO (2006) and Franchi (2014) noted that heritage has been divided into two main categories - heritage that presents itself in a material, tangible form for example, archaeology, art, movable objects, architecture and landscape etc. On the other hand, it's intangible heritage which demonstrates the cultural wealth of a given society but more vulnerable than material heritage and could disappear with its traditional custodians if measures are

not put in place to protect it. Intangible heritage includes traditions such as oral history, performing arts, social practices, traditional craftsmanship, rituals, knowledge and skills that are passed on from generation to generation within a community, (Riches Resource, 2014; UNESCO, 2017; CRATerre-ENSAG, 2006; Franchi, 2014). As fragile as intangible cultural heritage may be, it remains an important factor in maintaining cultural diversity in the face of the dynamic digital world (UNESCO, 2017). The foundation of intercultural dialogue rest on understanding intangible cultural heritage of different communities; which leads to mutual respect for other ways of life (UNESCO, 2017; Petronela, 2016). The significance of intangible cultural heritage may not only be the cultural manifestation itself but also the wealth of knowledge and skills that is transmitted through it from one generation to the next (South African National Heritage Council, 2017). The fact that indigenous communities identify themselves with the natural landscape makes towns, underwater heritage, and the natural environment to also be considered as part of cultural heritage (Franchi, 2014; Survival, 2018; UN-Indigenous people, n.d.). This may suggest that minority groups, mainstream social groups within a State and every nation, whether developed or Third World, benefit in various ways from the social and economic values of this transmission of traditional knowledge (UNESCO, 2003; Petronela, 2016; UNESCO, 2017). This implies that Cultural Heritage reaches its full significance when it clearly reflects on the knowledge and values that represent its importance and give meaning to its existence (CRATerre-ENSAG, 2006). In other words, all cultures, whether tangible or intangible, have both material and creative values as they are the reflection of the people creativity and uniqueness (The South African National Heritage Council, 2017; Riches Resource, 2014; UNESCO, 2017).

In relation to Africa, the Director General of ICCROM, Mounir Baochenaki, expressed that although the African continent has numerous traces that each represent a period or notable event in its long history, “one of the silent characteristics of the African people is their relationship with nature. Often, they have been able to shape nature, working with it and using the traditions, knowledge and know-how that they wisely adopted (ICCROM, 2008, p.v). The special relationship between the African people and nature has made it possible for them to discover many spectacular cultural landscapes and a variety of

sacred places which all form part of the basis of their beliefs, practices and “rules that are, in fact, genuine lessons in sustainable development, well before the concept became trend in modern-day society,” (ICCROM, 2008, p.v).

The question one may then ask is how such a rich heritage could improve the economic well-being of such communities. Khan (2014) then explains that indigenous knowledge rightfully belongs to the people who use it within the context of their local environment for survival. This implies that, apart from the proud representation of indigenous people’s identity, heritage sites for example national parks, museums, old towns, stately homes, and traditional landscapes should provide economic support for indigenous communities by creating employment through museums, exhibitions that attract tourists as well as archives and sites (Barnes & McPherson, 2019; McPherson et al., 2017; Rivera, 2015; Moualla & McPherson, 2019; Riches Resource, 2014; UNESCO, 2017; Khan, 2014). In other words, loss of cultural material may have contributed to the diminished role of museums in the economic development of indigenous African societies as estimates on African cultural material out of Africa is high (Sithole, 2011). Therefore, there are concerns that the natural assets that African Indigenes have been using for survival could becoming assets of multinational corporations, (Shiva, 2000; Khan, 2014). Barnett (2001, para. 3) seems to agree to that as argued that for “thousands of years, African tribesmen have eaten the Hoodia cactus to stave off hunger and thirst on long hunting trips” but the Hoodia was “at the center of a bio-piracy row” as “Campaigners say the cactus has attracted the interest of the Western drug industry”. Shiva (2000) then argued that international formalities like patents and intellectual property rights which are supposed to prevent piracy, would have to do more to protect traditional knowledge of indigenous people.

2.3 Conflict and Consensus

Sindima (2009) and Gumo et al. (2012) argued that the Africa indigenous people’s philosophy on sustainable resource utilization and nature conservation is rooted in their cultural beliefs. In other words, major environmental protection efforts and the control of

resources are influenced by cultural spirituality and are supported by religious beliefs and taboo systems that reserve respect for nature (Gumo et al, 2012; UNESCO, 2010).

In comparison, Landowners in the developed world are private individuals, corporate investors, or the state which may suggest that the land could be sold at the will of the owner (Agbiji, 2015; Mulwafu, 2004). For indigenous people, land is a communal property with a collective responsibility to preserve it (UNESCO, 2010; Context Institute, 1985, 1997; UNESCO, 2010). This suggests that the idea that the land can be owned, that it can belong to someone even when left unused or uncared for, may not be native to indigenous communities in Africa (UNESCO, 2010; Sakupapa, 2012). Although indigenous people vary widely in their customs, culture, and impact on the land, indigenous people embrace the land as the source of their existence and a gift from their creator that nourishes, supports, teaches and the source of their origin and identity (Alternation, 2013; UNESCO, 2010). This may suggest that the interdependence between nature and humans is acceptable to African indigenous communities. The communities usually believe that life is only possible if natural resources continue to be available for human use (Mulwafu, 2004; Rusinga et al, 2010). This automatically assigns a responsibility to everyone to make sure that resources are not depleted (Gumo et al, 2012). To indigenous communities, conservational values and practices are considered as their spiritual and social responsibilities that maintain their identity and make it possible for survival and not regulations passed down to them by any higher authority (Rusinga et al, 2010; Gumo et al, 2012).

The strong interdependence between nature and indigenous communities exposes indigenous people to face direct consequences of climate change (Survival, 2018; UN-indigenous people, n.d.). For example, Survival (2018) believes that in the Arctic it is not only the ice that is melting as a result of climate change but also the lives of the Inuit are dramatically affected to the extent that many coastal villages are worried about where to find a safe place to move entire communities. Many tribal communities are predicted to suffer from more droughts and higher temperatures in the Amazon (Survival, 2018). In Africa, Indigenous people in Africa's Kalahari Desert are forced to live around government drilled sources of water and depend on further government support for their livelihood due to rising temperatures, dune expansion and increased wind speeds which have resulted

in a loss of vegetation, and negatively impacted pastoral farming practices (Barnett, 2001; UN-Indigenous People, n.d.). All these findings might have urged the UN Secretary-General Ban Ki-moon, to state that he was ‘convinced that climate change, and what we do about it, will define us, our era, and ultimately the global legacy we leave for future generations’ (UN-Indigenous People, n.d., climate change, para. 1).

This may be suggesting that measures to mitigate climate change may also go a long way to protect indigenous people and their cultures. However, it was argued that climate change mitigation measures such as forest conservation, violate indigenous people’s rights and make it easier for authorities to, exploit and sometimes destroy their land – like climate change itself (Survival, 2018; Barnett, 2001). Such potential threats of climate change mitigation to indigenous people very existence bring out the human rights effect in climate change policies as issues of human rights and inequality to indigenous people (Barnett, 2001; UN-Indigenous People, n. d.).

Although the impact of climate change rest on indigenous landscapes, indigenous communities are responding and adapting in unique ways in their everyday lives (The United Nations University, 2012). Tribal people “resilience is rooted in traditional knowledge, as their capacity to adapt to environmental change is based first and foremost on an in-depth understanding of the land” (The United Nations University, 2012, para. 1). Further, UNESCO (2010) believes that traditional ways of life have proved highly durable and hunting and fishing have allowed the Inuit to survive in the Arctic; nomadic pastoralism provides a livelihood for people in the arid Sahelian region of Africa; shifting cultivation has sustained hundreds of distinct cultures in the fragile ecosystem in the Amazon and the forests of South-east Asia. Vandana Shiva, an icon for Third World Knowledge Rights, Shiva (2000) statistically noted that in spite of the challenges facing indigenous people in sub-Saharan Africa, women cultivate 120 different plants, African home gardens have more than 60 species of trees, rural families in the Congo eat leaves from more than 50 species of their farm trees. This successful way of indigenous life in even fragile habitats is because the indigenous people “use their unique knowledge of the environment not to exploit nature but to co-exist alongside it (Shiva, 2000; UNESCO, 2001)

In comparison to modern way of life, UNESCO Teaching and Learning for a Sustainable Future, UNESCO noted that, “non-indigenous people have not been able to survive in these extreme conditions without destroying the balance of the ecosystem”. (UNESCO, 2001, p.18/50). It then makes sense when Shiva remarked, “while women and small peasants feed the world through biodiversity, we are repeatedly told that without genetic engineering and globalisation of agriculture the world will starve” (Shiva, 2000, para. 19). This may be suggesting that indigenous people play important role in mitigating climate change. As Khan (2014), in an article *A New Kind of Colonialism* believes that knowledge of the natural world is beyond science, the question one may then ask is whether the resilience and knowledge of indigenous people have been considered by industrial advocates as part of efforts to mitigate global warming.

On the contrary, some Indigenous Advocates believe that although the industrial world is facing an ecological crisis, few industrial economists would admit they could learn from indigenous people as their economies are often called primitive, their technology dismissed as Stone Age, and most governments assume they can benefit only from salaried employment (Makinde & Shorunke 2013; Shiva, 2000; UNESCO, 2001; Survival, 2014). Yet, Biotech industry is making profit from resources from Indigenous environments (Khan, 2014).

As the environmental problems are becoming more and more complex and threatening to mankind (Maila, 2001), humanity needs to develop other systems of knowledge: whether indigenous or modern; Western or African, must be explored and their valuable capitals in terms of wisdom, values and skills be integrated into various policy frameworks for sustainable development, (Maila & Loubser, 2003). In efforts to discover important new cures for diseases such as AIDS and cancer, indigenous knowledge may be helpful (UNESCO, 2001). In other words, tapping into the intellectual resources associated with Indigenous Knowledge may not be only cost effective but could also enhance environmentally and ecologically sensitive activities in the world (O’Donoghue et al., 1999 cited in Maila & Loubser, 2003; Semali & Kincheloe 1999, cited in Mutekwe 2015).

This then brings to mind the call to join hands in scientific case studies in order to understand indigenous philosophies to the environment, their analytical knowledge in environmental change and their way of adapting to change in general (The University of New Castle-Australia, 2018).

In terms of globalization and its impact on the African Cultural Heritage, Dukor (2010) and Umeogu (2013) emphasized that Globalization has shrunk the world and made it possible for minorities to gain a sense of belonging in the sense that one can be updated on what is happening around the globe (Umeogu, 2013). However, others (Arowolo, 2010; Daramola et al, 2015; Richstand & Anderson, 1981), seem to disagree as they describe cultural globalization as the infiltration of foreign cultures into African culture, norms, values, and alteration of African social structure which has negatively affected the behavior of people in numerous ways, and forced many people to assume a lifestyle of self-interest, selfishness, individualism which led many Africans to attitudes and behaviors that are not native to most African communities. To a certain extent, Shiva (2000) agreed and added that globalization of the food system destroys the diversity of indigenous food cultures and their food economies. This was in line with earlier arguments by Lumun (2013) that cultural diffusion had led to modernity, making traditional practices and values in indigenous societies to be considered outdated. As a result, developmental concepts appear to many Africans as adopting western cultural practices and neglecting the African cultural values (Ntalaga, 2005; Arowolo, 2010). A such, Indigenous Knowledge is sometimes perceived as knowledge for the ordinary men and women in rural areas (Maila & Loubser, 2003).

Although Daramola et al. (2015) shared the same point of view that the Western world is using global economic development which in any ways favor the Western countries in what may be described as a one-way flow of media programs, other scholars, (Santos, 2002; Umeogu, 2013) on the other hand, believed that globalization could also be seen as a process by which a network of cultural, political and economic advantages and interests of different people of the world work for their mutual benefit. A such, globalization has increased economic prosperity through mutual penetration of various trends in cultural exchange through arts (Raikhan et al. 2013; Daramola et al, 2015). The

process brought availability of foreign goods, and contributes to the expansion of cultural ties between the people and has created great market economy to the extent that Africa stands to gain in all aspects in sustainable development (Santos, 2002; Raikhan et al. 2013; Daramola et al, 2015). From this perspective, one could then see the mass media, powered by modern communications and technologies, playing very important role in contributing to the socio-economic development of the entire African continent and thereby transmitting African cultural norms, social values and cultural beliefs across all cultures. Daramola et al (2015) added that it is lack of good systems to filter or differentiate the good from the bad, the moral from the immoral, and the fair from the unfair that result in loss of identity, loss of traditional values, and loss of self-pride. In that case, perhaps having a cultural framework with good standards could help filter external content to meet mutual cultural exchange agreements between nations. This means that even in situations where there could be the tendency of loss of the African indigenous cultural identities through globalization, efforts could be put in place to define and maintain such African indigenous cultural identities (Kanu, 2013).

In other words, the full benefits of globalization may be realized if there is mutual cultural definition which is linked to the African concepts of economic, political, and social development values (Kanu, 2013). To achieve this, further scientific studies may go a long way to empower and motivate global policy makers to make the necessary changes to promote mutual cultural benefits. For example, the image of the African indigenous people could improve if indigenous African music and dance could be part of Western mainstream broadcasting programs for the purpose of mutual cultural benefits (Kanu, 2013; Daramola et al, 2015).

CHAPTER 3: PROMOTION AS PROTECTION AND CULTURAL DIPLOMACY

This chapter focuses on the important of promoting mutual understanding through innovative cultural exchange activities such as Arts and sports and how such intercultural engagements could strengthen heart-to-heart contacts. The concept of soft power and how it has become an instrument for a country to enhance its ability to engage with and attract global audiences for prosperity and international influence are outlined and discussed as below.

3.1 Cultural Diplomacy and Soft Power

Some cultural experts, (Nye, 2021; Nye, 2014; McPherson et al., 2017; Cull et al., 2015; Nye, 2017; British Council, 2018; ICD, 2017; Portland, 2016; ICD, 2014; Cummings, 2009; Hwajung, 2011; Saeki, 2002) argued that Cultural diplomacy should be seen, from its multilateral point of view, as an enhancement of mutual cultural policy, cultural exchange and cultural attraction. Cummings (2009, p. 1) believes that the concept of cultural diplomacy “refers to the exchange of ideas, information, art, and other aspects of culture among nations and their people in order to foster mutual understanding”. It then makes sense when Kim (2011, p. 1) in an article, *Cultural Diplomacy as the Means of Soft Power in an Information Age*, referred to Cultural Diplomacy as “forming international bridges and interactions, identifying networks and power domains within cultures and transcending national and cultural boundaries”.

Joseph Nye defines soft power as co-optive power or indirect power which can help in “getting others to want what you want” and it shapes preferences of others by attraction of intangible resources such as universalistic popular culture or political cohesion (Nye, 1990: 31-35). Historically, Portland Soft Power Index Report (McClory, 2015, p.8) and others (Nye, 2014; Nye, 2021) noted that the term “Soft Power” is neither new, nor is its use limited to the developed world. McClory explained that the term was used by Nye “to describe the ability of a country to use attraction and persuasion in the pursuit of foreign

policy objectives, as opposed to force or financial payments” (McClory, 2015, p.8). “The appeal of soft power rests in its promise to deliver key international objectives without the high costs associated with the exercise of hard power” (McClory, 2015, p.8). The concept of soft power then becomes an instrument for a country to enhance its ability to engage with and attract global audiences for security, prosperity, and international influence (Nye, 2014; Nye, 2021; British Council, 2013; McClory, 2015).

As a result, the concept of soft power has moved from university lecture halls to foreign ministries and strategic documents of nations as the term becomes common on news stories and speeches of influential diplomats (McClory, 2015). According to the British Council (2013), recent years have seen the growing interest in cultural relations and cultural diplomacy which led to the foundation of the Institute for Cultural Diplomacy in Berlin, the development of academic courses across the world, and a steady flow of conferences and events. The reasons for this rapid evolution of cultural diplomacy might have been what cultural experts (Rivera, 2015; Cull et al., 2015; Nye, 2017; British Council, 2018; ICD, 2017; Portland, 2016; Kim, 2011) noted that cultural diplomacy breaks down barriers, connects across cultural differences, and engages people’s shared values which all add up to endure positive changes in government. This means that Cultural Diplomacy can effectively facilitates cooperation in spite of policy differences, creates a neutral platform for people-to-people contact, and serves as a flexible and universally accepted vehicle for peace process between countries when diplomatic relations have been strained or are absent (British Council, 2013; Rivera, 2015). The dynamic nature of culture calls for constant innovation to cope with the unique circumstances and challenges that each new period of cultural change may bring with it (Ryan, 2016). Therefore, Cultural Diplomacy could sometimes be the best or even only sustainable and effective option for responding to some particular changing circumstances, political shifts and crises (Ryan, 2016).

3.2 The Need to Revisit Cultural Relations

As cultural history plays a role in promoting and protecting indigenous cultures, the British Council Report (2013) noted that right from the beginnings of humankind, group of people have used diverse forms of cultures to express themselves and show their values, skills and knowledge to others through cultural display, exchange of gifts, trade in all aspects of life. however, it should be noted that globalization and the rise of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) could enhance systematic encounters but mutual receptiveness among cultures may not place all cultures on equal footing if efforts are not made to consider shared cultural values (Iriye, 2017; UNESCO World, 2009; Collins & Khan, 2016). As a result, the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) maintained that that Culture plays important role in the current global political environment and therefore, measures should be put in place to enhance respect for human rights, tolerance, cooperation and mutual solidarity among nations (Jahier, 2017). Therefore, it worth analyzing the various strategic roles that culture appreciation could play in peaceful coexistence in society.

In a proposed EU strategy, the top management of the EU believes that international cultural relations could make the EU a stronger global actor in the world, as culture is a source of inclusive growth and job creation (EU, 2017). The EU's role as a global actor in diversity promotion through international cultural relations is not limited to member states only but is also committed to support and assist third countries, through cultural diplomacy to safeguard the world's cultural heritage, (UNESCO Media Service, 2016). This adds meaning to Sandford Social Innovation Review, that any nation that do not invest “in art and imaginative capacity” would become a “nation unable to solve its problems, incapable of civil discourse, bogged down in a morass of multicultural conflict, and lagging the global innovation marketplace” (Friedenwald-Fishman, 2011, para. 1). The British Council agrees to this by stating that “culture and heritage stimulates tourism, which is significant not only in economic terms, but because tourists then return to their homes with an impression of a nation considerably influenced by their cultural experiences” (British Council (2013, p.8) It was statistically stated that, “Some 57 per cent of tourists say that

culture and heritage are strong influences on their choice of holiday destination; cultural attractions accounted for 18 of the UK's top 20 most visited sites in 2011; and the UK's culture and heritage is estimated to attract £4.5 billion worth of spending by visitors annually" (British Council, 2013, p.8). Therefore, supporting a plurality of co-existing artistic visions by supporting diverse cultures, helping consumers and artists refine their tastes, and paying homage to the past by capturing, reproducing, and disseminating could be important for commercial and an all-inclusive cultural expression, (Friedenwald-Fishman, 2011; Cowen, 2017; EU, 2017).

Although past legacies will continue to reflect as setback to many cultures, and globalization processes in many cases may continue to create inequalities in the cultural field, the progress of human sciences such as ethnographic studies and the recognition of the cultural dimension of human rights have made it possible to arrive at fairer valuations of previously misunderstood cultures and to think in the direction of genuine exchanges between all cultures (UNESCO World Report, 2009; UNESCO, 2016). Focusing on Africa, globalization has made it possible for new forms of creation, production, distribution, access and participation to revolutionize and brought the entire homemade African cultural expressions such as storytelling, music, dance, craftwork and films to professional standards (British Council, 2013; UNESCO, 2016: November 10). Although these changes have brought both opportunities and challenges to the creative chain, the process has improved African cultural impressions and perceptions about people and their cultures across the African continent (UNESCO World Report, 2009; British Council, 2013; UNESCO 2016: November 10). This then makes it important to take a closer look at the relevance of the theory of social capital and cultural tourism as means of cultural heritage protection and promotion.

3.3 The Relevance of Theory - Social Capital and Cultural Tourism, Cultural Heritage Protection and Promotion

Although there is considerable debate about the definition of social capital and its operations (Moscardo et al, 2013; Rodriguez-Giron & Vanneste, 2018), review of literature on social capital definitions across multiple studies (Rodriguez-Giron & Vanneste, 2018; Moscardo et al, 2013; Pawar, 2006; Moscardo, et al., 2017; Johannesson, et al., 2003; Portes, 1998) have revealed some common elements as: trust, networking, collective action, cooperation, shared norms and values, social interaction and relationships. These elements are in line with Rodriguez-Giron & Vanneste (2018, p.23) belief that “Social capital theory explains how resources are mobilised for common purposes, representing a key notion for understanding collective action.” Moscardo et al. (2013, p.223) defined Social Capital at community level as “the trust, obligations, reciprocity, shared values and social identity, and cohesiveness of social relationships within a community.” As such, community level social capital “offers members of the community access to support and resources to pursue various goals, and it is derived from networks, both formal and informal and both within and outside the community, associations and engagement in communal or social activity” (Moscardo et al., 2013, p.223). In this study, my focus is on analysing the structures that would allow social capital to be created among the targeted San community, the dimensions of social capital at community level, and the outcomes that could be achieved from its use for the community.

As to how cultural tourism could boost social capital in the targeted San community, Moscardo et al., (2013) and Mason (2006) noticed that there are both positive and negative tourism impacts on social capital, usually due to community conflict over tourism. Various studies (Rodriguez-Giron & Vanneste, 2018; Moscardo et al., 2013; Ashley, 2000; Jones, 2005; Moscardo, 2012) noted some of the conditions that contribute to conflict as inequitable access to tourism opportunities and benefits, competition for tourist attention, and the development of types of tourism that are inconsistent with community values and perceptions. Although such conflict is seen as depleting social capital by eroding trust and cooperation, it is possible that such a conflict could be managed by

community-based associations and organisations' leadership through shared values and identity (Moscardo, 2012; Finkel, 2010).

It then makes sense when Rodriguez-Giron & Vanneste (2018) and Moscardo et al., (2013) noted that the creation of both local and national networks and associations to be responsible for organising and coordinating tourism activity within a community has a positive impact on social capital. The use of events by local residents as a source of community pride, expression of shared values and identity, to socialise and build bonds with others have positive impact on social capital (Mason, 2006; Moscardo, 2012; Moscardo, et al., 2017). This then suggests the important role strategic events and networking could play in promoting cultural tourism and building social capital in the targeted San community (Struthers & Nzika, 2019). Section (3.4) discusses a need for strategic cultural exchange programs linked to cultural diplomacy and the UN-SDGs policies as means of building social capital for indigenous communities.

3.4 Innovative Cultural Exchange Programs as Channels for Cultural Diplomacy and achievement of SDGs

The International Trade Council believes that Cultural Exchange is “a two-way communications process that involves efforts to promote a nation’s image and values among other foreign audiences as well as to try to understand the culture, values, and images of other countries and their people” (The International Trade Council, 2016, para. 4). This implies that besides learning from one another, cultural exchange creates a chance for people to explore both their differences and their similarities (International Trade Council, 2016). In many ways, even very different cultures may have elements in common, no matter how unique the individual cultural expressions may be (Ryan, 2016). In other words, there is no approach that breaks barriers, connects across cultural differences, and engages people shared values more than cultural exchange programs (Nye, 2021; Nye, 2014; British Council, 2018; ICD, 2017; Portland, 2016; Friedenwald-Fishman, 2011; International Trade Council, 2016; Cull et al., 2015; Nye, 2017;

Cummings, 2009). This means that cultural exchange may give people the opportunity to discover, in non-threatening ways, that they have shared values and shared interests. It can reveal the potential for working together, and create the desire to do so, (International Trade Council, 2016; Ryan, 2016). Ryan maintains that cultural exchange is an important way to reach far and wide to both new and already known cultures, adding that, Artistic performance through cultural exchange carries more values in cross-cultural understanding than just an entertainment. Cultural exchange gives people the chance to experience cultural diplomacy in many ways that would inspire them to embrace cultural diversity (Salzburg Global Seminar, 2014; Ryan, 2016; Friedenwald-Fishman, 2011). In other words, strategic cultural exchange programs have a leading role to play in opening possibilities by creating alternatives to violence (Salzburg Global Seminar, 2014). Cultural exchange programs can help create trust, encourage empathy, raise awareness and inspire tolerance among people from different cultural backgrounds and beliefs (Salzburg Global Seminar, 2014).

Perhaps it was for this reason that the International Trade Council (2016) noted that it has become more important to promote mutual understanding through innovative cultural exchange activities such as Arts and sports in order to strengthen heart-to-heart contacts in society. In a conceptual paper addressed to the UN Secretary-General at a meeting on intercultural dialogue for peace and security, concerns were expressed those peaceful relations among people and nations were threatened in the contemporary world (UN Security Council, 2010). UNESCO also maintained that information and communication networks are enhancing contacts between different cultures and making it possible for mutual knowledge exchange (UNESCO World Report, 2009) “Yet it would be a mistake to underestimate the tenacity of prejudice, the depth of the reflex that prompts us to define our identity in opposition to others” (UNESCO World Report, 2009, p.57/420)

On his part, the UN Secretary-General, Mr. Ban Ki-moon, responded that Intercultural Dialogue would not only defuse tensions and keep situations from escalating, but it could also promote reconciliation in the aftermath of conflict and introduce moderate voices into polarized debates, (Ki-moon, 2010). He added that “at a time when prejudice and hatred

are all too common, when extremists seek new recruits through incitement and identity-based appeals, and politicians used divisiveness as a strategy to win elections, dialogue could be an antidote,” (Ki-moon, 2010, remarks). The UE added that intercultural dialogue would not only help to strengthen cooperation on cultural heritage, but it would also demonstrate the value of cultural diversity and human rights which would go a long way to promote understanding within and between societies, (EU, 2017). This belief might have influenced the EU’s strategic approach in external relations with a focus on culture in development cooperation, focusing on dialogue, mutual listening and learning simultaneously (Franke & Mellar, 2017).

According to Harvard Business Review, (Molinsky & Jang, 2016), focusing on cultural differences alone can have its downsides. In other words, common practices among cultures, regardless of their geographical locations, could stand a chance of improving intercultural dialogue (Molinsky & Jang, 2016: January 20). Therefore, sports, Art and Music are some of the common distinctive parts of broader cultures which play important role in creating mutual cultural experiences (Arts Council England, March 2014; British Council, 2013; Morais, 2011). Cultural Experts (Arts Council England, 2014; British Council, 2013) noted that promoting intercultural dialogue within societies could be seen as promoting dynamic interactions between ethnic groups, cultural and religious communities in order to realize the full benefits of cultural diversity. This may imply listening to others, being open to dialogue and making an effort to understand others for the beauty and benefits of cultural diversity, (Prodi, 2002; Friedenwald-Fishman, 2011).

For example, the International Trade Council (2016) believes that cultural diversity in a form of Arts Diplomacy stands a chance to promote mutual cultural interactions in a holistic manner. According to the Sandford Social Innovation Review, “there is no investment that connects us to each other, moves us to action, and strengthens our ability to make collective choices more than arts and culture” (Friedenwald-Fishman, 2011, para. 7). Langer (1966) also shares the same views as expressed that every culture develops some kind of art as part of its language. In other words, arts and culture can help us understand our humanity and the historical conditions we live in, but importantly inspires

us to think about reality and the possible changes we may need to make (Morais, 2011; Arts Council England, 2014). McPherson et al., (2017) believe that Arts have memorable ways of expressing important values and qualities of life in society. For example, values and qualities such as the expression of human thoughts, views, hopes and aspiration as well as sadness are all embedded in Arts (McPherson et al., 2017). It can entertain, inform, inspire or educate making it an agent of positive change in society (McPherson et al., 2017; Morais, 2011; Arts Council England, 2014). The Arts, as catalyst of change, can be used as a medium of confronting personal, social or political issues through criticism of the world as it is and a vision of the world as it might be, (Morais, 2011). This makes Arts very important for the development of democracy and society. For example, artwork can commemorate communal or individual great accomplishments or seeks to please people with beauty and hopes (Morais, 2011). In other words, one of the many importance of art is to refresh people and remind them of better things or transcendent realities, (Arts Council England, 2014). Arts in terms of inspiring and empowering the vulnerable in society, reminds us of our strength, weaknesses and aspirations (McPherson et al., 2017; Arts Council England, 2014; Morais, 2011). A provoking piece of art can be used to change people in society through compelling self-questioning that could lead individuals or groups to be aware of their potentials and vulnerability (Morais, 2011; Bisaria, 2017). It is then for a good reason that organizations including the British Council develop and implement innovative arts-based cultural exchange programs that would promote human connections and enhance the exchange of experiences and ideas among nations in order to deal with global issues such as empowering the vulnerable, promoting economic prosperity, freedom of expression and combating climate change (Arts Council England, 2014; Gummow, 2014; Ryan, 2016). Innovative and creative cultural exchange programs such as sports, together with local community members have great impact on both the athletes and on the communities (Kyle et al., 2017; Ryan, 2016). For example, persons with disabilities often face societal barriers as disability usually results in negative perceptions and discrimination in many societies (UN Division of Social Policy and Development Disability, 2016; Kyle et al., 2017). Various Researchers then suggested that sport and Adapted Physical Activity (APA), as means of cultural exchange, could play a key role in the lives of people with and without disabilities (Kyle et al., 2017;

Sportanddev.org, n. d.). In volatile situations which call for series of high-level meetings between top diplomats, cultural exchange interactions through sports could strengthen understanding, trust, and very important factors in resolving disputes and expanding bilateral cooperation and interests (South China Morning Post, 2017). For example, experts believed that the 2018 Winter Olympic Games brought an opportunity for diplomacy to help reduce tensions on the Korean Peninsula (Easley, 2018; Green, 2018; Snyder, 2018). This followed North Korea's decision to dispatch top level diplomats to South Korea as part of a delegation to the PyeongChang Winter Olympics, an action believed to have opened up possibility for sports diplomacy to develop sustainable relations between the two countries (Green, 2018).

As to how cultural exchange linked to the UN-SDGs policies could build social capital for indigenous communities, it worth noting that the UN Agenda for Sustainable Development, comprising 17 Sustainable Development Goals And 169 Targets, is a universal concept to transform the world by 2030 (UNESCO, 2018; Petti et al., 2020). The SDGs are a shared set of aspirations to ensure that change takes place at the global, national and local levels (British Council, 2020; UNESCO, 2018). The SDGs aim to integrate and balance the three crucial components of sustainable development – economic, social and environmental (UNESCO, 2018; UNESCO, 2017). Although the international community admits the role of culture as a driver of sustainable development (UNESCO, 2018), critiques (Petti et al., 2020; British Council, 2020) believe that none of the 17 SDGs focuses exclusively on cultural heritage. However, both Petti et al., (2020) and British Council (2020) acknowledged that the Agenda 2030 made reference to heritage in SDG 11.4 and indirect reference to other Goals. According to UNESCO (2018, p.12) SDG 11.4 focuses on “safeguarding cultural and natural heritage.” Petti et al., (2020, p.6) believes that the “SDG11 is the United Nations’ strongest expression ever of the critical role that” cultural heritage will play in sustainable development. Apart from target 11, other crucial references such as 4.7, focuses on promoting knowledge and skills and the appreciation of cultural diversity; targets 8.9 promote sustainable tourism and local culture aligned with target 14.7, promoting the sustainable use of aquaculture and tourism (UNESCO, 2018; UNESCO, 2017; British Council, 2020). Therefore, it is possible to link

the theory of social capital and cultural tourism to cultural exchange and cultural diplomacy as means to achieve the UN- SDGs.

CHAPTER 4: DIGITAL MEDIA LITERACY IN PROMOTING AND PROTECTING INDIGENOUS CULTURAL HERITAGE

4.1 Cultural Diplomacy in an Information Age.

The Internet Society (2015) and Carlisle et al. (2021) believe that the Internet is a unique platform for innovation, creativity, economic opportunities and social inclusion. That adds meaning to Portland (2016) notice that there were over 3.42 billion internet users across the world and that six new users take to the internet every second. In economic terms, Portland believes that the internet economy is worth \$4.2 trillion in the G-20 economies alone as billions of transactions take place online every day. Further, the growth in information technologies brought about the high speed with which information is disseminated around the world, usually through web and app-based platforms (Carlisle et al., 2021). The information age then made it possible for cultural diplomacy to strengthen soft power by attracting other cultures and ideologies through mutual exchange of intelligence and capabilities in various forms (Carlisle et al., 2021; Kim, 2011; Portland, 2016; Burson-Marsteller, 2016)

Perhaps that was why Portland Soft Power Index Report noticed that world leaders, diplomats and foreign ministries with varying levels of enthusiasm and competence, have developed interests to join conversations on major internet platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Snapchat. The report further stated that “the two most popular platforms, Facebook and Twitter” have seen a “huge uptake from governments to social media” (Portland, 2016, p.22/120). For example, Barack Obama did not only open his personal presidential POTUS Facebook page on 9 November 2015 (Alejandro, 2015; Burson-Marsteller, 2016) but he also wrote in his first post ‘Hello, Facebook! I finally

got my very own page. I hope you'll think of this as a place where we can have real conversations about the most important issues facing our country - a place where you can hear directly from me, and share your own thoughts and stories' (Alejandro, 2015, para. 2).

As to how such collaborative networks could facilitate interdependence and policy frameworks between nations, Soft Power Experts, Portland (2016) then explained that the ability of a state to engage through digital platforms and collaborative networks are now the engines of global governance and change. On the other hand, Garen (2014) argued that nation states will become much more effective in using the internet as an instrument of political and social control. Elon University (2014) also expressed concerns that communications networks are not merely tools of enforcing existing systems but they also change structures in such familiar systems which could then go on to change our understandings of being human, being social, and being political. However, Gray (2014) expressed hopes that as more of the global population comes online, there will be increased awareness of disparities in developmental issues regarding access to good quality health care, clean drinking water, education, food production and human rights. This means that the rapid growth of the digital communication networks would facilitate the process of bringing people together to share best practices, improve professional skills in all aspects of policies and to build relationships across cultural borders and industries (US Department of State, 2017; Burson-Marsteller, 2016; Portland, 2016).

Therefore, in strengthening intercultural bonds for a speedy development, the growth of digital media has become an important enabler of social and economic change by transforming how organisations and citizens interact and share new ideas and experiences (Carlisle et al., 2021; Gray, 2014; Internet Society, 2015; Burson-Marsteller, 2016).

4.2 Digital Media Adaption in Africa

According to Utley (2019), Africa is known as a great story-telling continent and digital media has presented Africans a great opportunity to shape their own narratives based on their values and norms, partner with one another and to even create modern wealth out of the process. Since the internet became widely accessible “in the 1990s, the Internet has enabled new products and services, improved economic efficiency, transformed access to information, and facilitated greater collaboration between governments, businesses and citizens” (The Internet Society, 2015, overview, para. 2). However, as the digital media technologies are not native to the Africans in the continent, it is obvious that digital media literacy would be a major hindrance to the adoption process. It’s therefore, understandable that GSMA (2015) noted that low literacy, for example in basic and advanced mobile internet use, act as a barrier to increasing mobile internet adoption in the continent. Although developing countries accounted for the majority of the illiterate adults that were reported globally, people in the developing world are adopting mobile technologies at a high rate but mainly for voice calls as many consumers are unable to tap into mobile internet due to the lack of basic literacy and digital skills, (Odendaal, 2015; GSMA, 2014).

Odendaal (2015) believes that “literacy is essential for understanding the mobile phone user interface, reading its display and using its keyboard” adding that “lack of English literacy further prevents many native language speakers from using the mobile internet”. Generally, regions with high levels of illiteracy are also those that lag in take-up of the mobile internet, (GSMA, 2014, p. 7/9). Illiteracy in developing countries remains prevalent in rural communities and among members of poor households including indigenous people as depicted in figure 1, (UNESCO Education for All Global Monitoring Report, 2006).

Figure 1: Literacy rates urban vs. rural 2007-2013. Source: GSMA Intelligence, UNESCO, World Bank, Indian Express, Tribune.

According to UNESCO office in Dakar, (UNESCO-Dakar, 2017) literacy rates in some west African countries were very low. Besides the already general high illiteracy rates stated as “nearly 40% of adults in Sub-Saharan Africa,” it was also revealed that “Digital literacy, which is not formally evaluated in most countries, is an even bigger barrier affecting the creation and usage of local digital content,” citing women as “more likely to cite digital literacy issues than men and also tend to exhibit less confidence with mobile devices than men,” (GSMA, 2015, p. 31). Digital local content was also noted as “a core part of the internet experience that consumers are seeking – whether for localized versions of global services, local entertainment packages or hyper-local information such as bus timetables or commodity prices” (GSMA, 2015, p. 31).

4.3 Growth in the Telecommunications Industry in Africa

According to Portland quarterly report, Karanja (2010), Africa has seen the fastest growth in mobile subscribers in the world, changing the way nations and citizens live with each other in the continent. This improvement has given many Africans the opportunity to interact via social media sites, as they create groups, accounts, pages and posts on social media platforms to promote their interest GSMA (2017: July). The process is not only direct and effective but could also be affordable for the ordinary natives (Karanja 2010: November).

According to GSMA Mobile Economy 2017 analyses, (GSMA, 2017, p. 2), Sub-Saharan Africa recorded 420 million unique mobile subscribers at the end of 2016, equivalent to a penetration rate of 43%. The report noted that the region continues to grow faster than any other region; the compound annual growth rate (CAGR) “of 6.1% over the five years to 2020 is around 50% higher than the global average,” estimating that “the region will have more than half a billion unique mobile subscribers by 2020,” (GSMA, 2017, p. 2), as shown in figure 2.

Sub-Saharan Africa unique mobile subscribers and market penetration

Figure 2: Sub-Saharan Africa unique mobile subscribers and market penetration. (Source, GSMA Intelligence, 2017, p.11).

In terms of mobile devices and internet connection adoption, the GSMA intelligence (GSMA, 2015, p. 2) noted that “migration to higher speed networks and smartphones continues apace, with mobile broadband connections set to increase from just over 20% of the connection base today to almost 60% by the end of the decade,” adding that “falling device prices are encouraging the rapid adoption of smartphones, with the region set to add more than 400 million new smartphone connections by 2020, by which time the smartphone installed base will total over half a billion”. Significant growth in mobile penetration was seen in many countries in the continent (Pew Research Center, 2015;

Lai, 2012). Although PwC (2016) believes that the digital innovation is transforming Africa's economic potential, creating new target markets and unprecedented consumer choice, one may still wonder whether such growth would be sustainable to meet the needs of the ordinary citizens including indigenous people in Africa.

4.4 Digital Media and Heritage Inclusion

In analyzing the role of digital media in promoting and protecting indigenous African cultural heritage, it may make sense to separate digital adoption from an all-inclusive cultural progress. As discussed (section 4.2), there has been a lot of progress in digital adoption across various aspects of mainstream development in Africa, for example in healthcare delivery, financial sector and in telecommunications. However, digital progress towards cultural promotion needs to be directed to address key needs and challenges facing people in rural communities (Carlisle et al., 2021; GSMA, 2014; Odendaal, 2015). Mobile mass connectivity and platforms can only improve indigenous people's ways of life if they create awareness about indigenous values and norms, provide better access to healthcare services, enables financial inclusion through improved ways of basic transactions, empowers indigenous people through online education and creating transparency in governance (GSMA, 2014; Odendaal, 2015; World Economic Forum, 2015; Carlisle et al., 2021). In other words, there is a need for digital inclusion, linked to cultural tourism and building diverse capital in the African context. The approach should be targeted at repackaging community cultural tourism into digital format for both local and international tourists (Carlisle et al., 2021; GSMA, 2014; Odendaal, 2015)

Although Entis (2014) warned that the free flow information networks could stop people from seeking out knowledge and narrow horizons in social realities, others (GSMA, 2015; Lungu, 2017; Gray, 2014; Carlisle et al., 2021) suggested that the advantages of the free flow mobile-based solutions could be more sustainable in addressing social issues in Africa. It then makes sense when GSMA (2015) argued that many of the social challenges that arise in some countries in Africa are as a result of lack of access to essential services due to poor digital infrastructure.

Perhaps if hands-on approaches such as co-designing of digital contents and the related platforms, which should include indigenous people participation in the design processes, could provide strategic channels for digital inclusion. The process of co-design would fully integrate local voices into policy decisions to implement and manage communication practices as well as tourists wishes. The ultimate aim would include providing diverse digital engagement platforms to suit governance framework for cultural tourism in the African context. On the other hand, World Economic Forum (2015) and GSMA (2014) noted that such steps towards digital inclusion among rural population in Africa could be a challenge due to lack of digital skills among the rural population. Section (4.5) below examines the possible challenges in digital inclusion in rural Africa.

4.5 The Challenge in Digital Inclusion.

As important as digital communication has become (Carlisle et al., 2021), the high rate of digital illiteracy in rural Africa and the exclusion of indigenous knowledge from Western education add to the information gap experienced in rural Africa, (Owiny et al., 2014; GSMA, 2014). According to GSMA (2014, p. 35) a “survey of 13,000 people in urban centres in 6 key African countries (Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa and Uganda) found that among nonadopters, lack of knowledge of how to use the internet was perceived as a larger hurdle than coverage or cost”. See figure 3.

Figure 3: Why do people not use the internet? Source: GSMA 2014/Google and Basis Research

This then calls for organizations to minimize barriers and support digital adoption in Africa (World Economic Forum, 2015). In order to minimize barriers and ensure user familiarity with internet access and internet technologies, linked to the relevant local content, mobile operators and organisations are collaborating to tackle the issues of awareness as well as initiatives to facilitate digital literacy in Africa (Cooper, 2017). It then makes sense that Mark Zuckerberg, Facebook’s co-founder and chairman, was willing to improve internet access through the Free Basics Initiative project in Africa (Shearlaw, 2016). Although critics see Zuckerberg’s plan to wire up the African continent as “a cynical marketing ploy” and not “a philanthropic gesture,” Zuckerberg maintained that access to the internet is a basic human right (Shearlaw, 2016, headline, para. 1). Many organizations including IBM, the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), Google etc. have also outlined various projects set to train many Africans in digital skills (Vanguard Media Limited-Nigeria, 2017; Nigeria Communications Week, 2014; Cooper, 2017).

However, in promoting digital literacy and adoption in Africa, it worth noting that digital technologies are not native to the African cultures. Therefore, it is important to

synchronize the digital growth with the values the African cultures hold for the citizens (Cooper (2017; Owiny et al., 2014). In other words, as oral cultures, the other challenges that would keep threatening the African Cultural Heritage would be the disappearance of traditional knowledge and skills due to deliberate or inadvertent destruction of indigenous knowledge, memory loss or death of elders (Owiny et al., 2014; Vanguard Media Limited-Nigeria, 2017; Nigeria Communications Week, 2014). This then calls for a need for strategic union between digital media, indigenous cultural heritage and cultural diplomacy linked to the acceleration of UN-SDGs.

4.6 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this study is guided by critical theory from the perspective of cultural diplomacy linked to social capital and cultural tourism (Nye, 2017; ICCROM, 2018; UNESCO-Courier, 2017; British Council, 2018; Portland, 2016; Cull et al., 2015; Cull et al., 2015; Berendzen, 2010; Bolaños, 2013; Asghar, 2013; Crossman, 2019, para. 8; Horkheimer, 1982; Said, 1978). The framework is set to conduct convergent mixed-methods case study among policymakers and forced-relocated San people in Platfontein, South Africa. The detailed literature review has revealed that unless strategic measures are put in place to protect indigenous people, governments and their developmental projects and the SDGs implementation processes could lead to accelerated loss of indigenous people cultural resources, their means of survival, which could all lead to their cultural assimilation and erosion (UNDP, 2015; OHCHR, 2012; UNESCO World Heritage Centre, 1992-2017). Rodriguez-Giron & Vanneste (2018, p.28) noted that “Social Capital theory offers grounds to study the gap between statements of intention and effective efforts. Understanding this gap can greatly contribute to the improvement of a

destination's ability to maximize benefits in more sustainable ways." However, McGehee et al. (2010) and Moscardo et al., (2013) noted that the concept of social capital is difficult to follow as its characteristics are context dependent. Therefore, different studies in both cultural and non-cultural-related fields propose diverse methodologies and methods in applying social capital theory to understand collective actions (Moscardo et al., 2013; Taylor, 2016; McGehee et al., 2010; Rodriguez-Giron & Vanneste, 2018).

Therefore, as discussed in the detailed literature review and also in section 9.5 and figure 8, the theoretical framework is based on the research objective 3: To contribute to a growing body of theory that demonstrates the role of cultural heritage protection and promotion as a form of cultural diplomacy.

CHAPTER 5: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

5.1 Introduction

This chapter utilizes autoethnography as the core methodology linked to the concepts of Critical Theory and Cultural Diplomacy as the theoretical framework to conduct convergent mixed-methods case study among policymakers and forced-relocated San people in Platfontein, South Africa. Guba & Lincoln (1994) and Asghar (2013) believe that selecting the appropriate paradigmatic framework is crucial in any research work. The paradigmatic framework defines the ontological, epistemological and methodological dimensions of any research work (Guba & Lincoln, 1994; Richards, 2003; Asghar, 2013). According to Keeves (1997) and Kivunja & Kuyini (2017), the Methodology research paradigm refers to the research design, methods, approaches and procedures used to achieve a research aim and objectives. The researcher follows these outlined processes through the data collection and analysis stages (Creswell, 1998; Hatch, 2002). Therefore,

the major components of this chapter include the relevance of theory of change, the assumptions and justification for the qualitative and quantitative methods, the setting and participant action selection procedures, informed consent and permission procedures, data collection procedures, data quality procedures and data analysis procedures. In addition, detailed descriptions which include my role as the principal researcher, assurance of confidentiality and the credibility of study results are outlined.

5.2 Research Aims and Objectives

Although digital diplomacy and digital inclusion could play an important role in protecting and promoting the San people cultural heritage, I noticed at the very beginning of the field work that the digital element was out of their reach. For example, I realized that among the targeted San people, the individual ability to read or write was very low. Hardly, did I see anybody with a mobile phone. Their main ways of passing on information was through word-of-mouth. On the other hand, the thirty-five (35) policymakers I interviewed at the very beginning of the field work showed high level of digital adoption as they all had mobile phones with internet access. However, I realized that there was no digital media expert among them. It was then understandable when the detailed literature review (Fihlani, 2014; IWGIA, 2006; UN, 2009; Renton, 2009; Flack 2013; Survival, 2014; MRG, 2016; Survival, 2017; GSMA, 2015; GSMA, 2014; Vidal, 2016) suggested illiteracy, lack of digital competence, lack of indigenous cultural awareness, and social hardships as the possible key issues among the target groups. Most of the policymakers at this early stage of the research also described the indigenous way of life as “primitive,” “backwards” and as “a shame to the African identity”. Whilst, this was problematic to the researcher in terms of judgement of the San people and cultural heritage sustainability it was nevertheless an important finding in its own right; this was the views of the policymakers who could help or not with the plight of the San people. Therefore, I had to change my methodology to concentrate more on the alignment of Cultural Heritage and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UN-SDGs) rather than digital diplomacy and digital inclusion. Therefore, my research aim changed: to investigate and explore

sustainable and effective ways that could enhance a two-way approach - Cultural Diplomacy linked to Indigenous Cultural Heritage promotion.

The objectives include:

- 1) To investigate how the San Cultural Heritage can be aligned with the UN-SDGs, especially SDG 11, to protect their Heritage and used as a form of Cultural Diplomacy by the Nation.
- 2) To investigate the awareness, by policy makers and stakeholders of the San cultural heritage as both tangible and intangible assets for promotion and protection by government.
- 3) To contribute to a growing body of theory that demonstrates the role of cultural heritage protection and promotion as a form of cultural diplomacy.

The change of the research objectives away from the original digital diplomacy to concentrate on the UN SDGs aligned with cultural heritage resulted in some implications: More time was needed for extra work in the field, mainly to build trust and to cope with culturally sensitive issues among the target groups before and during the one-on-one interviews. More time was also needed for an in-depth literature review to assess the political and cultural situation of the San People in relations to the UN SDGs. The financial implications were mainly the high cost in re-printing new questionnaires and the cost of living abroad - hotel accommodation, transportation etc. which all increased the study cost significantly.

5.3 Autoethnography as the Core Research Methodology

Autoethnography is the core methodology I used to conduct this study. According to Poulos (2021, p.4) Autoethnography “is an autobiographical genre of academic writing that draws on and analyzes or interprets the lived experience of the author and connects researcher insights to self-identity, cultural rules and resources, communication practices, traditions, premises, symbols, rules, shared meanings, emotions, values, and larger social, cultural, and political issues.” Autoethnographic process gives guidance and

explains how the researcher makes sense of specific academic theories and conceptual framework to realize the research objectives (Hughes, 2018; Chang, 2008; Hattangadi, 2019). This makes autoethnography the appropriate methodology for me to realize the theoretical framework set out to conduct this study. In other words, the autoethnographic study would make it possible for me to use narrative inquiry to fully explore the study aim and objectives (Ellis, & Bochner, 2000; Méndez, 2013; Chang, 2008; Hattangadi, 2019) which are outlined within the framework of critical theory linked to social capital and tourism. This is in line with the study quest to investigate social realities of forced-relocated San people from their ancestral lands due to political and socio-cultural issues.

Blundell (2001) and Yin (1994) believed that in a research about indigenous people, where meaning is given more priority over generalisations, using autoethnography and phenomenology are particularly useful. In order to achieve a balanced representation of viewpoints in an autoethnographic study, good relationship between the researcher and the group being studied is essential and requires a good level of mutual trust and understanding (Dammak, n.d.; Mertens, 2008; Reed & Ellis, 2019). In other words, unique relationships between the researcher and participants, often from the autoethnographic perspective, are essential in a research that is targeted at discovering personal experiences among indigenous people (Whitinui, 2013; Poulos, 2021; Adams et al., 2015; Shannon-Baker, 2016; Reed & Ellis, 2019). Some cultural organizations (UNESCO, 2017; UN-IPMG, 2019; Portland, 2016) advocated good intercultural relations through means of cultural exchange in promoting cultural diplomacy.

However, some scholars (Krauss, 2005; Coll & Chapman, 2000; Cousins, 2002) expressed concerns about the issues of reflexivity in autoethnographic research as interaction between the researcher and the subjects of study, in a process of obtaining data, stands a chance of changing both the researcher and the subject of study. Others (Holt, 2003; Sparkes, 2000; Anderson, 2006) also criticized the methodology for not having a clear distinction between the researcher-participant relationship which may challenge the scientific credibility of the methodology. On the hand, Whitinui (2013) and Poulos (2021) emphasized a need to consider the *epistemological perspectives* in indigenous autoethnography. Guba & Lincon (1994) and Kivunja & Kuyini (2017)

explained that the epistemology of a research is the relationship between the researcher, as the investigator, and what is already known. Hence critical theory researchers emphasize the importance of the interactive relation between the researcher and the *Participants Action* and the impact of social and historical factors that influence them (Krauss, 2005; Dammak, n.d.). Whitinui (2013, p.467) highlighted that “Indigenous autoethnography by its very definition asks us to consider epistemological perspectives equally and to draw together self (auto), ethno (nation), and graphy (writing). It also asks researchers interested in this method to consider their own level of connectedness to space, place, time, and culture as a way of (re)claiming, (re)storing, (re)writing, and (re)patriating our own lived realities as indigenous peoples.”

Therefore, my epistemological stance is an interpretivist one that fits well with an autoethnographic methodology. Epistemologically, interpretivists adhere to a subjectivist view in that subjective meanings and subjective interpretations have great importance (Pring, 2000; Dammak, n.d.) in what constitutes reality. Crotty (1998), cited in (Dammak, n.d., p. 5) argued that the object ‘cannot be adequately described apart from the subject, nor can the subject be adequately described apart from the object.’ This implies that, the relationship between the knower and the subject to be known is not of detachment, but rather of involvement and interaction (Krauss, 2005; Dammak, n.d.). *Critical epistemology* advocates “subjectivism which is based on real world phenomena and linked with societal ideology” (Scotland, 2012, p. 13). In other words, Knowledge is both socially constructed and influenced by power relations from within society. Scotland cited Cohen et al. (2009, p. 27) in an explanation that, ‘what counts as knowledge is determined by the social and positional power of the advocates of that knowledge’ (Scotland, 2012, p. 13). In such a culture of governance, academic and scientific communities, which are in charge of validating and legitimizing knowledge claims may unintentionally not contribute to the liberation of the marginalized (Crotty, 1998; Siegel, 2006) like the targeted San people in society (Survival, 2014). Regarding Indigenous Knowledge, different organizations may have differing beliefs and opinions. For example, indigenous knowledge advocates like Survival International and some nation-states who displace indigenous people from their ancestral lands (Survival, 2014) may have different opinions on indigenous issues and for that matter, may have different agendas on what constitutes indigenous people

cultural heritage. Therefore, critical paradigm argues that reality is alterable by human action (Scotland, 2012; Crotty, 1998).

The ontological philosophy in this study is keen on guiding the conceptual framework to address cultural and economic realities among the targeted San people. This then reflected on Kivunja & Kuyini (2017) highlights that ontological research paradigm is a branch of philosophy concerned with the assumptions we make in order to believe that something makes sense or is real, or the very nature or essence of the social phenomenon we are investigating. “Ontological assumptions are concerned with what constitutes reality” (Scotland, 2012, p. 9). This means that the Researcher needs to approach the situation bearing in mind the difference between how things really are and how things really work (Scotland, 2012; Scott & Usher, 2004). Scotland (2012) argued that the ontological position of the critical paradigm is historical realism. Historical realism is the view that reality has been shaped by social, political, cultural, economic, ethnic, and gender values (Scotland, 2012; Guba & Lincoln, 1994; Asghar, 2013; Dammak, n.d.). In other words, realities are socially constructed entities that are under constant internal influence (Scotland, 2012; Asghar, 2013). Therefore, my choice of autoethnography as the core methodology to conduct the study shows how I would manage all external influential factors alongside my own reflections to realize the study aim and objectives. My rich intercultural experiences then became some of my core competences in the study.

The analysis above then justified my choice of methodology and my position as indigenous African autoethnographic researcher in this study. My position was further validated by Adams et al. (2015, p.2) as explained that the autoethnography research method “uses deep and careful self-reflection—typically referred to as “reflexivity”—to name and interrogate the intersections between self and society, the particular and the general, the personal and the political.” Hughes (2018, p.40) advocated that “self-reflective critique required to complete” a PhD level autoethnographic study is “acceptable, even desirable, and valid approach.” Therefore, my stand point as a native autoethnographic researcher would also be an empowering process for me as well as other African auto-ethnographers from diverse cultural backgrounds. Perhaps it was for

these reasons that various studies (Ellis, & Bochner, 2000; Méndez, 2013; Chang, 2008; Hughes, 2018; Hattangadi, 2019) outlined that autoethnography research methodology is unique because it is self-focused, and context-conscious. This systematic and intentional approach to socio-cultural understanding of social situation sets autoethnography apart from other qualitative research methodologies (Ellis, & Bochner, 2000; Méndez, 2013; Chang, 2008; Hattangadi, 2019).

In terms of data quality, Adams et al. (2015) and Whitinui (2013) noted that the process involved in turning autobiographical field dairies into autoethnography is a holistic approach in research and therefore enhances the overall research quality. Hughes (2018) and others (Poulos, 2021; Ngunjiri at el., 2010, Chang, 2008; Ellis, & Bochner, 2000) described the process as a methodological step that requires the auto-ethnographer's deep cultural awareness, ability to find a balance between multiple approaches, and remaining calm in uncertainty. This suggests that autoethnographic data collection processes are usually intertwined and interactive with data analysis and interpretation linked to personal experiences (Chang, 2008; Hughes, 2018; Méndez, 2013). This means the analytical and interpretive processes go alongside data collection - critical evaluation approach that empowers autoethnographic researchers to refine their criteria which will in turn shape the final phase of their analysis and interpretation process (Whitinui, 2013; Poulos, 2021; Ellis & Bochner, 2000; Chang, 2008; Hughes, 2018; Méndez, 2013).

Various studies (Whitinui, 2013; Poulos, 2021, Hughes, 2018; Adams, 2017; Ngunjiri at el., 2010; Ellis & Bochner, 2000; Méndez, 2013; Chang, 2008; Hattangadi, 2019) added that autoethnography makes it possible for ethnographic research to use self-reflection and writing skills to explore sensitive and critical personal experience and connect the findings from autobiographical point of view to bring out the wider political and socio-cultural meanings and understandings to improve policy decisions. Therefore, autoethnography is a core ethnographic research methodology through which I can explore and portray the targeted San people culture in South Africa where a phenomenon is being experienced (Hughes, 2018; Ellis & Bochner, 2000; Méndez, 2013).

The ethnographic approach is a qualitative method for a study of people in their own environment through the use of methods such as participant observation and face-to-face interviews (Reed & Ellis, 2019; O'Neill & Perivolaris, 2015; Brown & Hill, 2006). The holistic nature of ethnography makes it possible, as a discipline, to look at the past, present and future of a community across time and space, (Brown & Hill, 2006). This brings to light the remarks of Krüger (2008, p. 13) that ethnography as a qualitative research method is “located within the interpretive paradigm that generates knowledge from people’s shared understandings and negotiation within a historical and social context”. This is particularly useful in the context of the targeted San people where the understanding of their historic and cultural positions, linked to the context of their current lives is crucial. This could give highlights on ways and means to align the San Cultural Heritage with the UN-SDGs for the affected San to reconnect to their heritage and build social capital.

As Interpretive researchers use data collection methods which enable them to achieve deeper understanding of the emotions, experiences as well as perceptions of the subject matter under investigation (Morse & Chung, 2003; Punch, 2009; Coyle & Williams, 2000; Morse & Chung, 2003; Schulze, 2003), the challenge in this study was for me to choose the appropriate data collection methods which would suite the purpose of the case study. Krauss (2005) and Mertens (2008) then recommended that critical researchers could use data collection methods that best work and serve their critical enquiry. Other scholars (Johnson & Turner, 2003; Punch, 2009; Shannon-Baker, 2016; Lared & Oliveira, 2017) recommended interviews as data collection tool in qualitative research due to their flexible nature; researchers may choose to either design unstructured interviews, structured interviews, semi-structured interviews; or either to triangulate and use any two in a study. As such, interpretive researchers choose the type of interviews that are aligned with the purpose of the study and the research questions; the methods of data collection that enable them to build a relationship of trust with the subjects (Coyle & Williams, 2000; Johnson & Turner, 2003; Morse & Chung, 2003; Schulze, 2003; Dornyei, 2007). Therefore, *Go-Along* interview methods were used to conduct the *participants action* interviews. Go-Along methods are techniques of data collection in which the researcher moves alongside informants to collect information (Madanth, 2018; Carpiano, 2009).

As hunter-gatherers, the San of Southern Africa are generally nomadic (Hitchcock et al., 2006; Totten & Hitchcock, 2010; Survival, 2014; Hitchcock, 2019). As a survival characteristic amongst almost all indigenous societies, particularly where food is concerned (Hitchcock, 2019; All Things South African, 2013; Survival, 2014), the adult San spends most of the day gathering/hunting or searching for medicinal plants (Hitchcock et al., 2006; Totten & Hitchcock, 2010; All Things South African, 2013; Survival, 2014; Motaor Network, 2018; Hitchcock, 2019). This implies that the San/Bushmen are very active people and therefore, would prefer to move around within a suitable space for their daily activities. During an initial visit to the community in Platfontein, South Africa, I noted that the people were stable, friendly, active and free to move around in their wide environment which fitted the *Go-Along* interview methods (Madanth, 2018; Carpiano, 2009).

5.4 The Relevance of Theory of Change and Cultural Diplomacy in the San Heritage Protection and Promotion

The review of literature in this study has revealed that unless strategic measures are put in place to protect indigenous ways of life, the UN-SDGs implementation processes by governments and some international organizations could lead to accelerated loss of indigenous people cultural resources, their means of survival, which could all lead to their cultural assimilation and erosion (UNDP, 2015; OHCHR, 2012; UNESCO World Heritage Centre, 1992-2017). This then highlights a need for a re-negotiated cultural policy framework (see Figure 4 below) whereby the responsible authorities, through a two-way approach, could revisit the affected San people's situation for possible policy-reconsideration in the integration process (UN, 2015; Global Policy Forum, 2002; UNESCO World Report, 2009). A re-negotiated balanced cultural policy framework (see figure 4) means technical interconnections between qualitative phenomenological in-depth researchers, policymakers/implementers and direct contributions from experts from all aspects of policy development including cultural intermediaries (Munatsi, 2011; Azi, 2012; GSMA, 2014; ICD, 2014; McClory, 2015; ICD, 2017; Portland, 2016; British Council, 2018).

Figure 4: A re-negotiated balanced cultural policy framework (British Council, 2018; GSMA, 2014; McClory, 2015)

According to Nye (2017) and Lin & Hongtao (2017), the importance of having such a balanced cultural framework is to help policymakers differentiate between cultural resources and the process involved in bringing out attraction from the resources to create soft power. If that is achieved, then stakeholders could clearly define cultural resources, preserved them, protect them and promote them through creative and innovative means as part of tourism and nation branding for the good of all the citizens, regardless of their cultural differences (Barnes & McPherson, 2019; Nye, 2017; Lin & Hongtao, 2017; McPherson et al., 2017). In order for the study outcome to make a sustainable impact on the lives of the affected San people, it worth recalling Putmans (1993) emphases on bonding and bridging capital for understanding and transitioning change. Therefore, the concept would create awareness among the responsible policymakers so that they could appreciate opinions of the San people and perhaps stand a chance of putting the San cultural heritage on the frontline of policy development. The concept would also help in resolving any outstanding policy issues in regard to local content development and could also provide policy implementers a toolkit for similar intercultural negotiations when necessary (GSMA, 2014; McClory, 2015).

As to how Cultural Diplomacy and cultural exchange could play a role in the process, it worth noting that Cultural Diplomacy promotes the exchange of ideas, information, arts

and culture for mutual understandings amongst citizens or different nations (Cummings, 2009; Cull et al., 2015; Nye, 2017; EUROPA NOSTRA, 2016; South African Department of Arts and Culture, 2019; Hwajung, 2011). Cultural Diplomacy derives its relevance from the worldwide need for mutual exchange and dialogue between cultures to enhance global peace and stability (EUROPA NOSTRA, 2016; Cummings, 2009; ICD, 2014). The South Africa Department of Arts and Culture (2019) believes that historically, nation-states have actively promoted and practiced cultural diplomacy for many decades, and some for more than a century, including Britain with the British Council, Germany with the forerunner of the Goethe Institute, France with the Institut Français, and the Americas with the United States Information Agency and reabsorbed into the Department of State, China with many Confucius Institutes and Cultural Centres world-wide. Although it is not all countries that may already have formal cultural diplomacy policies or established institutes to deal with their foreign cultural relations, almost all countries in the world actively practice cultural diplomacy in one way or the other (Cull et al., 2015; Nye, 2017; South African Department of Arts and Culture, 2019). In recent years the concept has gained recognition in such that the EU's strategic approach to cultural diplomacy is targeted at promoting cultural relations as a way towards sustainable social and economic development, inter-cultural dialogue for global peace and to promote and protect cultural heritage (EUROPA NOSTRA, 2016).

As to how the concept could be applied at grassroot level, in regards to the affected San people situation, the British Council through its *Cultural Heritage for Inclusive Growth* programme believes that a "bottom-up rather than top-down ethos aims to benefit people more directly, by strengthening relationships within communities to foster local ownership, social accountability and shared responsibility, as well as investment in the local economy for more inclusive and sustainable growth" (British Council, 2018, p. 11). As such, the British Council has initiated pilot projects in some developing countries to promote an-all-inclusive cultural promotion for sustainable development (British Council, 2018). Therefore, it may not come as a surprise when British politics were apparently consumed by Brexit and yet the fundamentals of the UK's soft power remained strong as a comprehensive annual soft power index by Portland Communications believed that the

UK was once again the leading soft power nation (Portland Soft Power 30, 2018; British Council, 2018). The UK cultural promotion strategy and success story then drew the attention to the potential of the rich African Cultural Heritage in reshaping the African continent in all aspects of development. The rich African indigenous knowledge systems which formed the basis of Africa's unique establishments such as political systems, religious beliefs, language structure and indigenous technological practices could make Africa a strong global intercultural player in all aspects of development, (Africa Ceremonies, 2013; South African Department of Arts and Culture, 2019). However, as the indigenous tribes like the targeted San people and their cultures are still struggling to maintain their heritage and identity, elements of these unique African traditions could be in danger of disappearing (South African Department of Arts and Culture, 2019; Africa Ceremonies, 2013).

Perhaps it was for this reason that soft power expert, Joseph Nye (Nye, 2017) emphasized the need for nation states to develop and promote the cultural talents of their civil societies as most of a country's soft power comes from its intercultural strength and beauty. This then validates the adopted theory of change in this study as it prioritizes qualitative phenomenological in-depth case study to learn about the effects of urgent issues affecting the targeted San people and serves as a road map for developing and protecting indigenous cultural heritage. The road map would enhance data-driven policy dialogue and decision making in promoting and protecting the San culture. In other words, creating communication platforms for policymakers and indigenous advocates to deliberate on urgent heritage issues could go a long way to enhance stakeholders' efforts towards the realization of the UN-SDGs policies through heritage for inclusive growth (British Council & Russia, 2017; UNESCO, 2016; South African Department of Arts and Culture, 2019).

Theoretically, the Institute for Cultural Diplomacy-Berlin (ICD, 2014, p. 2) believes that "Cultural Diplomacy, when taught and applied at all levels, possesses the unique ability to influence 'Global Public Opinion' and the ideology of individuals, communities, cultures or nations, which can accelerate the realization of the 5 principles of cultural Diplomacy: (1) Respect & Recognition of Cultural Diversity & Heritage, (2) Global Intercultural Dialogue, (3) Justice, Equality & Interdependence, (4) The Protection of International

Human Rights, (5) Global Peace & Stability.” The theory further stated that, “by accomplishing the first principle, one enables the second, which in turn enables the third until the fifth ultimate principle of global peace and stability is achieved,” (ICD, 2014: p. 2). Soft Power Experts (Cummings, 2009; Cull et al., 2015; Nye, 2017; ICD, 2014) further emphasized the importance of respect, transparency and local empowerment as the basis for cultural diplomacy to achieve mutual respect and recognition of cultural diversity and cultural heritage. Therefore, the adopted theory of change is aligned with the study aim and objectives to create awareness about respect and recognition of the San culture as a culture of equal rights and as part of the global universal cultures (Conservation Watch, 2017; OHCHR, 2012; MRG, 2000; UN, 2009; Survival, 2017). This then reflected a need to cooperate and collaborate with authorities and diverse stakeholders during the field work at the destinations (see section 5.5).

5.5 The Need to Cooperate and Collaborate with San Advocates in Southern Africa and Beyond

Struthers & Nzika (2019) believe that collaborating with both formal and informal actors is crucial in building sustainable channels for resource mobilization to empower minorities in micro-entrepreneurship in rural Africa. Therefore, the selection of the targeted collaborators was intended towards a collective resource mobilization to build diverse capital for the targeted San people and to promote cultural tourism for the nation. In the UK’s strategy to enhance and maintain its leading position in international cultural relations, the British Council cultural programmes operate through a wide range of partnerships and collaborations across many countries and around the world (British Council, 2018; Portland, 2016; British Council, 2020). This then gave me a direction to collaborate and work with various authorities and stakeholders - researchers, policymakers, traditional leaders, industry, policy implementers and NGOs as a way to accelerate the SDGs 1, 2, 10, 11, 16 & 17 policies (UNESCO World Heritage Centre, 1992-2017; UNESCO, 2018; British Council, 2020; UNESCO, 2016).

The targeted collaborators as San advocates and the research participants as policymakers/stakeholders were actors who could work collectively to mobilize diverse capital for the San people. In order to realize the study aim and objectives, it became crucial

to link the theoretical framework to cultural exchange and cultural diplomacy as means of accelerating the UN- SDGs. The process involved would require a group of actors to operate collectively towards the promotion of cultural tourism and social capital in which access to diverse resources would become very crucial (Sharpley, 2009; Rodriguez-Giron & Vanneste, 2018). The common forms of such diverse recourses, which are usually in control of individuals, institutions, firms and stakeholders, would include: financial capital, built capital, human capital, technological competences and political will to facilitate both internal and external actions (Rodriguez-Giron & Vanneste, 2018; Sharpley, 2009). This then influenced my strategy to cooperate and collaborate with the advocates, authorities and any possible stakeholders in the research location through the data collection process (See Table 1 below).

Table 1: Key Research Collaborators at Research Destination, South Africa

<p>Research Institutions/San Advocates included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local Advisory Team (people from diverse professional backgrounds) • Sol Plaatje University and McGregor Museum both in Kimberley, South Africa • The South Africa Broadcasting Corporation (SABC) • University of Zimbabwe • The San Research Center at University of Botswana • The Kalahari People Fund, Michigan State University USA • Diamond Creative Vision Hub (DCVH), a South African local NGO based in Kimberley which was already operating in the research community, Platfontein
<p>Authorities/Stakeholders included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key individuals at the Northern Cape Municipal Assembly, South Africa • The Ministry of Economic Development • Platfontein Communal Property Association (CPA) • Houses of Traditional Leaders • The South African National Defense Forces (SANDF) • Airports Company South Africa (ACSA), Kimberley

The selected study location as well as the selected institutions to collaborate and cooperate with emerged from the research documented in the broader review of literature. Although rock art and archaeological evidence can place the San ethnic group as far north as Libya, Egypt, Sudan and Ethiopia, (Kalahari Meerkat Project visitors' guide, n.d.), my collaboration efforts in this research were focused on experts and institutions operating in Botswana, Namibia, South Africa and Zimbabwe where most of the remaining San people are located (Hitchcock, 2019). My aim was to work towards creating a possible regional intercultural platform for San Researchers, San Advocates and Policymakers to continuously deliberate and discuss scientific and policy issues in order to create possible synergies in their efforts to promote indigenous people.

After several email communications to establish possible collaborators within the Southern Africa region, I made an initial familiarization trip to South Africa, Botswana and Zimbabwe to establish one-on-contacts with any possible San advocates including research institutions, NGOs and individuals who could be operating in related field. The main aim was to first of all integrate into the cultures ahead of the main part of the research work. My objectives were to find out the basic underlining issues and possible solutions that would ensure the success of the entire research work. The outcome would help me chose the best possible methodology and strategies in regards to the study aim and objectives.

On arrival in South Africa, I managed to form a Local Advisory Team to coordinate my familiarization and integration processes and to further lead me to possible San advocates so that I could locate a need-based San community in Southern Africa to conduct the research. The team consist of traditional leaders and people from diverse professional background. Together, a community called Platfontein, which hosts forced relocated San people at different stages near Kimberley in South Africa, was identified. With the support of the Advisory Team, I managed to network with some San researchers in South Africa, Botswana, Zimbabwe, Namibia and the USA.

Picture 1: Some of the members of the Advisory Team at the first meeting in Kimberley, South Africa. January 2018

I also concluded a collaboration agreement with a local South African NGO, Diamond Creative Vision Hub (DCVH), a nonprofit business development social enterprise that provides emerging and aspiring entrepreneurs with basic entrepreneurial resources, skills and tools to start, manage and grow their businesses. DCVH then served as my link to other cultural intermediaries and authorities at the Northern Cape Municipality in South Africa to present my research work and get feedback during various stages of discussions.

The first step in contacting the institutions and individuals was that, I first of all sent out my research abstract to several organisations, outlining my interest as wanting to get in touch for us to discuss ideas about promoting and protecting the San cultural heritage. Then I followed up with phone calls, emails and in-person meetings when it was possible. The interested institutions then liked up with me. In our discussions, I would outline my motivation as the need for a collaborative effort to create a common cultural diplomacy platform which could host cultural researchers and policymakers to enhance data-driven policy decisions in Africa. I then stated my passion for a quantitative study to inform a qualitative phenomenological in-depth case studies to learn more about the effects of

global issues such as conservation, migration and globalization on Indigenous Cultures in Africa and in the world at large.

As the outcome of the discussions, they were all inspired by my research topic and methodology and have since collaborated with me in building local networks with community leaders and policymakers, providing me with reference letters for bureaucratic formalities such as visa acquisition etc., so that the research could go on as planned (see correspondence in appendix 5). Key summaries of my notes with target groups during this integration period (see table 2) were recorded and used as a guide for further literature review.

Table 2: Summary Outcome of Integration Visit to Research Location

<p>Key notice about Authorities/policymakers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• A senior policymaker recommended that: <i>“My brother, I think the San people have to be integrated into the modern way of life as a way to secure their livelihood security and better lives”</i>.• Some of the policymakers referred me to comments of a former president who had described the San people way of life as “primitive, backwards and a shame to the African identity.”• During our small talks, I noted that policymakers were regularly checking their mobile phones and would excuse me for few minutes to respond to messages. This then made me curious to find out more about their digital competence levels in regard to digital governance and how digital platforms could be used as possible points to draw their attention to indigenous cultural issues.
<p>Key notes about the San People:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The chief of the targeted San told me that they were not happy at Plantfontein.• They described their everyday lives to me as “hectic and depressive.”

- A San chief challenged me to investigate his opinion through my research work: “...you can talk to my people..., find out from them whether we feel home here or not, whether we are worried about losing our identity or not. Then you can bear me witness...”
- The individual San ability to read or write was very low. Hardly did I also see them with mobile phones.
- Communication transmission was mainly through word-of-mouth.

The summarized outcome in table 2 added meaning to the detailed literature review (Fihlani, 2014; IWGIA, 2006; UN, 2009; Renton, 2009; Flack 2013; Survival, 2014; MRG, 2016; Survival, 2017; GSMA, 2015; GSMA, 2014; Vidal, 2016) which suggested that illiteracy, lack of digital competence, lack of indigenous cultural awareness, and social hardships were the possible key issues among the target groups. Therefore, the outcome of my integration period and the detailed literature review informed the survey questions and wording as well as the choice of research methodology.

At the international level, my advocacy strategy was also embedded in the rest of my presentations across similar networks in the United States of America, Europe and the African continent during the entire study period. I focused on the need to collaborate in search work alongside sharing technical knowledge as catalyst to emancipate the most vulnerable like indigenous people in society. There were high interests for future collaborations and cooperation in all the presentations and discussions across the continents.

Pictures 2-3: Presentations at Notre Dame of Maryland University-USA, the San Research Centre-University of Botswana, 2018.

At international conferences in Europe, my presentations focused on sensitizing the international community on the importance of cultural diplomacy and cultural heritage for peaceful national development in Africa through digital and cultural platforms. I reminded audiences of the political, economic and cultural dimensions of Cultural Diplomacy and Cultural Heritage as a possible two-way developmental approach in Africa. Therefore, I emphasized the continuous need for qualitative phenomenological in-depth case studies as possible ways to address urgent indigenous cultural issues and at the same time accelerate the realization of the UN SDGs as outlined by various studies (UNESCO-Courier, 2017; UNDP, 2015; McPherson et al., 2017; Rivera, 2015; Hitchcock, 2019).

Pictures 4-7: Presenting at various conferences in Berlin-Germany.

See some related links to Youtube video (courtesy of ICD-Berlin)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YpHz-gqUE5M> , <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Sgf3sjbqGXU>

5.6 The Implemented Research Paradigm

The implemented research paradigm presents the ethical consideration and validity of the core methodology adopted to conduct the study. Details of data collection and the data management procedures are also outlined to justify scientific and ethical standards that were followed throughout the study:

5.7 Ethical Consideration and Validity of Autoethnography

The fieldwork process started in January 2018 and covered a period of about two years with periodic visits to the field. Starting from January 2018, I spent a total period of about

two months in the community to complete my integration process ahead of the actual field work. The aim was to allow enough time for me to build trust with the target group. During this integration period, it was widely understood among the chiefs and the people in the community that my research work would be a service to the community and to a large extent, the chiefs took a responsibility as they voluntarily appointed interpreters to assist me to better communicate with the target groups throughout the research work in the community. However, informants' participation remained voluntary.

Within the two years, I made seven (7) visits to the community of which I spent a period of about six (6) weeks in each visit with the San people observing and doing go-along chats and activities with them. During each visit, all the formalized ethical processes signed to guide the research process, including the obtained consent, were reviewed to ensure that their views and wishes had not changed. Otherwise, room could have been created for a review of ethical standards or any concerns. The formalized processes including obtaining their consent and keeping up to high ethical standards, as required by the University of the West of Scotland, set the grounds for me to investigate the targeted San people situation and auto ethnologically describe their critical personal experiences.

Prior to conducting the study, I reviewed the ethics and procedures for conducting research as presented by various scholars (Hudson & Taylor-Henley, 2001; Marshall & Batten, 2004; Lock et al., 2000; Patton, 1990). I strictly adhered to all procedures and regulations prescribed by the University of the West of Scotland. Specifically, I completed the necessary paperwork to gain the approval of the targeted San to conduct research within the community as well as to complete all requirements set forth by the UWS's Ethics Review Board; approval number 2018-4881-3678. With the approval of both parties, I then selected participants for the study and sought their permission using all prescribed procedures.

According to Hudson & Taylor-Henley (2001) and Marshall & Batten (2004), the notion of community control in cross-cultural research demands that research processes empower the community by respecting cultural values and belief systems, which is linked to the basis of ensuring informed consent. As the principle of informed consent demands, (Hudson & Taylor-Henley, 2001; Marshall & Batten, 2004) I gave detailed information to

participants about different aspects of the research in comprehensible language (see Participant Information Sheet in Appendix). Clarifications issues such as the participants' potential role, the nature of the study, my identity as the researcher and the source of funding, the objective of the research, and how the results would be published and used were clarified and repeated whenever it was necessary.

As recommended by Marshall & Batten (2004) and Creswell (1998), participants were then given an Informed Consent Form (see in appendix) to sign as gaining consent approval. Components of this approval included: (1) participation in the study is voluntary, (2) the participants right to withdraw at any time from the study, (3) the purpose of the study and the data collection procedures to be used, (4) an assurance of confidentiality statement, (5) a statement listing any risks to the participants, (6) any expected benefits to the participants, and (7) a signature and date line giving permission to participate in the study.

At the final stage in the informed consent process, I would provide all signed consent documents to all participants prior to the interview. I instructed the participants to review the documents carefully and to ask questions if they did not understand any part of the documents. On the days of the interview, I would review the documents again and provide an opportunity for questions prior to beginning the formal interview. As Weiss (1994) recommended that interviews should be carried out in the comfort of the respondent's normal surroundings, the interviews were carried out in settings that were comfortable for both the interviewer and interviewee, allowing for flexible time frames to ensure that the respondent did not tire, which could reduce the quality of the outcome (Weiss, 1994). The qualitative interviews sometimes went beyond the scheduled time; for instance, from one hour to two hours per meeting, so long as it was comfortable with both parties.

The ethical basis of my choice of the autoethnography was influenced by the study aim to bring a positive change to the research community. The emancipatory element in the study was guided by the theoretical framework, critical theory linked to social capital and tourism. The theoretical framework reflected the advantages of autoethnography outlined by Richards (2008) and Méndez (2013) that the methodology makes it possible for those

being emancipated to represent themselves and speak for themselves instead of being used by others as research objects. Méndez (2013, p.282) highlighted that “autoethnography represents for many the right to tell their truth as experienced without waiting for others to express what they really want to be known and understood.” These advantages outlined were also in line with Said (1978) advocacy for respect and dignity for research target groups like the targeted San people, and not to use them as research objects by researchers.

My role in this study was that of an observer-as-participant; the primary instrument of data collection, coding and analyzing the data from interviews, observations, field notes, document reviews and questionnaire to uncover the emerging concepts and patterns. Creswell (1998) cited in Robertson (2007, p. 48) defined the role of the researcher in a research as ‘The researcher builds a complex, holistic picture, analyzes words, reports detailed views of informants, and conducts the study in a natural setting.’ Others (Merriam, 1988; Yin, 1994; Patton, 1990; Hatch, 2002) also narrated the role of the researcher in research as a data collection instrument.

Therefore, the case study topic was carefully chosen by the “researcher” as Francis Alhassan Adams. My autoethnographic background has enriched me to link my experiences and the study context to the broader methodology adopted in the study. For example, I have already taken related courses during my Masters studies in International Business Management so I am familiar with the concepts and academic claims. I am also of similar ethnic group with similar rural experiences as the people in the research community and with wide range of professional intercultural experiences which would make it easier for me to use Go-Along interview methods to collect qualitative data.

As I am of similar cultural background with similar rural experiences as the San people, I feel I have an obligation to approach them from the perspective of cultural exchange and cultural diplomacy. This would help me prepare the grounds to handle all cross cultural-sensitive issues and make our interactions effective through our diverse cultural background (Chang, 2008).

5.8 Data Management and Storage

The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance (European Commission, 2018; European Union, 2018) was strictly adhered to during the entire study. On 25 May 2018, the EU General Data Protection Regulation superseded the UK Data Protection Act 1998, bringing a 21st-century approach to data protection compliance (European Commission, 2018; European Union, 2018). It expands the rights of individuals to control how their personal information is collected and processed, and places a range of obligations on the researcher to be more accountable for data protection (European Union, 2018). The EU General Data Protection Regulation demands that the researcher demonstrates compliance with the data protection principles (European Commission, 2018; European Union, 2018). This involves taking a risk-based approach to data protection, ensuring appropriate policies and procedures are in place to deal with the principles of transparency and accountability as well as individuals' rights to enhance a culture of data privacy and security.

Therefore, the data collection, analysis and write up was done by myself from the beginning to the end. The data was saved on password-protected computers and stored securely. Only I, the University of the West of Scotland and the local contact person for the research community would have access to the data. The information was anonymized so that those reading reports from the research would not know who has contributed to it, unless a participant explicitly agrees that his or her name could be made public.

5.9 Data Quality Procedures

Miles & Huberman (1984) and Robertson (2007) listed three logical steps in data analysis: data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing and verification. Many researchers believed that the researcher has the responsibility to make sense out of a large amount of data gathered, organize the data by recurring patterns or themes, and to clearly communicate what the data reveals (Robertson, 2007; Patton, 1990; Hatch, 2002).

In this study, the five areas that were used to present the plan for data analysis are: data collection, data analysis, data validation by respondents, data triangulation, and data

representation. Therefore, this section gives details of the methods used to organize and reduce raw data into meaningful pieces, and to transform the meaningful pieces into credible results of the entire study.

5.10 Data Analysis

The importance of the Data Analysis phase in a case study was expressed by Hewitt-Taylor (2001, p. 41) that “Data analysis forms part of the research methods used in an enquiry, and should, therefore, be consistent with the philosophical underpinning of the study”. Kolb (2012, p. 84) referred to Bogdan & Biklen (2007) explanation that data analysis is “a systematic process of sifting and arranging all information obtained from interview transcripts, field notes and other material collected to increase your understanding of the data to enable the presentation of what have been discovered”. It therefore makes sense when Kolb (2012) and Miles & Huberman (1994) noted that in a case study, reducing the data into manageable units and coding information are integral parts of the data analysis process. Both Robertson (2007) and Creswell (1998) further noted that data analysis in a case study consists of a detailed description of the case and the setting in conjunction with a structured approach at analyzing results.

Therefore, the data collected from each case was first organized accordingly. Within each case, attention was given to emerging categories that could help determine how cultural diplomacy linked to digital media could safeguard the San/Bushmen cultural heritage. The categories from each data collection phase were compared to identify recurring themes that give detailed understanding of the targeted San/Bushmen situation. The identified themes were then compared to find the most salient and urgent themes affecting the targeted San/Bushmen. Data collected from document reviews and observations recorded throughout the case study were used as supplementary information to support the entire interviews.

5.11 Data Collection

In a period of about two (2) years, starting from January 2018, I spent about six months to collect three hundred and seventy-five (375) structured interviews among policymakers/implementers and seventy-seven (77) structured interviews among the tribes. Within the two years I made seven visits to the tribes of which I spent a period of about six weeks with the San people observing and doing go-alongs chats and activities with them.

Data collection in this study was oral, which conforms to the cultural norms of indigenous society (Foley, 2004). Data was collected from three sources that included quantitative survey, qualitative interviews through Go-Along interviews, and direct observations. The techniques used included going along with the informants in different environments, such as farms, baby-sitting, the grocery store or cultural entertainment grounds when it was important to the Informants, and then asking questions about their everyday lives. The data collection methods were through face-to-face interviews in a form of individual go-alongs, focus group go-alongs and direct observations, (Butler & Derrett, 2014). The face-to-face interviews would not only capture verbal cues but would also capture non-verbal cues including body language which could signal me to make adjustments in order to keep to the appropriate research standards (Mathers et al., 2007; DeFranzo, 2014). In other words, the face-to-face interviews would make it possible for me to capture participants' emotions and behaviors, which are essential in the case study, with high ethical standards. Capturing non-verbal cues may not be possible by using other interview methods (Opdenakker, 2006; DeFranzo, 2014). Face-to-face interviews also provide the opportunity for the researcher to motivate, engage and keep participants on track till the end of the interviews (Opdenakker, 2006; Mathers et al., 2007; DeFranzo, 2014). Face-to-face interviews are in-the-moment and may therefore have limited technological distractions compare to other methods such as online interviews which are often completed during time convenient for the participant but could be in the midst of other distractions such as web surfing, telephoning etc. (Opdenakker, 2006; DeFranzo, 2014).

As art-based mobile data collection was recommended by the Journal of Contemporary Ethnography (Reed & Ellis, 2019), the data documentation methods included video recordings, photography, historic site visits; for example, symmetries, and artefact analysis such as devices that have meaning to the targeted San/Bushmen cultural heritage and general experiences. Brown & Hill (2006), Butler & Derrett (2014) and Reed & Ellis (2019) believed that such ethnographic data collection approach and documentation methods would give a detailed account of the circumstances surrounding the targeted group.

Some of the interviews were recorded on audio with supporting notes. A process of cross comparison of data analysis was used to ensure correct classification and recording of outcomes as a measure to ensure the overall reliability of the study (Denzin and Lincoln 1998). The data was stored in a structured, organized format, and in a safe location to ensure its protection from damage (Creswell, 1998). Therefore, crucial measures were followed to accurately and systematically collect and protect the data throughout the study period.

5.12 Data Validation by Respondents

According to Hewitt-Taylor (2001), selecting a method to analyze qualitative or quantitative data could be relatively straightforward but selecting a method to ensure that the data analysis is congruent with various sources of data could be more challenging. Kolb (2012) and Kolb & Hanley-Maxwell (2003) then argued that data validity is an area of concern in research methodologies and therefore, researchers need to account for the information provided in a study. In other words, it is the researcher's responsibility to take precautionary measures to confirm areas of validity within the research (Kolb, 2012; Strauss & Corbin, 2008). In the process of obtaining validity, Kolb (2012) and Nolan & Behi (1995) suggested that the qualitative aspect in research findings should be presented to participants and their views explored. Some scholars, (Hewitt-Taylor, 2001; Silverman 1993, Wellington 1996), also suggested that this should also be applied in the qualitative data analysis phase. Therefore, the interpretation of the responses and

emergent findings in this study were discussed with the targeted San family throughout the study.

The negotiation of outcomes in discussing the emergent findings with the participants was considered alongside with the equality of power and mutual respect for all stakeholders involved in the study. Although this procedure may not fully validate the findings, it brings transparency to the study process which makes the interpretation acceptable to the respondents (Hewitt-Taylor, 2001; Silverman 1993). Although achieving a balance of power in the process was important to emancipate the targeted San family, Hewitt-Taylor (2001) and Riley (1990) believe that in such a study, the research respondents should not be given too much power through the research interpretations but should rather try to make them recognize and accept the descriptions in the study as accurate portrayals of the underlining issues. This guidance was followed in the discussions about the interpretation of the data with the participants and all possible disagreements over the data interpretations were resolve.

5.13 Data Triangulation

The data triangulation technique is usually the convergence of data gathered by different methods such as data from interviews, , written archives, or can also be achieved by using the same method gathered over time (Salkind, 2010; Kolb, 2012). This makes triangulation method meets multiple interests and needs in a research study (Elmusharaf, 2012). Kolb (2012) then believed that the goal of obtaining triangulation is the enhancement of validity and trustworthiness. Therefore, the triangulation of the data in this study gave a clear overview and detailed description of the targeted San situation and therefore, validated the study conclusions.

Salkind (2010, para. 1) argue that although some researchers view triangulation techniques as “critical to establishing corroborating evidence” others would stress “on the potentials of triangulation to provide multiple lines of sight and multiple contexts to enrich the understanding of a research questions”. For example, Mertens and Hesse-Biber (2012) argue that Triangulation based on the integration of quantitative and qualitative

data put the data into a more comprehensive explanatory framework and not to merely look at agreement or disagreement between the data sets. Kolb (2012, p. 85) referenced (Glesne & Peshkin, 1992) that “Establishing trustworthiness and considering study limitations are major factors in accurately reflecting the integrity of the research project”. As it may be challenging to “prove absolute exactness of research,” triangulation provide various strategies to improve trustworthiness (Kolb, 2012, p. 85). In other words, the data triangulation stage was to enhance credibility of the data interpretation in the study by linking multiple sources of data to multiple approaches used to analyze the data (Glesne & Peshkin, 1992; Kolb, 2012).

5.14 Data Representation

The final stage of the data analysis in this study involved representing and reporting the results realized. Creswell (1998) cited in Robertson (2007, p. 71) refers to this stage of data analysis as the ‘packaging of what was found in text, tabular, or figure form.’ Therefore, convergent method was used to represent and report findings in a way that would give more meaning and understandable to the readers. A narrative format was used to provide detailed descriptions of the San people situation as well as direct quotations to provide access to the thoughts of the participants. Tables and figures were used to highlight contextual data and to illustrate theme development from the quantitative phase through the qualitative phase to the convergent phase.

5.15 Limitations

The targeted San people were not able to show me around in their natural environment as their current location was far away from nature. The most experienced family members were no longer physically strong enough for as to take a trip to take an overnight bus trip to nature. This in a way limited their experience sharing moments with me. However, I still managed to tap into that by bringing them pictures from nature for us to discuss.

Due to the change of the research objectives away from the original digital diplomacy to concentrate on the SDGs alimnt with cultural heritage, more time was needed for extra

fieldwork and desk research to assess the political and cultural situation of the San People in relations to the SDGs. It was also very hard to find literature on African Cultural diplomacy linked to the UN-SDGs. The financial implications were mainly the high cost in international travels, re-printing new questionnaires and the cost of living abroad for an extensive period of time.

5.16 The Convergent Mix-Methods

At this stage in the study, it was crucial to reflect on the study theoretical framework linked to the study adopted theory of change before choosing the method to implement. The theoretical framework was based on critical theory linked to social capital and tourism. Creswell & Plano Clark (2007) believed that choosing mixed methods research combines the strengths of each methodology and minimizes the weaknesses. However, earlier studies (Ravitch, 2010; Sallee and Flood, 2012; Berg, 2009; Richards & Richards, 1994) noted that in many social sciences, policymakers would usually attach more importance to quantitative orientations than results from qualitative approach. On the other hand, the study cannot also take only the political stand by sticking to only the quantitative approach and giving less or no priority to the qualitative perspective. Despite the debate, others (Krauss, 2005; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2007; Toomela, 2008) argued that the quantitative-qualitative debate is philosophically or theoretically looking at the identification of underlying basis that is used to construct a scientific investigation. In consensus, Toomela (2008) and Creswell & Plano Clark (2007) believed that mixed method enhances the need to understand what information is encoded in a variable so the interpretation is meaningful. This implies that mixed methods could enhance the strengths of both positivism and constructivism, reducing the tendency of positivism to ignore the interdependency between humans as researchers and objects as participants, and the tendency of constructivism to over-emphasize these factors (Bhaskar, 1989). Therefore, “many researchers have turned to mixed methods methodology as a way to address the critiques of quantitative and qualitative methods” (McKim, 2017, p. 213). This then makes the convergent mixed-method the most appropriate to implement this study.

5.17 Convergent Parallel Design.

Due to the geographical nature of the research location (high cost involved etc.), it was important to design the research in a way that would make it possible for both the quantitative and qualitative data collections concurrently. To ensure this alongside the study aims, the convergent design (Wyse, 2011; Cameron, 2015; Wisdom & Creswell, 2013; Shannon-Baker, 2016) was considered the most appropriate in this study.

Also, for the purpose of corroboration and validation, I would triangulate the methods by directly comparing the quantitative statistical results and qualitative findings. Therefore, two datasets would be obtained in the process, analyzed separately, compared and interpreted, see figure 5.

Figure 5: *Convergent Parallel Design*. Source: (Wyse, 2011; Cameron, 2015; Wisdom & Creswell, 2013; Shannon-Baker, 2016)

5.18 The Quantitative Phase Approach.

The quantitative phase was at the beginning of the study and was in two parts which were both used to assess digital literacy competence and indigenous cultural issues among the target groups: 1) Policymakers/Stakeholders, 2) The affected San people at Platfontein in South Africa. The aim was to select a sample representative of each targeted population so that inferences could be made about each population (Elmusharaf, 2012; Iared & Oliveira, 2017). However, the sampling methods and interview techniques differed from each group because of the distinctive nature of each target group.

5.19 The Quantitative Themes and Questionnaires Development

The quantitative design, questions and wording were informed by the broader literature review and the outcome of my integration trip to the research location at the very early stage in the field work (see Table 2 in section 5.5). The data collection was oral, which conforms to the cultural norms of indigenous society (Foley, 2004; IWGIA, 2006; Flack 2013). Three specific themes guided the qualitative study: (1) To what extent do policy makers understand the benefits of a holistic approach to cultural research to inform a cultural framework? (2) How competent are policy makers in digital governance? (3) To what extent can the targeted San people participate in online discussions? These themes were used to collect the quantitative data by using closed survey approach utilizing the questionnaires. See questionnaires in appendix 1.

Table 3: The Survey Target Groups and Key Themes and Relevance

Targeted Group	Key Themes	The Relevance to Achieve Cultural Protection and Preservation
<p>Part 1: participants were drawn from actors who could work collectively to mobilize diverse capital:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authorities mainly at local government level • Law Enforcement personnel • Industry • Some influential individuals from the Private sector, Radio Broadcasters, journalists and few traditional leaders (mainly from different ethnic groups other than the San) 	<p>(1) To what extent do policy makers understand the benefits of a holistic approach to cultural research to inform a cultural framework?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To enhance Data based governance • To promote the San heritage through cultural diplomacy linked to the UN-SDGs • As means of cultural tourism and diverse capital for the San people
	<p>(2) How competent are policy makers in digital governance?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As the bases to fully take advantage of the global digital infrastructure and its numerous platforms to promote the San cultural Heritage
<p>Part 2: Focused on the targeted San Extended Family</p>	<p>(3) To what extent can the targeted San people participate in online discussions?</p>	<p>Empowerment possibilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy as means towards self-advocacy • To participate in online discussions etc.

Part 1: Policymakers/Stakeholder Selection and Interviews

The targeted research participants as policymakers/stakeholders were actors who could work collectively to mobilize diverse capital. Part 1 in the survey investigates policymakers/stakeholders digital-media literacy competences and the importance they may attach to data-driven governance and indigenous cultural heritage promotion. In a period of about six months, spread across one and a half years, three hundred and seventy-five (375) policymakers/stakeholders who introduced themselves as natives of either South Africa, Namibia, Botswana or Zimbabwe, were interviewed at face-to-face meetings. It was important to target the multinationals because the literature review, (Hitchcock et al., 2006; Bolaane & Saugestad, 2011; Survival, 2014), revealed that majority of the San ethnic group live within these countries as South Africa, Namibia, Botswana and Zimbabwe.

Key Informants Sampling method was used to select study participants among policymakers and stakeholders. Key Informants, because of their personal skills and position within society, are better informed and therefore, have deeper insight about what is going on around them in the society they live in (Elmusharaf, 2012; Shannon-Baker, 2016). Therefore, targeted participants were among people who hold or had held management/administration level public/private offices or are playing prominent community leadership roles.

In order to ensure that good quality of data was obtained in the research (Butler & Derrett, 2014; Mathers et al., 2007; DeFranzo, 2014; Reed & Ellis, 2019; O'Neill & Perivolaris 2015; Brown & Hill, 2006), the survey was conducted through face-to-face interviews. Participants were interviewed at events such as conferences and workshops, hosted at prominent hotels, guesthouses and professional training institutions.

Right at the beginning of the survey, I noted that the target groups were not comfortable talking about their competences and educational background. It then became very important for me to first of all build relationships with them through informal small talks/conversations. Such small talks with the policymakers at the conferences would usually take place during breakfast, lunchbreaks and in the evenings after the day's

sessions. I would usually introduce myself as a researcher in my field who was also interested in knowing more about policy improvement issues in the African continent and hence my interest and willingness to share my ideas and learn directly from them. In that way the target group would see me as someone who was humble enough to learn from them and not to judge their knowledge and competence levels. Perhaps that was their biggest motivation to voluntarily build relationship with me, share their opinion and experiences with me and went on to answer the survey questionnaires during our discussions.

At the end of each conference, participants would always express their wish to meet up with me again and therefore, some would hint or directly invite me to participate in the next workshops or conferences (at my own cost) so that they could introduce me to new set of people. Most of such conferences took place in Johannesburg, Cape Town and Kimberley all in South Africa. Few also took place in Gaborone-Botswana, Windhoek-Namibia and Harare-Zimbabwe.

Picture 8: Francis Adams at Policymakers conference in Kimberley, South Africa, 2018

Although the approach was very expensive for me, the process involved was very helpful for me to understand and expand the local network across policymakers, academia and influential people at the grassroots within the Southern African region (South Africa,

Namibia, Botswana and Zimbabwe) for the purpose of the study. The diagonal network I put in place made it possible for me to also meet up with some chiefs and some retired people as opinion leaders who met the selection criteria. Such interviews took place at the participants' residences and at public gatherings, for example, during cultural entertainments. The survey results were tabulated as Part1-Table 1.

Part 1 Survey Results

Part 1-Table1. Target group: Stakeholders/Policymakers

Q1. How would you describe your profession?

A. Civil servant /government official	285	76%
B. Private Sector	90	24%

Q2. Do you think there is the need to research more about indigenous cultures e.g. the San/Bushmen in order to maintain their way of life?

A. Yes	171	46%
B. No	204	54%

Q3. How would you describe the indigenous way of life as an African tribe?

A. Original	124	33%
B. A shame to the African identity	251	67%

Q4. What is your wish for indigenous people?

A. Integrate them into mainstream society for a better life	263	70%
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B. Maintain their originality and promote their heritage	112	30%
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Digital media

Q5. How would you describe your competence level in managing the global digital infrastructure/ideologies and networks?

A. None	87	23%
B. Basic	278	74%
C. Expert	10	3%

Q6. How would you describe your internet skills?

A. Basic - email/SMS exchange	251	67%
B. Good - manage online information	109	29%
C. Expert level	15	4%

Q7. Do you often go online - every hour?

A. Yes	289	77%
B. No	86	23%

Q8. What is your main source of news update?

A. Television	71	18.9%
B. Social Media platforms	302	80.5%
C. Word-of-mouth	2	0.5%

Q9. What updates would you wish to get every day?

A. Culture/Music	175	47%
B. Tourism/Sports	150	40%
C. Politics	39	10%

D. Food Commodities	11	3%
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Part 2 of the survey focused on the forced-relocated Automover extended family. The survey was designed to get the overview of possible cultural issues which could be facing the family members as a result of the force relocation and to also assess their digital media competence levels. Volunteer Sampling method was used to select study participants. Seventy-seven (**77**) out of the total adult population of eighty-six (**86**) family members were surveyed in face-to-face interviews.

The Volunteer Sampling approach became particularly useful in the study as potential participants were dispersed throughout the community and therefore, difficult to contact directly (Elmusharaf, 2012; Shannon-Baker, 2016). Volunteer Samples are often drawn through advertising, requesting people to volunteer to participate in the study (Elmusharaf, 2012). However, as the chiefs and the people were supportive to the research and thereby gave their consent, the chief would inform the population any time I arrived. A date would be set for me to address the population by reminding them of the essence of the research project and the survey procedures. Volunteers would then be recruited, and the survey days and times would be set to suit the participants. The entire survey took place in the community, Platfontein, South Africa. All participants were given the same questionnaire and enough flexible time so that responses could be compared. The questionnaires were administered by me and the results were then tabulated as Part 2-Table 2.

Part 2 Survey Results

Part 2-Table 2. Target group - The Target San People at Platfontein, South Africa.

Q1. How would you describe your everyday life at Platfontein?

A. Good	20	26%
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B. Hectic and Depressive	57	74%
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Q2. How would you describe the future of your heritage?

A. There is hope for our heritage	29	38%
B. There is no hope for our heritage	48	62%

Q3. How would you describe your literacy level?

A. None	54	70%
B. Basic	21	27%
C. Good	2	3%

Q4. How would you describe your internet skills?

A. None	71	92%
B. Basic	6	8%

Q5. What is your main source of news update?

A. Television	15	19.5%
B. Radio	7	9.1%
C. Word-of-mouth	55	71.4%

Table 4: Summary of Key Quantitative Results

Key Theme Revealed	The Challenge in Promoting Cultural Tourism
<p>Lack of the San Cultural Awareness</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers lack awareness about the San ways of life as indigenous people and the contribution they could make to cultural tourism if promoted. • Majority of respondents wished that indigenous people should be integrated into mainstream society for “a better life.” • Indigenous cultural research was given less priority among the survey respondents
<p>Low levels of Digital Media- Competence Among authorities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital governance competence levels among policymakers were very low as only 3% of the surveyed respondents said they were digital media experts
<p>Low levels of Digital Media-Literacy among the San People</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Literacy level among the targeted San was very low • The San main source of information exchange was through word-of-mouth.

5.20 The Qualitative Design and Target Group

Data collection in the qualitative phase was through Go-Along interviews, and direct observations. The Go-Along method is a technique of data collection in which the researcher moves alongside informants to collect information (Madanth, 2018). According to Carpiano (2009), the Go-Along method is a hybrid between participant observation and qualitative interviewing which suits the purpose of this research. In other words, the Go-Along methods are capable of revealing hidden dimensions and patterns of personal and social life (Madanth, 2018; Kusenbach, 2012) which are crucial in this case study.

Content redacted due to uninformed consent for publication from the photographed subjects. Original photo shows the thesis author with the community. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Pictures 9-10 Go-Along method in research in the community - daily interactions. Source: Researcher's filed Pictures.

5.21 Go-along Research Theme

The go-along interviews were guided by three open-ended themes:

(1) Looking at their long journey consisting of several forced-relocations, where would the Automover family call their home and why? (2) To what extent could such relocations affect their preferences in regards to food and traditions as their heritage? (3) What are their impressions about classroom education instead of their traditional education? These three themes were explored many times in different contexts in the participants action interviews. They acted as broad themes to allow the participants to tell me a whole range of things that were important to them, so for example on the topic of food, we spent many hours/weeks on this, they demonstrated their farming techniques to me and I learned to participate with them. So, one theme, acted as a topic of interest and I learned to draw out the discussion and meaning, sometimes from non-verbal communication too. This will become evident in my findings.

5.22 Qualitative Data Collection Approach

The qualitative interview questions adapted both open-ended and semi-structured formats. As a cultural research, it was necessary to apply data collection methods and techniques that are flexible enough to fit the code of ethics and the human experiences being sorted for (Iared & Oliveira, 2017). DeFranzo (2018) and Farrell (2016) believed that the important benefit of combining open-ended and semi-structured questions is that

they allow the researcher to discover more than anticipated. Therefore, the format was chosen so that the targeted San/Bushmen could provide detailed responses such as sharing their experiences, motivations, behaviors and concerns that may otherwise not be known to me as the researcher but important in finding a sustainable solution to their situation. It was then anticipated that the open-ended questions would lead respondents to express themselves freely by revealing psychological and mental fundamentals of their daily experiences, problem-solving strategies, their thoughts, hopes, fears, and wishes (Opdenakker, 2006; Farrell, 2016; DeFranzo, 2018).

5.23 Participants Action Selection

Key Informant Sampling method was used to select participants for the qualitative study. Key Informants, as a result of their personal skills or position within their environment, can give a good quality of data in a short time during interviews (Family Practice, 1996; Elmusharaf, 2012). The Automover extended family had agreed that the family heads, Kakenge Automover, and Mandalena Automover, were more experienced as they had seen it all from their entire trip starting from Angola in the 1960s through Namibia down to their current location in Platfontein, South Africa. Therefore, the two family heads had offered to take me through their emotional journey as separate cases 1 and 2.

Case 3; Participants Action

McKim (2017, p. 209) believes that focus groups are great ways of “gathering lots of information from a group of individuals” as it allows participants to share their opinion and expand on each other’s responses (McKim, 2017; Beyea & Nicoll, 2000). Therefore, the group discussions provided an opportunity for the group to coordinate their individual experiences in order to obtain several perspectives on the same topics being discussed for a possible consensus (McKim, 2017; Morgan & Spanish, 1984). Participants were asked about their experiences and their wishes. The number of participants were based on expert’s recommendation of sampling 4 to 10 participants (Stake, 2006; McKim, 2017). There were 7 female participants (78%) and 2 male participants (22%) in the group.

Observation

The observation data formed the basis of the go-along interviews. Each step of the qualitative interviews was set to get an in-depth clarification to the previous step. The most common themes observed were noted and tabulated as part of the qualitative data which then complemented the quantitative phase findings and both data sets were used for the convergent analysis (DeFranzo, 2018; Mathers et al., 2007; Farrell, 2016).

CHAPTER 6: CASE STUDY IN SOUTH AFRICA

6.1 Introduction

This case study is a field study of a forced-relocated San community, Platfontein, South Africa. The aim of the research is to understand the cultural issues through informants' feelings and their experiences in order to make suggestion for sustainable San cultural promotion and protection.

The broader literature review revealed that many developmental projects like national parks or game reserves are, or have been demarcated on ancestral homelands of tribal people, leading to evicting them from lands that they have been depending on and have been managing for millennia (Hitchcock et al. 2006; IWGIA, 2006; UN, 2009; Renton, 2009; Flack 2013; Survival, 2014; MRG, 2016; Survival, 2017: February 10). In Africa, although it is still difficult to quantify victims of evictions from indigenous lands due to lack of appropriate data (Survival, 2014), many indigenous tribes have been evicted from their ancestral lands in recent years, (Survival, 2014; Survival, 2017).

These evictions do not only destroy both the lives of tribal people and the environment they have shaped and cared for over generations but also reduce tribal people to beggars and recipients of government handouts in resettlement areas, (IWGIA, 2006; UN, 2009; Renton, 2009; Survival,2014; Hitchcock, 2012). Eviction, to indigenous people means their self-sufficiency being taken away (IWGIA, 2006; UN, 2009). Although the intervention of several organizations including the Working Group of Indigenous

Minorities in Southern Africa (WIMSA) has led to some positive developments, the success made in solving some of the extreme challenges that confront some of the Indigenous people like the San/Bushmen communities is still limited (Bolaane & Saugestad, 2011). This study is to examine the role of Cultural Diplomacy linked to the UN-SDG as means through which sustainable Indigenous African Cultural Heritage, specifically the San, could be promoted and protected.

6.2 Background - The San and the Rich Cultural Heritage they Embody in Africa

The San, also known as Bushmen, Basarwa, or Khoesan, make up a marginalized Indigenous minority in Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa, with more than one half of the estimated population of 100,000 people living in Botswana (Hitchcock et al. 2006; Hitchcock, 2012; Bolaane & Saugestad 2011, Barnard 2007, Taylor 2011). Barnard (2007) believes that the San are the oldest and original inhabitants of Southern Africa, where they have lived for thousands of years. Kalahari Meerkat Project visitors' guide (n.d., p. 1) believes that the Bushmen home is in the vast expanse of the Kalahari Desert and they have remained "the remnants of Africa's oldest cultural group, genetically the closest surviving people to the original Homo sapiens 'core' from which the Negroid people of Africa emerged".

In terms of their geographical and social identity, Nthomang (2002, p. 3) notes that the San people "have always made up a distinct population in southern Africa with a subsistence economy based on foraging (hunting and gathering); they speak a number of phonetically highly complex khoisan click languages; they are light-skinned and somewhat smaller in physical stature than their neighbors. Their social organization is based on small bands united in flexible egalitarian structures, with a leadership ethos based on consensus". Consideration of an individual's opinion is naturally based on their level of skills and experience in the particular field of discussion (Bush Calls Safaris, 2018). Some of the things the Bushmen ethnic groups have in common includes "historical continuity with pre-colonial societies, strong links to territories" which show their

“strong identification with the land on which they carry out their traditional ways of life) distinct social, economic and political systems, culture and beliefs, non-dominant societies and an identity distinct from national societies,” (Nthomang, 2002, pp.3-4). The San people also share “discrimination as an ethnic group because their traditional ways of life (hunting and gathering) is not recognized by mainstream society, particularly by post-Independence nationalist governments which see the foraging mode of existence as uncivilized and backward and as having no place in modern ways of life” (Nthomang, 2002, p. 4).

6.3 Their Way of Living – understanding social structure

Traditionally, large percentage of the Bushmen’s diet consists of plant food, including berries, nuts, roots and melons gathered primarily by the women and the rest is meat (mostly antelopes), hunted by the men using poisoned arrows and spears on hunts that could last several days, (Bush Calls Safaris, 2018; Trip Down Memory Lane, 2013; Exploring Africa, 2018). In terms of social structure, the San ethnic group made their own temporary homes from wood that they gathered, (Trip Down Memory Lane, 2013). For several thousands of years, their hunting & gathering economy and social structure had remained virtually unchanged until very recent times, (*Kalahari Meerkat Project visitors’ guide, n.d.*). Several hundreds of local plants and their uses were known to bushmen, along with the places where they grew – not only providing a balanced nutrition, but also moisture from roots even in time of drought, (Motaor Network, 2018). Plants were used in ways similar to western phytomedicine to treat wounds and heal illnesses; other plants were rather part of healing ceremonies in which a healer would burn plants to make rain, trance to heal an ailment, or perform a charm to bring fertility, (Motaor Network, 2018 & All Things South African, 2013). *Hoodia gordonii*, a known San ethnic group plant, even made the worldwide news since it was patented by a pharma company as a diet support due to its traditional San usage to suppress appetite and hunger (Things South African, 2013). However, the Kalahari Meerkat Project visitors’ guide (n.d., p. 2) noted that the

San “health, in general, is not good though: 50% of children die before the age of 15; 20% die within their first year (mostly of gastrointestinal infections). Average life expectancy is about 45-50 years; respiratory infections and malaria are the major reasons for death in adults. Only 10% become older than 60 years”.

6.4 Some of the Problems that the San People face

Over the past two centuries, the Bushmen tribes have “been hunted, persecuted and driven off their traditional lands by more assertive tribes to the point where they now generally live-in landless poverty,” (Nthomang, 2002, p. 4). *Kalahari Meerkat Project visitors’ guide* (n.d. p. 3) explained that, after the Bushmen homelands were invaded by cattle herding Bantu tribes about 1,500 years ago and followed by “white colonists over the last few hundred years”, the Bushmen have since “faced discrimination, eviction from their ancestral lands, murder and oppression amounting to a massive though unspoken genocide, which reduced them in numbers from several million to 100,000”. As a result, Nthomang, 2002 & Bolaane, 2014 have both noted that the San ethnic group have lost their ancestral land, resources and cultural identity, adding that, one of the most salient markers of Bushmen identity is their common experience of dispossession, mistreatment, exploitation and neglect by those more economically and politically powerful than themselves. Although the San ethnic group suffer from a perception that their lifestyle is 'primitive' and that they need to be made to live like the majority cattle-herding ethnic groups, specific problems vary according to their geographical location, (Siyabona Africa, 2017).

6.5 The San Ethnic Group paying the price of conservation in Botswana

In 1961, the government of Botswana established the Central Kalahari Game Reserve to protect wildlife resources and reserve (Taylor, 2011) and sufficient land for traditional use by hunter gatherer communities of the Botswana Central Kalahari, including the San people (Upstream Journal, 2012). Unfortunately, these tribes in the Botswana's Central

Kalahari Game Reserve were among the most persecuted by authorities after diamonds were discovered in the reserve in the early 1980s, (Taylor 2011, *Upstream Journal*, 2012).

Figure 6: A map showing the Central Kalahari Game Reserve. Source: *Upstream Journal Winter 2012 Vol. 24 No.2*

The Guardian reported (Vidal, 2016, para. 2) that Botswana police helicopter spotted nine young San men, who had been hunting antelope to feed their families and “There was a burst of gunfire from the air and the young men dropped their meat and skins and fled”. Mostly through luck, “no one was hit, but within minutes armed troops arrived in a jeep and the nine were arrested, stripped naked, beaten and then detained for several days for poaching in a nature reserve,” (Vidal, 2016, para. 2).

According to the report, the incident took place “just days after Botswana’s wildlife minister Tshekedi Khama, the brother of President Ian Khama, announced a shoot-on-sight policy on poachers. Khama claims the policy, which is supported by conservation groups, will deter poaching and the illegal wildlife trade, which is widely seen by Europe and the US as disastrous for biodiversity”. The report maintained that there were no rare or endangered species such as elephants or rhinos in the areas where the bushmen hunt.

The disconnection between the Bushmen and their ancestral lands by Governments has led to misunderstandings between the Bushmen and the Governments as Fihlani (2014) noted that, although some governments officials accused the Bushmen of destroying

reserved parks, the Bushmen argued that their years of living in harmony with the environment proved that their ways are ecologically sustainable. The Bushmen maintained that their relocation was an attempt to do away with their culture, (Fihlani, 2014). It then makes sense when the South African San Institute (2018) noted that in some of the forced-relocated communities, almost everybody dresses in western dress and not their traditional San/Bushmen leather clothing. In some of the communities the aged remember their history and have a lot of traditional knowledge and skills but passing their heritage on to the young people is not possible as a result of change of their environment, (South African San Institute, 2018).

It was argued that the forced relocation of the San people has led them to become “second-class citizens in the lands of their birth, suffering daily discrimination” not only in “the eyes of European settlers, but by their fellow Africans as well” (Lee et al., 2017, para. 2 - 3). Of course, the government would try to provide relocated communities with schools, water facilities etc. but on the other side it also forces the San people to live in permanent settlement which is different from the traditional migrating lifestyle that they are used to. Due to the lack of employable skills among most of the relocated Bushmen, unemployment was noted to be high in the community (Fihlani, 2014).

Meanwhile, Survival (2003) in an article, *World Bank funds controversial diamond project on Bushmen's land [Botswana]*, noted that wealthy sport hunters from abroad are welcomed to newly constructed modern game lodges in the park. This shows a disconnect in both local and international policy when it comes to indigenous people's needs and protection. The lack of policy protection for the San people has led to their persecution in their own land (Fihlani, 2014; Vidal, 2016). This suggests the issues might have systematically stripped some of the Bushmen off their homes, land and culture and those affected could be living in resettlement camps at various locations other than their ancestral lands where they have become vulnerable to mainstream social issues including alcoholism, boredom, depression, and illnesses such as TB and HIV/AIDS etc. (Lee et al., 2017; Popovic, 2018). Therefore, there is a need for evidence-based in-depth study about the San people to enhance policy decision that could protect the San ethnic group and their heritage.

6.6 Location Selection and Setting; Critical Case Approach.

The selected study location emerged from the research documented in the broader review of literature. Although historical evidence can place the San ethnic group at various locations on the African continent (Hitchcock, 2019; Kalahari Meerkat Project visitors' guide, n.d.), this research focuses on Botswana, South Africa and Zimbabwe where most of the remaining San people are located (Hitchcock, 2019) as indicated in figure 7.

Figure 7: Numbers of San in Botswana, Namibia, South Africa and Zimbabwe (Hitchcock, 2019, p. 3)

Once the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee granted permission (with approval number 2018 - 4881-3678, see in appendix 4) to conduct the study, the I traveled back to South Africa to continue the process. My choice of Critical Case Approach to select a community and the setting was informed by Elmusharaf (2012, p. 18) belief that Critical Case approach “Permits logical generalization and maximum application of information to other cases because if it's true of this once case it's likely to be true of all other cases”. The Critical Case Approach became crucial because the broad literature

review revealed that forced relocation of indigenous people was not limited to the San/Bushmen alone (World Bank, 2016; Conservation Watch, 2017; Survival, 2014.) The Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, (OHCHR, 2012, p. 2) noted that “in some countries, governments and multinational corporations continue to construct hydroelectric dams and roads, and conduct mining and logging activities, that threaten to harm the land’s fragile ecosystems and damage large areas of land inhabited by indigenous people”. The World Bank believes that it does not matter where indigenous people live, they “face distinct pressures, including being among the poorest and most marginalized in their societies,” just as the situation of the San ethnic group (World Bank, 2016, para. 1). This then make Platfontein, which hosts forced-relocated San/Bushmen at different stages in South Africa, a suitable critical case to study.

6.7 The San People at Platfontein Community in South Africa.

Platfontein is a community located in an arid region of the Northern Cape Province in South Africa, 15 kilometers outside the city of Kimberley. The community has a population of about 5,185 people (Statistics South Africa, 2011) which include two San tribes, the !Xun and the Khwe (Mollema, 2017; Soskolne, 2007). The San of Platfontein are believed to have their origin from Angola and Namibia (Mollema, 2017; Soskolne, 2007; Uys, 1993). In both Namibia and Angola, the Xun and the Khwe were militarized first by the Portuguese army during the Angolan War of Independence (Mollema, 2017; Soskolne, 2007; Uys, 1993). Mollema, (2017) and Van Wyk, (2015) believed that the militarization of the San started in 1966, by the Portuguese Security Police (PIDE) and were successfully used against the Angolan liberation movements in their struggle for independence of Angola. After the Popular Movement for the Liberation of Angola (MPLA) assumed power in Angola in November 1975, many of the San soldiers were recruited by the then apartheid South Africa to fight against the South West African People's Organisation (Swapo) in its struggle for the independence of Namibia (Weinberg, 2017; Soskolne, 2007; Dalton-Greyling & Greyling, 2007; Mollema, 2017; Van Wyk, 2015).

When Namibia became independent, the South African fighting units had to be withdrawn from northern Namibia and many of the San soldiers had to resettle in South Africa, as they were not sure whether the newly elected Swapo party could retaliate or not (Dalton-Greyling & Greyling, 2007). The South African National Defence Force then offered them sanctuary in a tent town that it built on a windy plain in Schmidtsdrift in the Northern Cape (Weinberg, 2017; Mollema, 2017; Dalton-Greyling & Greyling, 2007)

Few years later, a democratic government was elected in South Africa and all financial support to the San soldiers came to an end, rendering the San soldiers jobless (Mollema, 2017; Van Wyk, 2015; Dalton-Greyling & Greyling, 2007). At the same period, their place of residence at Schmidtsdrift was judged to belong to a Tswana ethnic group that had been removed from the land decades earlier (Brand South Africa, 2003). The San were again forcefully relocated in groups from Schmidtsdrift to Platfontein (Brand South Africa, 2003; Weinberg, 2017; Mollema, 2017; Dalton-Greyling & Greyling, 2007). Soskolne (2007) then suggested that the San recruitment into such wars contributed to the loss of their indigenous way of life as hunter-gatherers. In other words, any means of limiting the San people's ability to hunt and gather bush foods in their original land could be a destruction to the San people's heritage (Soskolne, 2007).

6.8 Part 2: Focus on the Kakenge Automover Extended Family

The case study is focused on the Automover extended family living in the Platfontein community. Mollema (2017) believes that the force-relocation of the San at Platfontein has affected their values and beliefs. The San at Platfontein, as indigenous people, were originally living as mobile nuclear families who used to have enough land and space to sustain their family groups through hunting and gathering (Mollema, 2017; Hitchcock, 2019). However, at Platfontein, they have to start a sedentary life and have to share a smaller area of land with other people (Mollema, 2017). That means they would have to adopt to a new set of mainstream social values and norms. The process could affect their values and norms in many ways (Hitchcock, 2019; Soskolne, 2007; Mollema, 2017). The process could affect their values and norms in many ways (Soskolne, 2007; Mollema,

2017; Hitchcock, 2019). Therefore, the study decided to investigate a case of the Automover extended family at their current home in Platfontein.

In an interview, the elders of the Automover family narrated that their original home was in Angola and that they started their forced-relocation journey in the 1960s and have since been relocated seven times till their current location in Platfontein. According to the family heads, the family has one hundred and eighty-eight (188) members of which ninety-nine **(99)** are females and eighty-nine **(89)** are males. The adult population age of eighteen years and above was eighty-six **(86)**. The family believed that they were the last group to be relocated from Schmidtsdrift to Platfontein in 2012. Therefore, they were still in the storms of adopting to mainstream social life and the related challenges.

As the last to be relocated, most of the Automover family members were yet to benefit from the South African government provided housing for the community. Most of the family members including the most elderly members were living in aluminum self-made shacks as shown in picture 11 below. The rest of the family members were scattered in the community due to lack of accommodation.

Picture 11: Platfontein, the research community near Kimberley, South Africa.

CHAPTER 7: THE QUALITATIVE RESEARCH FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

7.1 Lay Out of the Findings and Analysis

This chapter discusses my community life and roadmap to the qualitative study. The chapter gives details to the specific go-along methods and logical approaches through which the qualitative data in this study was collected and organized to reveal key emerging categories and themes that gave guidance to how cultural diplomacy linked to the UN-SDGs could safeguard the affected San people cultural heritage. Details of how the identified themes were compared by using tables and subheadings to find the most salient and urgent themes affecting the targeted San people are outlined. Details of data collected from document reviews and observations recorded throughout the case study and used as supplementary information to the entire interviews are also discussed in this chapter.

7.2 My Community Life and Roadmap to the Qualitative Study

The qualitative phase involved periodic visits to the research community in South Africa and the process covered a period of about two years, starting from January 2018 till February 2020 although the actual data collection started in July 2018.

My host family, the Automover extended family members, were unemployed and depended on the South African government subsidy. Although they wished they could have provided me with accommodation to live with them in the village, they did not have the possibilities. They live in aluminum constructed shacks and did not have enough space for themselves. So, I would always stay in a guesthouse in Kimberley, about 15km from the village, and then visit them for us to spend the day time together. Plus, my university did not want me staying in the village with them for security reasons since the environment was potentially hostile and basic.

When I asked the family why they were living in aluminum constructed shacks while other families were living in concrete houses, they explained to me that the concrete houses were provided by the state and only the families who arrived in the earlier stages of the relocation got those concrete houses. They told me that they were unhappy about their housing because the aluminum shacks were not good for any weather, neither winter nor summer. My personal experience about the housing situation was that, in summer the rooms would become extremely hot. When I visited again in the wintertime, I noticed that the rooms would become very cold but because of lack of enough space, they would not be able to set up large open fire to warm themselves like they used to do in nature. So, no matter what weather it was, they would face the worse of it.

Right from the beginning and throughout the quantitative phase, I realized that my host family members were not keen on showing me their food culture. They preferred leading me to a shop to buy my own canned food and drinks to offering me their house made food. Due to our similar cultural background, I knew that that was not normal. I expected them to welcome me with their home-made food. One afternoon I told one of the family heads, Kakenge, that I was interested in learning how to cook the local San food. Besides that, I was also tired of eating from the shops so I would like to eat the San food. Kakenge then said to me that he was very sad that since I arrived his family had not been able to welcome me with the San food culture. Almost in tears, he said to me that:

“It is all because we do not have food ... What we eat is not our staple food so I am sorry but we simply do not have what we would call food or our own medicine etc. and that is our situation here...,”

His remarks about his family disconnection from the San traditional food were in line with what recent similar case studies in Africa (Hitchcock, 2019; Mwangi, 2019; UN Food and Agriculture Organization, 2019) believed to be the consequences of shifting indigenous people from indigenous way of life to modern way of life. Therefore, I reflected on his feelings by telling him that I could also feel his pain and that I appreciated his courage in telling me his sensitive experiences. Then I noted the topic down as an area to investigate further and then diverted the conversation to a more comfortable topic for that moment.

There were such emotional expressions during various discussions in topics such as: discussion about their departed loved ones to the ancestral world, some specific geographical locations they have lived in nature, and discussions about some specific artifacts. There were various forms of non-verbal language and deep emotional expressions during the discussions. Emotional expressions observed were mainly shedding tears.

Content redacted due to uninformed consent for publication from the photographed subjects. Original photo shows the thesis author with the community. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Picture 12-14: nonverbal communications and emotional moments during discussions.

The topics in the discussions which led to such emotional expressions were then noted as areas to further explore. In other words, the emotional expressions and the nonverbal communications observed served as a guide to explore the affected San family experiences, feelings and views throughout their journey, as a result of forced relocation starting from Angola till their current location at Platfontein in South Africa. Therefore, the responses obtained in the go-along interviews were the participants' reflections on their experiences and emotions. The responses represent some of their current feelings and concerns as a result of the rapid change of their environment - moving from indigenous way of life to mainstream social life and the related consequences for this particular forced-relocated San family.

Although I was still at the early stage of the qualitative interviews, my observations had already revealed to me that the targeted San family was worried that their traditional food and herbal medicine, as key aspects of their San heritage, were disappearing and I would like to explore further into that. For example, a family member narrated to me that:

“We are worried about losing our heritage...the closer we get to mainstream society, the wider the distance between us and our traditional food and medicine...”

Another family member also expressed his concerns that:

“It takes so much time and a lot of money to build a modern home... but if that is one’s choice then there is no problem. It becomes a big problem if you are forced to live such an expensive but boring life. First of all, it is very difficult to breathe if you sleep in these modern houses. There is very little light in them and in the night, you cannot even see the stars from inside the rooms.... everything about those modern houses is very uncomfortable. One always needs time to get use to them...”

When I asked them whether the authorities were aware of their concerns, another family member answered me that:

“If you tell them you miss your culture, they say we are thinking backwards...If you tell them you miss your native food, they would tell you that you are not civilized. They see our traditional medicine and healing methods as primitive and less important compare to their healing methods in the clinics”.

In heavy emotions, an elderly family member expressed his feelings:

“They refer to us as fools but they never tried living our way of life. Our indigenous way of life is more difficult than their modern way of life...which means that we are intelligent beings and that is why we could survive in nature without going to the banks for money...but who would listen to us...?”

Another family member added that:

“Things were different back in Angola where our journey started in the 1960s. Very soon our children will join other religions and that could be the end of our ancestral beliefs...”

Chief Kakenge also added his pain:

“It’s a pity that authorities never listened to our concerns...they tell us what to do. Otherwise, there are many things I wish I could discuss with authorities...”

Tables 5 below shows summary of key themes that emerged from my observation.

Table 5: The Main Qualitative Notes by Observation

<p>The targeted San People emotional expressions, behavior/skills etc. included the following:</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• They were more concerned about losing their heritage• They were very peaceful and moving about freely• They were very suspicious of researchers/strangers• Withdrawal – less motivated to meet authorities• Very low voice tone – almost timid (would make very short sentences)• Shedding tears during discussions about their journey and everyday life• Sobbing when sharing specific experiences relating to the forced-relocations• Folding arms during discussions• Reluctant to talk during formalized meetings• They pay attention to details and logical flow of facts during discussions• They were interested in long-term relationship• They were very interested in sharing inter-cultural experiences with me.• Very expressive when meetings were imbedded in an activity such as farming, taking a walk together or cultural entertainment etc.• They were not keen on mobile phones and electrical gargets• They preferred word-of-mouth mode of communication to digital communication• I noticed broken electric extension wires lying on the floor and people were walking over them• Some newly-built government houses, meant for some of the forced-relocated families, were not occupied and were in bad condition.• They prefer their traditional houses to aluminum the shacks or concrete houses• They prefer cooking on open fire instead of gas stoves• Acacia trees were their most preferred place to hang their laundry instead of the modern drying lines

- They prefer their self-made toilet facilities to modern toilet facilities
- They crave for their traditional food and herbal medicine
- They exhibited very low levels of literacy across all ages
- High level of unemployment - they would spend the whole day loitering around.
- They depended on government monthly social grant.
- Most of the children were not going to school
- High levels of alcoholism
- Escalating theft cases in the community
- High levels of teenage pregnancies
- They are talented in the San traditional music and dance
- Exhibited micro-entrepreneurial skills and they are skilled in traditional handicraft etc.

Concerns and trust related verbal expressions (in short sentences as their way of talking at the beginning) included:

...my son, you are one of the very few visitors we can trust....so feel free and talk to us...

...life here is hectic and depressive...

...we have received many researchers here but none could help us improve our situation....

...things were different back in Angola where our journey started in the 1960s...

...I am happy you came all the way from Europe just to see us and be with us....we love you for that..

...your presence here with us has given me hopes for my children and grandchildren...

...you have the same resemblance to people I knew in Angola where we started our journey many years ago...

...please feel comfortable and be with us...

...we don't feel at home here..... we miss home...

...we are worried about losing our heritage...

...cultures may be changing but why do we have to live like other cultures and not the other way around...?

... why don't they join us in our ancestral lands, where there could be enough land for all of us?...

...I am sorry but we simply do not have what we would call food...we lost our food heritage...

...my grandson, you are one of us... that is why you respect the San cultural values and norms...

...feel free and stay with us...

...the closer we get to mainstream society, the wider the distance between us and our traditional food and medicine...

...very soon our children will join other religions and that could be the end of our ancestral beliefs...

...Unemployment is one of the big issues here... the stigma is such that employers don't see us employable even in jobs that we could do. So the best way would be to set up our own businesses...

...we would have loved to educate our children in nature...

...I don't like mobile phones...I prefer talking to my relatives in person...

...they say that our culture and way of thinking is backwards...

...If you tell them you miss your native food, they would tell you that you are not civilized...

...it's a pity that authorities never listened to our concerns...they tell us what to do. Otherwise there are many things I wish I could discuss with authorities.

*.... Authorities never tried reading our books...in fact they cannot even read our books –
nature*

.... They do not understand that we can read our own books...

The observations noted in Table 5 were in line with crucial themes that emerged from the literature review that indigenous people have been subjected to processes of domination and discrimination and their cultures have been viewed as being “inferior, primitive, irrelevant, something to be eradicated or transformed” (UN, 2009, p.53). This was also inline with the beliefs of most of the policymakers I interacted with at the early stage of the field work. They described the indigenous way of life as “primitive,” “backwards” and as “a shame to the African identity.”

I had noticed at the very beginning of our interactions that the San people were not comfortable with formalized meetings and recording of our daily activities. They would become tense and reluctant to talk. Therefore, I would memorize daily field notes and record them immediately afterwards in private. It then became crucial that a strategic in-depth study was needed to reveal as many concerns as possible before one could engage them in any form of structured discussions that could lead to finding solutions to their concerns.

The challenge was then for me to find out other possibilities for them to tell me their sensitive experiences in comfort. Therefore, I decided to start with autoethnographic ways of interactions by participating and promoting practical activities such as housekeep, gardening/farming etc. as a way of sharing our intercultural experiences. The ethnographic ways of investigations (with specific questions) would follow only when I was sure of our solid mutual trust and respect for one another.

Therefore, I decided to set three (3) practical and logical steps to guide me investigate the situation deeper in order to make a sustainable impact: 1) Trust Building; I would remain sensitive and keep building trust with them while recording their concerns, 2) Further Research; In order to make any positive impact as the outcome of the study, I would need suitable methods to explore more about the extent to which their heritage (food, healing, dance, etc.) has been affected as a result of the forced-relocation and find out possible means of empowering them, 3) Ensure sustainability; put into practice sustainable follow-up and monitoring plans for the long-term perspectives of the study impact.

7.3 Step 1: Participant observations and Interactions while building trust

My first approach was to observe and capture the participants concerns. The participants observation data formed the basis of the qualitative approach. In other words, the methodology and strategy I adopted to investigate the situation were based on what I observed right from the beginning of the field work. Each step of the qualitative go-along interviews was set to get an in-depth clarification to the previous step.

Right from the beginning of my time in the community, I found it important to remain sensitive to the affected San people emotions throughout my time with them. For example, chief Kakenge narrated to me during my very first informal conversations with him:

“My son, you are one of the very few visitors we can trust....so feel free and talk to us”.

When I told him that I wanted to know his experience with researchers, he responded:

“...we have been receiving many researchers and officials here who would tell us that they are here to investigate our situation but nothing changes for one reason - they do not listen to us but they would bring us what they think are the solutions to our situation. Some foreign researchers have taken advantage of our situation and exploited us a lot. For example, Madam XX came here to write my autobiography. She made so many pictures of me and my family. Then she left and she never came back. Someone found

out that she went around the world exhibiting our pictures at important cultural events and making money for herself. This is just one of such examples and reasons why we don't trust most of the people who come here as researchers etc..."

I then repeated my commitment to remain honest and stick to my university ethical standards throughout my time with them.

Although they were not outspoken at the beginning, I observed that they were active and would move about freely. They were willing to show me around more than engaging me in conversation. Of course, the fact that I always needed an interpreter in any meaningful communications compelled us to resort to practical means of understanding one another. This had its advantage in a sense that even when interpreters were not around, I could still interact with the family very well in practical activities like taking a walk or they would show me how to use some traditional household equipment. This then gave me the direction to engage them more in physical activities in the trust building process. The strategy was in line with go-along interview methods (Carpiano, 2009) and therefore supported qualitative data collection methods. I then decided to participate in household work as my way of showing solidarity and commitment to be integrated into the family. The idea was to fully understand their way of life so that we could support one another as a family in managing the household activities such as cooking and caring for their children.

My first assignment that I took upon myself was to baby-sit their children. This was because I had observed that the mothers were always managing the children alongside the household duties. I would make myself available in the open compound and encourage some of the parents, especially the fathers, to join me. I decided to encourage the fathers in the babysitting as I had realized that the mothers were doing the babysitting all the time. So I told them that it would be good if we, as men, could also learn more about babysitting as a job for both fathers and mothers. Everybody thought it was a laudable idea and at the end the babysitting time became a normal gathering moment for both mothers and fathers together with their children. As time went by, the babysitting activity became more useful as I did not have to call for special meetings for focus group discussions but could sometimes have spontaneous discussions.

Content redacted due to uninformed consent for publication from the photographed subjects. Original photo shows the thesis author with the community. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Picture 15: Happy moment as we gather for babysitting duties

7.4 Step 2: Research about the San People Potentials and Empowerment

My intensive involvement in the household activities had improve our trust for one another. Although the improvement in trust did not change their feelings that much, it improved individual confidence in our interactions. For example, we could then tease one another, ask questions about almost everything and freely request for assistance in any ways that one would wish. That was the moment I thought was right for me to find out their skills and potentials, linked to the San heritage, as means of securing their livelihood.

7.5 Backyard Farming Project as Cultural Exchange- the San Food and Healing Heritage

The San food and healing heritage outlines ritual processes that harness supernatural powers to lead them accomplish their various wishes such as resisting against evil spirits, curing the sick or transition from one stage to another (Hitchcock et al. 2006; Hitchcock,

2012; Bolaane & Saugestad 2011, Barnard 2007, Siyabona Africa, 2017; Taylor 2011). As hunter-gatherers, the San selection of traditional food and healing methods ranges between animals and vegetables in their immediate environment (Barnard 2007, Hitchcock et al. 2006; Siyabona Africa, 2017). The processes and experiences involved in such daily routines are connected to their religious realities and the essence of their existence (Hitchcock, 2019; Hitchcock, 2012; Barnard 2007). Perhaps it was for such reasons that Moore et al., (2019) advocated a need for a theory of change that would look beyond marginalized cultural identities to ensure sustainable heritage protection and promotion and the benefits for local, national and regional development.

I was aware that the San family was concerned and worried about losing their traditional food and herbal healing as key aspects of their intangible heritage. Therefore, I wanted to explore further about the extent to which their food and healing heritage has since been affected as a result of the force relocations. Although the way to proceed without hurting them then became a challenge for me, I knew that I only had to be creative enough to find practical ways of motivating them to talk to me in their own way and in comfort. Perhaps I should tell them a summary of my autobiography and if they seem interested in knowing more about my life, then I would let us do a productive long-term activity, which could last for months, through which I would tell them my full childhood story – farming.

I thought my experiences could make sense to them because I was born into a hunter-gatherer community but due to circumstance beyond my possibilities, I had to restart my life in a town on my own as a child of thirteen years of age with a physical disability etc. So, I understood very well what it meant and how it feels to integrate into a modernized society from the countryside. In other words, if I manage to let them believe that I was once in similar situations before, that may let them read different meaning to their emotional pains. In that way we could discuss sensitive things but would now see them from the exchange and learning points of view. That may help us reduce the intensity of the psychological and emotional pain that may be involved in sharing our experiences. So, at one of our usual babysitting gatherings, I asked them if they would like to hear my childhood story. Everybody was interested and so I started: I spent my first twelve years as a hunter-gatherer, just like the San. By the time I was twelve years of age I could call

myself a promising indigenous boy because I was very successful as a herd boy, a herbalist and as a hunter-gatherer. I was well connected to nature and I understood the language of nature very well. It was a life that I thought could never change until March 1992 when I fell sick in my knee. The sickness did not only result in my disability but also deprived me of my life with nature as I moved to a town. I had to rethink and re-engineer my life, using my indigenous knowledge, to fit into mainstream social life and proceed in what I believed was the right direction. Here I was with them as a potential academic, hoping to make a change in the lives of indigenous people - my past life and my true-culture...

At this point, the chief spoke through the interpreter that I should tell them the details about how I made it through my journey to become an academic. I then explained that by the time I had the opportunity to start going to school, I was already thirteen years of age with the disability and without any family support. However, I placed so much value on education that I tried very hard to keep myself in school through farming and casual work for neighbors. I then made it through to study at university level in Ghana, then I went to Germany to study for my master's degree, and I was now studying for my PhD in both the United Kingdom and Germany.

As part of the many rewards for all the struggles that I went through to get modern education, I have traveled many times to America and other countries to see how other people live their lives – the motivation that brought me to learn from them as San ethnic group. Therefore, I was very proud to tell them that I was happy about everything in my life. I then admitted to them that I had gone through a lot of psychological and emotional pain which were similar to what they were going through but such experiences taught me that, once we were still alive, we could still change things for the better, at least starting from supporting and guiding a child to go to school...

The adults were very moved and they wanted to ask me more questions but I told them that I was becoming emotional in revisiting my childhood difficult times. Besides that, the story was long. On the other hand, I could tell them the practical part of the story - show them how I funded my schooling through farming with my disability. In that way they could also teach me the San farming culture in the process. I then requested that we make a

farm together so that we could exchange our various farming cultural skills and knowledge. From the scientific point of view, the strategy and method were in line with Hitchcock's (2019) belief that virtually all hunter-gatherers and former foragers in Africa supplement their livelihoods from agricultural means. In other words, encouraging the San family in local food production could enhance their nutritional values and physical wellbeing (Espeso & Carlisle, 2017; Mwangi, 2019; UN Food and Agriculture Organization, 2019; IFAD, 2019; Daño, 2019).

The whole household was very happy about such a cultural exchange project. We then cleared the backyard of the compound, about 100 Quadra meter, together and it was enough for us to start the project. We had decided to do mixed cropping. Mixed-cropping is a traditional farming method whereby the farmer plant different kinds of crops on the same piece of land at the same time (EIP-AGRI Focus Group, 2017)

Although every family member was part of the project, I insisted that we set up a focus group to manage the project. McKim (2017) and Beyea & Nicoll (2000) believed that focus groups allow participants to share their opinion and expand on each other's responses. This would enhance detail discussions on all the pending sensitive topics. By that time, I knew who the key informants were; according to their role in the community, knowledge in addition to having access to the information desired, willingness, communicability and impartiality (Family Practice, 1996; Elmusharaf, 2012; Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Therefore, Key Informants method was used to select the focus group members with the belief that they would give a good quality of data in a short time during discussions (Family Practice, 1996; Elmusharaf, 2012). There were nine (9) family members who were selected to form the focus group. The number of participants was based on experts' recommendation of sampling 4 to 10 participants in focus group discussions (Stake, 2006; McKim, 2017).

Picture 16: one of our Focus Group meeting sessions

My very first lesson that I learned from the San philosophy emerged during the soil preparation phase on the farmland. I had noted that the soil was very sandy and from my Ghanaian farming experience, such a pale-looking sandy soil would not support crop cultivation unless we applied manure to the soil. I then shared this experience with the group and wanted to know whether we could get cow dune from somewhere to manure the soil ahead of the sowing stage.

Picture 17: Farmland preparation at Platfontein, 2019

The daughter of the chief, who was always very shy, unexpectedly stood up and said that she wanted to tell me something. She spoke to me through one of the interpreters:

“Adams, from what you said, it is very true that you grew up in a village. You have eyes to see what could be obstacles ahead of you. I think that is why you came all this far in your life. Your request to learn from us is all because you want to re-examine your gained experiences and that is good...”

As shy as she was always, she refused eye contact but came to me and then held my hand and we took few steps onto to the farm plot. She fetched the soil with her hand and put it into my hand and we returned to the group. Then she said:

“The soil may look sandy but it may not be sandy. So I want you to feel the soil in your hand and tell me what you think...”

When I examine the soil in my hand, indeed, the consistency of the soil was different from what I had thought – the soil looked sandy but it was not sandy when I felt it. When I told her so she smiled and said:

“Adams, don’t be shy to keep re-examining your experiences wherever you go. You are already like that and we admire you very much...”

I thanked her repeatedly for the lessons taught to all of us. I admired how well-articulated she was in presenting her impressions about me and her general beliefs in life and the philosophy behind everything.

On our next meeting they informed me that the 100 Quadra meters land would be enough for us to plant at least fifteen different crop species including medicinal plants at the same time. I agreed with them because Vandana Shiva, an icon for Third World Knowledge Rights, noted that in sub-Saharan Africa, backyard gardens usually contain more than 60 species of crops and herbs for household consumption (Shiva, 2000). I then wanted to know what criteria we would use to select the crops to cultivate. This stage was very important to me because the selection of the crops to cultivate would reveal what their immediate and most urgent needs were. Therefore, I told them that back in Ghana when I used to farm during my schooling days, my choice of crops to cultivate was influenced

by the market demand, the time taken for the crops to mature and of course, the season. I told them that it was always a lot of work for me in the dry season because I would have to water the crops every day till harvesting.

“That is interesting... your main aim was to make money for your school. Maybe we should also think about doing that one day. We used to cultivate for our consumption. Our choice of crops and herbs to cultivate was based on their medicinal values and our needs,” a group member said.

When I asked for the details, they explained to me that their choice of crops and herbs to cultivate was influenced by the foreseeable medicinal needs in the family. Therefore, it was very important for them to consider possible treatment needs for the elderly, children, pregnant women and nursing mothers in the family. They further explained that there were some of the treatments that would require the combination of more than two kinds of herbs. Therefore, the more crops and herbs we would plant, the more we would meet family’s possible healthcare needs.

At this point during my stay, I noticed that we were more relaxed and talkative after an activity. So, we did most of our focus group discussions without scheduling special meetings. The advantage, I realized, was that the people were more relaxed and more opened during unscheduled meetings than they would have been at scheduled meetings. One afternoon while we were taking a break from the farm work, one of the elders in the group narrated to me that:

“At some specific places in the early stages of our journey from Angola, we did not have to make backyard farms. We could get all the food that we needed from hunting and gathering. There were also some places where the location of our settlement would not support hunting and gathering. In that case, we would make a farm to supplement our diet and medicinal needs. But the closer we get to mainstream society, the wider the distance between us and our traditional food and medicine”.

As a concern, another elder explained that:

“Everything, including our staple food as our heritage, has changed. I miss my original food. Any time authorities relocate us we are introduced to a new food. So I ended up

developing new taste for other people's food and in no time the new food would become my staple food. The worst is that my children who were born here in a foreign land have been disconnected from the San traditional food. This is painful to me because that part of the San/Bushman food heritage, inherited from our roots, is gone for good. These and many things make me feel very poor here..."

He added that:

"We are not used to buying food from shops, we are hunter gatherers, and I don't think it is a sinful way of life. Authorities want us to live like they do and what does that mean?"

On her part, Mandalena added that:

"Our food was also our medicine. Most of the food that we gathered had medicinal values for us. But here we are, in Platfontein, we cannot find our traditional herbs to treat even simple ailments but rather, we rely on other people's beliefs and medicine from their shops".

I then reflected on their feeling by telling them that I also had similar experience: Anytime I move into a new culture, even within Ghana, my favorite food would change, and I realized that the farther I travel from my home village, the more exotic my favorite food becomes. For example, in Africa (Ghana, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Botswana and Zimbabwe), my favorite food included maize-made food but in Germany I would say fruits, mainly apples, oranges and pomegranates. Whenever I go to Baltimore-USA, I would say crabcakes are the best. So at the end I do not really remember how my traditional food from the Gonja tribe in Ghana tastes like. However, I knew that I could always go back to trace my food heritage. Therefore, there was hope that at the right time I would get connected to my food heritage and traditions.

I then wanted to know more about how the gradual process led to the disconnection between them and some parts of their traditions, especially their food and their healing traditions as the elders just explained. Another elderly group member narrated that:

“All the seven times that we have been forcefully relocated came as a surprise! So we never had time to decide on which kind of crops and their seeds to take with us. We also never had the means to go back to any of the places we were before. Otherwise, we could have brought whatever seeds and plants we would need at the new location. By the time experience had taught us to always take the most needed herbs and crops seeds with us to anywhere we are being relocated to, the harm had already done - great deal of our food and herbal heritage is gone...”

Indeed, the most challenging stage in our farming cultural exchange project was where and how to find the fifteen indigenous crop species we wanted to plant. It was not possible for us to find most of the seeds we needed in South Africa unless someone would bring them from Namibia. It took us many days of asking their relatives and friends in the village before we managed to find just six out of the fifteen species of seeds we had hoped to plant. The seed search experiences were in line with recent studies beliefs that most seeds used by indigenous people are informally saved and shared among friends and family members or locally traded (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2019; IFAD, 2019; Daño, 2019). We then bought few exotic seeds: carrots, green beans etc. from the shops in Kimberley.

Although we were disappointed that we did not get all the seeds we wanted to plants, the practical process we went through in the farming project revealed the gradual steps that disconnected the San family from their food and herbal heritage. The nice thing was that we were able to recap memories and shared experiences without hurting our emotions, which was my main aim in introducing the farming project. By the beginning of the third month after planting, some of the crops had already matured and we started harvesting. As usual, the feeling was very rewarding to all of us, especially the group members who managed the project.

Picture 18: crops growing well

The group was inspired to take the farming project further, this time on a large scale if they would get enough resources mainly enough space and traditional seeds. This then led us to the next stage of brainstorming in how to proceed.

7.6 The San Dilemma - Cultural Erosion

My observations and notes, as discussed, showed that the targeted San people were not happy about their general situation in the community. So, I decided to get a bit of the specific situations that could be the main issues. In the follow-up interactions with the elders, I wanted to know from them whether they felt home at Platfontein with all the support from the South African government in terms of schools, a clinic, good road network and access to clean drinking water etc.. into the Platfontein community. Kakenge expressed that:

“Our current place is not home for me and my family. I miss my environment and all that existed in it. I miss my traditional house and my daily routine which is hunting and gathering. Because of this bad feeling, some of our people have abandoned the concrete houses authorities provided them and went back to our traditional land, somewhere in the bush...”

Content redacted due to uninformed consent for publication from the photographed subjects. Original photo shows the thesis author with the community. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Picture 19: A session with the chief, Kakenge Automover

His feelings expressed were in line with the detailed literature review (MRG, 2016; UN, 2009; OHCHR, 2012) that indigenous cultures were threatened with extinction as they have continued to experience the loss of access to lands, territories and natural resources. Emphases on the strong link between culture and environment among indigenous people, as they share their way of life - spiritual, cultural, social and livelihood with their traditional lands were highlighted in the literature review (Espeso & Carlisle, 2017; Conservation Watch, 2017; MRG, 2016; UNESCO, 2017).

Their feelings expressed then added meaning and perhaps answers my initial observational notes and questions: why some newly built government houses, meant for some of the forced-relocated families, were not occupied and were in bad condition. Kakenge then said to me that he would look for enough evidence and would take me around to see for myself. About six weeks later, he took me around the village. When we went along, I noted that some of the deserted houses were almost burnt down from the inside. So I wanted to know what could have been the cause of the fire. Kakenge took his time and explained to me that:

“My son, we are not used to stoves. In the San natural environment, we would set open fire with firewood in the middle of the shelter and we would all sit around it to socialize, cook and plan our activities. So the last tenants who lived in these burnt houses did not know that these modern houses are not built for that kind of life. So they ignored the stoves that were provided them by authorities and set open-fire on the floor, inside the houses, and they almost burnt themselves to death...”

He then showed me some of the burnt houses and specifically led me to some improvised houses some community members made to suit their housing wishes.

Picture 20: Burnt and rejected concrete house

Picture 21: Preferred improvised house instead

Even after such experiences were being recorded in the community, a check inside their rooms revealed that they still insisted in their preferred traditional open fire.

On my first interaction with Mandalena Automover through an interpreter, she appreciated my physical presence by saying,

“I am happy that you came all the way from Europe just to see us and be with us. We love you for that. Your presence here with us has given me hope for my children and grandchildren... You also have the same resemblance to people I knew in Angola where we started our journey many years ago. Please feel comfortable and be with us.

You are one of us... that is why you respect the San cultural values and norms...feel free and stay with us..."

Her welcome expressions suggested to me that she might have experienced what Edward Said (1978: p. 11) described as "Western style for dominating restructuring, and having authority over the Orient". On the other hand, I am of similar ethnic group with similar hunter-gatherer experiences as the San people. So, fitting into the community to work with them for better understanding of their situation was easier than it could have been with other researchers.

Picture 22: Time with Mandalena Automover

Her reference to Angola also provided an opportunity for me to follow up with a question, whether she thought her journey from Angola all the way to the current location in South Africa worth it.

"It doesn't worth it," she said. "We are being moved around like we were not human beings, like we could not be on our own, like we do not have our feelings. It is hard to accept the way we are being controlled," she said.

When I asked her, whether she felt home at Platfontein with all the government support, she answered that,

“I have been relocated 7 times, starting from Angola all the way to our current location in Platfontein-South Africa. To me, home is not where I started life back in Angola and it is also not my current place in South Africa either. To me, home is where we were recently moved from - Schmidtsdrift, 70km from Platfontein”.

In my follow-up question as to why *Schmidtsdrift* was the dearest to her heart, the 76-year-old answered that,

“Schmidtsdrift is where most of my family members are buried. So everything there in the environment has meaning to me...but I cannot go back there with my surviving family to live with our departed dear ones. I miss my departed family very much and they are just 70km away from us here in Platfontein”

One day while we were collecting firewood in the wilderness, I wanted to know from the women whether there were any hopes for them to also get their concrete houses from the state in the future. They explained to me that they would have preferred their traditional self-built San huts.

“We are not really keen on that topic because whether our current aluminum shacks or concrete houses, none would suites our preference – self built San traditional house,”
said a group member.

Some weeks later we decided to do one of our usual group-go-alongs and so we went for a walk together. During the walk, a group member explained to me that:

“...the concrete houses occupants were also provided with modern toilet facilities. However, the toilet facilities were too modern to most of the occupants and so they abandoned them and built their own toilet facilities. The modern toilet facilities are just uncomfortable. One needs time and patience to get use to them”.

They then showed me evidence (pictures 23 and 24) as we went along.

Picture 23: Preferred self-mad toilet.

Picture 24: Abandoned modern toilet

They also told me that the treated water the government provided them was tasteless. Another group member explained that:

“...there were times that some of us could no longer stand the tasteless treated pipe-water ...and some family members had to go on foot, covering more than 70km, in search of free-flowing river water”.

The San Housekeeping alongside modern equipment - the challenge

In our household, I noted that there was a gas cylinder and its burner but they were never used. My host family preferred cooking on their usual open fire to using the gas burner. They usually pack the gas burners aside and find all possible means to prepare their meals in their tradition ways as shown in the picture 25.

Picture 25: Traditional ways of cooking were preferred to a gas burner as packed aside (arrowed).

When I asked them the reason, they told me that they were not used to using gas burners. A twenty-year old mother of two then explained to me that:

“Cooking on gas stoves is difficult for us because the equipment and the process involved are not native to us. Besides that, the food cooked on the gas stoves does not taste good compare to the food cooked on open fire”.

Her sister, a mother of four, added that:

“Besides cooking, open fire in the San culture has it spiritual and healing importance. Therefore, we prefer going all the way to the nearby wilderness to gather firewood for the household to using the gas burner”.

I then told them that I knew the process involved in gathering firewood and setting up an open fire but I had not practice that for almost thirty years. Therefore, I would like to participate in the process as remembrance of my childhood. The women were very excited to hear that and from that day, I would sometimes go with them to the wilderness to collect firewood for the traditional open fire in the house. The open fire method was

kept as an important part of the San family housekeeping activities and we enjoyed the process very much together.

Picture 26: Carrying fire wood from the wilderness for our household

Picture 27: Acacia trees were the most preferred place to hang their laundry instead of the drying lines

They did not also show much interest in the electricity facilities provided them as they told me that most of them were not interested in watching television and very few had mobile

phones as their only electrical gargets. I then wanted to know whether it was as a result of lack of access or lack of interest in the phones.

“Most of us do not know how to use the phones. Besides that, we are living with all our family members and we really do not have contacts beyond the village. So our main way of receiving and passing on information is through word-of-mouth,” a group member said.

This then added meaning to the survey findings that 92% of the surveyed San participants did not have basic digital skills and 71.4% of the participants relied on word-of-mouth as their main source of news updates. There were some areas that I noticed broken electric extension wires lying on the floor and people were walking over them. I was, however, not sure whether they were livewires or not. I then concluded that the targeted San family were not yet adapted to cope with the modern ways of life. However, I knew there was still more to explore and I would also crosscheck and get the opinion of the chief, Kakenge, and Mandalena, the oldest and head of the family, through individual go-along interviews in the later stage of the study.

The Targeted San Impressions about Formal Education

In traditional communities learning is practical and elders play important roles in teaching and passing on knowledge and wisdom to the youth in the native language (Survival, 2018; Antoine et al. n.d.; Mulwafu, 2004; Gumo et al, 2012; Blackstock, 2007). In indigenous set up knowledge may focus on skills needed for survival (Gumo et al, 2012; Blackstock, 2007). On the other hand, acquiring classroom education needs a trained teacher to facilitate learning which may involve the use of a nonnative language to explain theories to learners (Survival, 2018; Antoine et al. n.d.; Gumo et al, 2012; Blackstock, 2007). Therefore, I was wondering what the situation was in the community.

When I noted that most of the children were not going to school, I started teaching them, at least art work. On any returned trips from Germany or from the USA I would bring with me educational material just to encourage the children to learn. When I was sure of the

parents' trust and appreciation in teaching the children, one day I asked some of the parents why most of the children were not in school. They gave me many reasons:

“We really do not know what they are teaching them there in the schools – are they teaching them how to read and write or they are turning them against their own San identity...? Fortunately, or unfortunately, our children do not like going to the school,” said a young father.

A young mother of three girls added that:

“The children complain that they would have to learn in English which they do not understand...we understand our children how difficult and embarrassing it would be to learn in a language you do not understand. That is why we don't want to force them to go to the school”.

The young parents' frustrations were in line with a long conversation I had with the eldest woman of the family concerning modern education for her grandchildren:

“...I do not know how my grandchildren are coping with this modern way of learning. I wish they could learn from nature where they are no lies. My granddaughter showed me pictures of giraffes and other animals in her book which she is learning about. But if she were to learn in nature she would interact with the real animals and in that way, she could also learn from them and not just about them. Animals are also teachers in that sense...”

This then drew my attention to their strong belief that the indigenous form of education was the kind of education they believed in. When I followed up on the topic, chief Kakenge explained to me during one of our go-along walks:

“Nature is the best teacher...I am not sure how this classroom way of learning can bring our grandchildren closer to relate with nature. The children sit in classroom all day and the teacher tells them about his or her experiences. In our San way of education, we guard and guide the children to experience things by themselves in nature. Then we correct them... based on how they may react to their own feelings...”

When I reminded Kakenge of the power behind modern knowledge in all aspects of life, he took his time and explained to me:

“My son, I know that it is the modern education which gives people the power to dictate to us but that does not make it better than our traditional San education. In our ancestral lands, our way of education would be enough for us to live there happily with nature. We did not need the modern way of medical treatment because we had access to our traditional herbs and medicine. What do you think, my son....?”

I told him that I respected his opinion and beliefs very much. I then told him that the topic was very interesting to me and I would like to discuss it further with the focal group members after my visit to the San Research Center at the University of Botswana in Gaborone. Indeed, when I returned to the village, I discovered more about their impressions and feelings regarding the topic. An elderly man said in a bit of anger:

“Our colonial people and even present authorities say that we are not educated and that is why we cannot read or write. But they forget that our books are deferent from their books. Our books include the bare sandy floors, stars, smell of our environment etc”.

In her opinion, a middle-aged woman added that:

“They do not even know that such books are knowledge reservoirs...otherwise they would ask for our opinion on decisions that concern our wellbeing. In fact, we were never jealous of our colonial people’s education. But now we have no choice but to let them torture our children in the name of giving them education...”

An elderly man, a retired San soldier, who saw it all at various military camps gave his opinion:

“...when they say we are stupid all because we cannot read or write, the question most of us would like to ask them is that, why did our colonial people recruit us (the San people) into the military to fight for them? My brother let me tell you something.... our main duty in the military was tracking... this means reading foot prints of the enemy and making intelligent guess for our colonial people to succeed in defeating the enemy. How could a stupid person carry out such a complicated task successfully ...?”

As they believed that nature was where “their books” were, I wished they could take me around in nature for a lesson but that was not possible at their current collation. Perhaps I should go to nature and bring them pictures of some of “their books” and ask them how they feel about such pictures. I then rescheduled my activities in order to spend some time in nature to make specific pictures of what I thought could be “their books”. Some of the pictures I came back with included endangered animals, insects, specific plants, wild fruits, different rivers etc. (see some of the pictures in appendix 6).

When I showed the pictures to an elderly family member, she was full of smiles at the beginning. She told me that she respected everything she was seeing in the pictures. Then she pointed at a rhino in one of the pictures and said:

“In nature, some things may not necessarily form part of our everyday food but they all contributed so much value to our quality of life....and that is what makes everything in nature an important book to us. For example, our men would not hunt a rhino or an elephant but that doesn’t mean that these animals were not part of our lives... we would use their faeces to treat some specific diseases etc...”

She also pointed at ostriches in one of the pictures and said to me:

“Ostriches were also not animals that our men would usually hunt but the ostrich egg is very important in the San household. We would use hallowed ostrich eggs to store water. We would also use the ostrich egg shells and their feathers to make our traditional products like bangles etc...”

In tears, she said to me:

“...I like this beautiful picture of the river. It reminds me of my mother who is no more. Rivers provided us with more than just water. Whenever I visited a river with my mother, the flowing sound of the river and the happy songs the many birds would be singing by the riverside were always good sources of very good music for us. Such good music comes with so much spiritual nourishment....”

Due to her heavy emotions, I told her that we would continue with the rest of the pictures together with the other family members another day. I then thanked her for letting me know how important the “San books” were to them.

Chief Kakenge was also concerned that the modern way of learning in confined structures known as schools could end up becoming a threat to his heritage as he expressed:

“My grandchildren are learning from confined places called the school but they are not learning from nature where my heritage began and will always be”.

Mandalena also expressed concerns that her grandchildren could lose their identity as a result of the way they were being integrated into mainstream society.

“...our children and grandchildren have no chance to learn from nature and I am worried about that. There is so much wisdom back home in nature but it seems that we will never go back home...” she added.

Content redacted due to uninformed consent for publication from the photographed subjects. Original photo shows the thesis author with the community. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Picture 28: A group go-along session with both Chief Kakenge and Mandalena

Due to the fact that they have been relocated many times till their present location, they were not sure if the current location was going to be their permanent home. However,

they expressed that even if there would be another round of relocation, they would have no choice but to follow the orders as usual.

“Forced-relocation is very humiliating and at the end you lose your confidence in many things...but we would be ready to go. After all, we would not have a say in that. Perhaps life would be better at the new place...” focus group member said.

Kakenge expressed that:

“I don’t know how I would feel if we have to be relocated again. It is always like that...we have to always follow what authorities tell us. Remember we have been relocated many times. So we can be relocated again. Of course, at some places life was better. For example, in Namibia we were closer to nature than here in Platfontein...”

On her part, Mandalena expressed that:

“Relocation is possible so I have decided not to develop relationship with the environment here. In that way it is easier to relocate...”

Unemployment and Social Vices in the Community.

I noted high levels of teenage pregnancies. Most teenage mothers and some of their babies looked malnourished. One day some of the women, including two daughters of Kakenge decided to go and show me the village clinic. On our way we were all in a very happy mood. So I took that chance and asked them whether the high numbers of teenage pregnancy in the village has a cultural meaning. The eldest among the women told me that the situation has no San cultural meaning but rather it was the consequences of the force-relocation. She then said to me:

“...look my son, I have two teenage daughters. Each has a second child but none has a husband. I help them take care of their children because they are my grandchildren. I am proud of that but as I am aging, what would happen if I join my ancestors one of these days? Who would support them...?”

A young mother of two then added that:

“We don’t have jobs... we are stigmatized in such a way that employers are not interested in employing us. So life is very hard and boring here...”

One of the women told me that she was worried about the youth and the spread of HIV/AIDS in the village and she narrated:

“Adams, sometime ago they told us that HIV/AIDS cases were on the rise in this our San community. That means it is a new development among us. In other words, we would have been better off if we were in our remote areas in our ancestral lands.”

The women also told me that alcoholism was very high and burglary cases were becoming more common in the village. When we returned home, I told Kakenge that I enjoyed my walk with the women very much. I then shared with him what I learned from the women. He said to me that he was happy to hear that. Then he said:

“There are many things I wish I could discuss with authorities. Alcoholism and drugs have become the order of the day here in the village. I do not have to tell you this as you can see it whenever we take a walk around. Most people spend their social grant on alcohol and not on food. What it means is that the government is paying us money to become alcoholics. As a chief, these are some of the things I would have love to explain to authorities if they could just listen to us”.

I then wanted to know his opinion and what he might have observed so far, as a chief, about possible domestic violence cases in the village.

“We are very peaceful people but the frustrations are changing many things among us. For example, most of the boys you see around are very violent. They don’t mind engaging in street fight. Stealing has become part of us here in Platfontein. The thieves are not from Kimberley or any other place. They are our own children who are doing that,” he said.

As the topic was about frustrations linked to domestic violence, I decided to get a balanced opinion. So the following weekend when I came to visit, I brought the topic up in order to get the opinion of the women. One woman then said to me:

“My son was a good boy when we came to Platfontein. But with time he started behaving strangely and one day he got into a street fight with somebody. The fight resulted into many bad things...and as we are speaking, he is in the care of correctional service. I don't know if he would ever come out again”.

Another woman also shared her pain that:

“As for me the most painful thing is that I do not know if my son is still alive. He got influenced by a group of very hard boys and I do not know where he is right now.... But in nature we never had such painful experiences...”

One afternoon, while we were still on the babysitting duty, one of the parents told me that thieves had broken into a nearby shop and made away with a lot of groceries. We all thought such cases could be related to the high unemployment among the youth as well as the high number of teenage alcoholics in the village. In an environment where teenagers were unstable like I was told, I thought it was very important to guide children early enough so that they may know the difference between what was theirs and what was not. So one afternoon, while I was still on babysitting duties together with five parents, I told them to let us take a walk with the children (eight children, ages between 3 and 9) to a nearby shop for me to show them how to shop. My intention was to let them know that they had no legal right to own anything in a shop if they did not pay for it. The parents agreed with me and we set off to the shop. When we got to the shop, I gave them money and asked them to take fruit juice bottles from the shelves and after that they could pay at the counter. Due to the language barrier, we had to be with the children at the counter to support them in the transactions. After the payments were done, I told them that they were now the legal owners of the fruit juice and everything they had paid for and we could return home with all that we had paid for. The parent appreciated the outing and that practical form of teaching the children.

The Targeted San Wishes and Requests

Their wishes and recommendations suggested that they would like to engage in a dialogue with authorities. A male participant expressed that:

“The authorities did their best by providing us with all the treated water, electricity, access roads and some of our San people even have the concrete houses built by the state. All these put together might have costed the authorities a lot of money. On the other hand, they could have saved all the effort and money if they had relocated us to the right place in nature where integration would have been natural for us...”

In my quest to get more details about why they thought integration in nature would have been easier and less expensive, a female participant clarified that:

“What we really need is an environment that would make it easy for us to keep and protect our identity and not the authorities to think that they are doing us good by giving us their food or their handouts. They could take us to our ancestral lands which are our preferred environment and we would survive on our own. We were always rich in our own environment. I wonder why they think that social amenities are what make life meaningful...”

Another female participant added that:

“... we are intelligent and wise and that is why we could cure all kinds of ailments with our traditional medicine but right now we all know that it is just a matter of time and we will lose all our herbal knowledge...when our elders die that would be the end. The only way out is if we could get reconnected to our heritage. So we just wish authorities could listen to us as equals....and maybe you can help us, my brother”.

On the other hand, I reminded them that cultures are actually changing and one has to adapt to such cultural changes in order to improve one’s living standards and contribute to national development. So I wanted to know from them whether my reminder made any sense in connection to their integration process. A very vocal female participant reacted to that:

“Cultures may be changing but why do we have to live like other cultures and not the other way around? Why don’t they join us in our ancestral lands, where there could be enough land for all of us but not enough modern clothes, televisions and cars?”

An elderly female participant expressed that:

“I personally do not blame our current authorities. I think the problems came from our colonial people..., they destroyed our culture, our life and turned us against our own people by recruiting us to fight against our own people...”

A male participant had a slightly different opinion as he expressed that:

“I also don’t blame the currently authorities because we were both in the same kind of situation in the past...this means we have similar experiences. Therefore, I would have expected the current authorities to understand our situation better and involve us in their policy decisions because of our similar experiences”.

Another group member expressed her hopes that:

“...for now, we try to preserve our culture and traditions by teaching our children about the San way of life - recognizing our own traditional royal leadership and also celebrating cultural events like our spiritual dance. We also try to tell our children about life in nature where there is trust among living beings. Maybe things would change one day for us...”

In terms of the way forward, chief Kakenge had expressed that:

“Unemployment is one of the big issues here... the stigma is such that employers don’t want to employ us even in jobs that we could do very well. So the best way would be to set up our own small businesses...”

The focus group participants also expressed that they were bored not being engaged in any income generating activities. A young mother expressed her frustration that:

“We don’t have jobs... so life is very hard and boring here in Platfontein...”

In finding out how to align their potential and skills to self-help initiatives, linked to the San heritage, the data revealed that participants wished they could have a wide space in their backyard to plant their own crops and medicinal plants. They were enthusiastic that they could get seeds from familiar places in the wilderness and from extended family members and friends in Namibia where they had lived for many years before they were relocated to South Africa. They stated that:

“...we wish we could go back to Namibia to bring our native crops and herbs...”

“We are talented in our Arts and Craft. We miss making our cultural products and performing our traditional dance. These are also the only ways for us to pass on our heritage to our children. If we do not teach our children and grandchildren our traditional ways of life, they have nowhere to learn them from...”

“...we can't wait to be busy...”

Their wishes and arguments were in line with the concept of Orientalism explained by Edward Said, “as a Western style for dominating restructuring, and having authority over” a specific culture (Said, 1978: p.11). The United Nations Indigenous people ' Major Group for Sustainable Development (UN-IPMG, 2019, p. 3) added to the historical point of view that indigenous people have always experienced marginalization, exclusion, and disempowerment as a result of colonization and the formation of States which “resulted in the historical injustices committed against the indigenous people through forced assimilation, implementation of discriminatory laws, policies and practices, imposition of elite democracy, authoritarian rule and exploitative economic system”. As the way forward, the UNDP (2015, p. 9) then emphasized the facts that “Indigenous people’s economic, social and cultural rights as well as civil and political rights are recognized by the international human rights framework and in particular have been specifically articulated in the Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous people to ensure that the historical inequalities faced by indigenous people are addressed and their priorities reflected including in national development plans.”

7.7 Traditional Entrepreneurship as Empowerment

As time went by, I realized that all the group members were indeed unemployed and depended on government subsidy. So, if we were not busy on the farm or in household duties then there was nothing productive to keep us busy. The group members had told me several times that the high unemployment rate among them was due to the fact that they did not have any employable skills. I agreed with them for some time but at one of our general meetings I brought the topic up for us to discuss.

I told them that I understood their unemployment situation very well. On the other hand, I remembered very well that in my home village, some grownups made their livelihood through handcraft work. I told them that hunting and farming were not the only traditional occupations but other occupations like weaving, pottery etc. were means for survival. Therefore, I wanted to know if my home cultural experiences made sense in the San culture in a rural setting. They answered me that it was the same in the San culture too. They explained to me that, actually, they were all skillful in the San handcraft and at some points they even made few souvenirs for tourist and earned some income out of that. I then praised them for having such valuable skills which could change their income situation if only they would like to take a challenge. Everybody was happy to hear that we were likely to take another learning project apart from the farming project. As the farming project was very successful, they told me that they were looking forward to hearing my new idea and what we could do together.

I then told them that I would have to buy souvenirs for my friends back in America and in Germany. But if they knew how to make souvenirs, then I would be glad to buy from them directly. They were very happy to hear that. However, they told me that they did not have the capital to buy some of the materials such as different kinds of beads, ostrich eggshells etc. to start. I told them that it was very normal one to have a business plan first before one would go out to look for the capital. Therefore, all they needed to do for us to start the handcraft project was to sit together as a group and plan what they would like to do, and I would fund them the production cost to start. We agreed on one-week period for them to do their research and present their business plan to me.

A week later I returned to follow up on them. They were prepared and waited for me with their impressive business plan. Their request was within my budget so I gave them the money to start. I then told them that I was leaving for Botswana to conduct some surveys and would be back in three weeks to buy the products. We then agreed on a three-week period for them to deliver their products. I told them that I was strict with the timing because the long-term survival of every business depends on the ability to meet deadlines. In that way, they understood that the three-week delivery period was a fair challenge we agreed on. Then I was gone for three weeks.

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Pictures 29-30: Some of the group members and their products on display.

When I returned, they had made the most beautiful San handcraft products up to standards. I then bought everything and paid them the difference left. It was one of our happy days in the village. I was very impressed about how creative they were and the fact that they showcased high levels of potentials in running a micro-enterprise.

As the outcome, the exercise brought to light how the targeted San people traditional skills and potentials could be developed into an area for inclusive growth. This gave me the direction to further discuss with them to get their consent and interest, then I could advocate for them for experts in micro-enterprise development to coach and mentor them for them to proceed on their own businesses in the direction of heritage for inclusive growth.

7.8 The San Cultural Entertainment

As time passed by, I realized that our mutual cultural exchange interactions were in a good flow. We had gained trust for one another and we were always enjoying our cultural differences. On the other hand, I am of similar cultural background with similar rural experiences as the San people. This means that our mutual cultural interactions were very African.

At this point, I revisited my aim in the study – to find possible ways to protect and promote the San cultural heritage, which should also mean beyond national and continental borders. On the other hand, I was not sure how they would react to cultures with different life experiences. Therefore, I thought it was equally important for me to share my foreign cultural experiences with them so that they may see the need to accept other cultures outside the African borders without fear of losing their own culture. In that way, we would create awareness about the importance of mutual cultural acceptance which was the desired aim of my study. The challenge for me was how to strategically present this idea to the people for them to embrace it. On the other hand, even if they reject the idea of mutual cultural exchange beyond continental borders at that moment, it would still serve the study a purpose to further investigate on how to win their interest. This then put great importance on the strategy and the method in which to share some of my foreign cultural experience with the people.

I then remembered that most of the children were not going to school. There were also few burglaries in the neighborhood and the chief told me that cases of teenage alcoholism in the village was on the rise. The chief also confirmed to me that the social issues were as a result of the cultural frustration among the people in the village. If that was the case then I would share an intercultural experience that would motivate the children to be in school where their teachers may support them cope with the socio-cultural issues around them. Therefore, I decided to celebrate my birthday with everyone and then tell them about the story behind the celebration – the beauty in being a school-going child.

My hope was to let the children and their parents know that classroom education was very important in every culture. By this time of my stay, the children related to me like their brother or their uncle and would always want me around them. In no time, I noticed that the children started to like activities that I would participate in, for example our daily walks together with their parents. So my interest then became an important voice that could direct them to take initiatives. Perhaps that was the moment for me to let them know that my best interest was to see them going to school. I wanted the children to have the impression that they could become my long-term friends if they would go to school. I then planned my survey activities in Zimbabwe in a way that I would be back in the community early enough for my birthday.

I returned to South Africa from Zimbabwe few days before my birthday in 2019. When I finally made my way to the community on road trip from Johannesburg, as usual, it was a happy moment for all of us to be together again. The following day I told the chief that I would like to celebrate my birthday with them in a bit more western way. I explained to him that it would be a party where there would be enough drinks and cake for everyone. But before the celebration, I would like to explain to the parents and their children my motivation behind the occasion. He agreed and gathered everyone for me to address them.

I told them that I did not grow up celebrating my birthdays. In my first twelve years, I could only think of naming and burial ceremonies as the most important stages in one's lifecycle. However, when I moved to the town where I started schooling at age thirteen for the first time, I was introduced to birthday celebrations by my school mates. However, I never celebrated my birthday and at a point I concluded that birthdays were for only people who had parents. It was a very painful experience that would have lasted for the rest of my life had it not been some wonderful school children in the United States of America who changed that feeling when I was already 35 years of age.

I told them that school children of the Sisters' Academy of Baltimore in the USA stopped that pain in me when they and their teachers surprised me with the best birthday celebration that I have ever had. I explained that I was sponsored by my American "adopted" family to visit them in Baltimore in 2015. As part of the visit, there were several

stage-talks that were arranged for me to interact with audiences at locations like Notre Dame of Maryland University, schools etc. and the Sisters' Academy of Baltimore was one of the schools I had the honor to interact with the school children and their teachers.

I had the honor to first talk to them as a group of the whole school where I told them about my childhood struggles to be in school and then encouraged them to learn hard. After the group talk, I was scheduled to meet them in their various class rooms for them to ask me any questions that they might have. The children inspired me with their questions and my love for them will never end. I stressed on the fact that our interactions were so special that my American family and friends keep sponsoring me to America so that I could keep in touch with school children of the Sisters' Academy of Baltimore and other places. My adopted family has since set up a scholarship fund in my name to sponsor some of the children in the school. The best result is that, I have since been receiving inspiring letters from some of the school children through the schools' administration, telling me how I inspired them to learn hard.

Picture 31: Time with the school children at the Sisters Academy in Baltimore, USA

The lesson that I learned from that experience was that if I did not go to school, it would not have been possible for me to establish my American network and get to know the school children in person. In other words, If I had dropped out of school, the pain of not celebrating my birthday would have troubled me for the rest of my life.

Therefore, I emphasized that classroom education, like the indigenous education, was not only good for us to earn our living but it could also prepare us to mutually accept other cultures and their wisdom, through which we could also get mutual healing in many ways. I then distributed learning material, including coloring books I had brought for the children from the USA and Germany, to some of the children as a way of closing the day. The chief, the parents and most of the children told me that they were all inspired to focus on classroom education.

Picture 32: Art books for some of the children

Few days before the birthday celebrations, the chief told me that his family was preparing a birthday surprise for me in a form of the San traditional dance. He then told me that they have a traditional dance group and I would see it all on my birthday. I was very surprised that they had a dance group and more surprised that they decided to honor me with such high cultural standards. On the other hand, I understood that they were very practical people and that they really loved me. So I thanked him and said to him that I was looking forward to the weekend of the celebration. By this time, I had become friends with some

policymakers within the Kimberley municipality through the initial quantitative study phase and the research-related networking. I then decided to invite some of the policymakers to join me to the village for the celebrations. I wanted all of us to witness the beauty of the San culture as it was shown in the quantitative study that there was lack of such awareness. My belief was that such personal experiences could inspire individuals to meditate deeper on indigenous people and their situation. Perhaps that could change mind sets about the way the San people in particular were viewed. Although I did not know what kind of surprise the chief and his people said they had for me, I encouraged my invited guest to come with their cameras to capture whatever that may come up. In that way, our experiences could be shared among a wide range of contacts through digital means. I believed that would already be an achievement in restoring the San People cultural identity and dignity. I was happy that my invited guests did come with professional photographers and together, we drove in a luxurious car to the village for the celebrations. When we arrived on the compound, many family members had gathered and were waiting for our arrival. The joyful manner in which we were welcomed showed that we were all in a celebration mood. The children in the family were very generous and so they had invited many of their friends from the neighborhood. I rewarded them for being generous to bring their friends to share the cake and the drinks with everyone. There were quite a number of the children who I did not know and that added so much beauty to the occasion. We then had a wonderful time sharing everything together. The parents were very happy that their children had a lot of fun with my birthday cake and drinks.

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Pictures 33-34: Sharing birthday cake at Platfontein, South Africa. January 2019

It was now time for the family to present to me their birthday surprise. We were seated on the compound while the dancers were in a room. I then remembered that, usually most cultural entertainments in my home village would start like that; audience would form a circle and wait for the dancers emerge from a room or sometimes from the nearby bush, depending on the location. This time, I did not know what to expect from my San host family. When everything was set for the group to come out, they sent a messenger to inform me that, by the culture, most of the dancers would keep their upper bodies naked so I should be aware of that before they come out. I told them that I was ready for everything.

When they came out, I realized that all the dancers were women and majority belonged to the focus group that I have been working with. I was surprised because they never told me about their musical talents and abilities until it was time for them to show me. On the other hand, I knew that by the culture, they were very practical people and I loved that about the San culture. My Gonja culture in Ghana is also like that – usually people do not boast and so one would never underestimate the others' abilities.

Content redacted due to uninformed consent for publication from the photographed subjects. Original photo shows dancing in the community. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Picture 35: The dance group of all ages

The music was a wonderful mixture of traditional drumbeats, clapping and singing together. Although there was no a lead singer to direct the flow, we all managed to participate very well, at least clapping along. Besides their melodious voices and amazing dance movements, they also took that opportunity to explain to the audience in choreography, the San herbal treatment: collecting the herbs, preparing the herbs and pounding them in a traditional mortar, and applying the herbs to the patient in need.

Everybody was impressed about their creative ways in showing us the deeper part of the San culture through their talents in the San traditional music. The dance group consisted of all age groups; children, teenagers and adults between thirty and forty years of age.

After the entertainment, the chief explained to me that the age difference among the dance group members was good for continuous learning and maintaining their San dance heritage. I then thank the chief, the dance group, my invited policymakers and all the audience for their wonderful birthday present. I told the people that I was very happy that they loved me and they gave me the very best that they had in a form of the San traditional entertainment.

Content redacted due to uninformed consent for publication from the photographed subjects. Original photo shows the thesis author with the community. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Picture 36: The choreography moments

As my aim was to make a positive change by celebrating our cultural differences, I was happy about the sequence in which our cultural exchange activities were progressing. For example, just by sharing my continental birthday celebration experiences with them, they were inspired to show me such rich cultural asserts that they possessed. So I told everybody that, indeed, mutual cultural exchange could motivate us to look within ourselves and bring the best out of us in more dignified and confident ways which could promote love and care for one another. Therefore, I reminded my host family that not all about their heritage was lost. I then encouraged them to hold onto what they were having while working hard to reconnect themselves to whatever they might have lost, for example their food and healing heritage. I then encouraged all the audience including my invited

guest, the policymakers, to join me in their minds and hearts to meditate on such a rich cultural performance linked to the situation that the San people were in. Then I left for Germany to present at a conference and would be back to continue with the research. I planned to follow up on whether our meditations would result in something as the outcome of the celebration.

Indeed, as the outcome of the celebrations, when I returned to the community about five months later, I had gained the full support of all my invited guest in my research efforts to reconnect the affected San people to their intangible heritage. Some of them told me that my approach to the San people issues was very unique and they were very interested in the research final findings and recommendations as my input in the San people issues. Tables 6, 7 and 8 in section 7.9 below show the tabulated summaries of key themes and the related responses revealed in the qualitative phase.

7.9 Summary of Key Qualitative Results by Themes

Table 6: The Research Key Themes and Key Summary Responses

Key Research Themes	Key Responses
<p>(1) Looking at their long journey consisting of several forced-relocations, where would the Automover San family call their home and why?</p>	<p><i>...Our current place is not home for me and my family. I miss my environment and all that existed in it. I miss my traditional house and my daily routine which is hunting and gathering. Because of this bad feeling, some of our people have abandoned the concrete houses authorities provided them and went back to our traditional land, somewhere in the bush...</i></p> <p><i>....as for me home is where most of my family members are buried....everything there in the environment has meaning to me...but we cannot go back....</i></p>
<p>(2) To what extent could such relocations affect their preferences in regard to food and traditions as their heritage?</p>	<p><i>...If you tell them, you miss your culture, they say we are thinking backwards...If you tell them you miss your native food, they would tell you that you are not civilized. They see our traditional medicine and healing methods primitive and less important compare to their healing methods in the clinics....</i></p> <p><i>.... the closer we get to mainstream society, the wider the distance between us and our traditional food and medicine..."</i></p>

	<p><i>“...there were times that some of us could no longer stand the tasteless treated pipe-water ...and some family members had to go on foot, covering more than 70km, in search of free-flowing river water...”</i></p>
<p><i>(3) What are their impressions about classroom education instead of their traditional education?</i></p>	<p><i>...nature is the best teacher ...I am not sure how this classroom way of learning can bring our grandchildren closer to relate with nature...</i></p> <p><i>...In our ancestral lands, our way of education would be enough for us to live there happily with nature ...</i></p> <p><i>...I know that digital media has something to do with computers and mobile phones...I know that it is the modern education which gives people the power to dictate to us but that does not make it better than our traditional San education...</i></p> <p><i>...We really do not know what they are teaching our children there in the schools – are they teaching them how to read and write or they are turning them against their own San identity...? Fortunately, or unfortunately, our children do not like going to the school...”</i></p> <p><i>....the children complain that they would have to learn in English which they do not understand...we understand our children how difficult and embarrassing it would be to learn in a language you do not understand. That is why we don't want to force them to go to the school”</i></p>

Table 7: Key Themes and the Effect on Achieving the San Cultural Protection and Preservation

Key Theme Revealed	The Effect on Social Capital and Cultural Tourism	Key Responses
A disconnect between the affected San and authorities	Lack of Trust and Mutual Respect	<p><i>...it's a pity that authorities never listened to our concerns...they tell us what to do. Otherwise, there are many things I wish I could discuss with authorities...</i></p> <p><i>...my son, you are one of the very few visitors we can trust....so feel free and talk to us...</i></p> <p><i>...we have received many researchers here but none could help us improve our situation...</i></p>
Lack of the San cultural awareness and support from authorities	The San doesn't feel home at Platfontein	<p><i>...we don't feel at home here..... we miss home...</i></p> <p><i>...I miss our relationship with home – in nature. Here, people call it nature but we call it home...</i></p> <p><i>...There is so much wisdom back home in nature but it seems that we will never go back home...</i></p>
	Their food heritage has been eroded	<p><i>...I am sorry but we simply do not have what we would call food...we lost our food heritage...</i></p>
	They lost their traditional healing heritage	<p><i>...I miss our traditional medicine and our native food...</i></p> <p><i>...Authorities see our traditional medicine and healing methods primitive and less important compare to their healing methods in the clinics....</i></p>
	They lost their San housing tradition	<p><i>...whether our current aluminum shacks or concrete houses, none would suite our preference – self built San traditional house...</i></p>
	Their housekeeping methods are being eroded	<p><i>...Cooking on gas stoves is difficult for us because the equipment and the process involved are not native to us. Besides that, the food</i></p>

		<p><i>cooked on the gas stoves does not taste good compare to the food cooked on open fire...</i></p>
	<p>Formal education is a challenge to the affected San people</p>	<p><i>...We really do not know what they are teaching our children in the schools – are they teaching them how to read and write or they are turning them against their own San identity...? Fortunately, or unfortunately, our children do not like going to the school...</i></p>
	<p>High unemployment</p>	<p><i>...We don't have jobs... we are stigmatized in such a way that employers are not interested in employing us. So life is very hard and boring here...</i></p>
	<p>Teenage pregnancy, alcoholism, theft and aggression on the rise</p>	<p><i>...There are many things I wish I could discuss with authorities. Alcoholism and drugs have become the order of the day here in the village. I do not have to tell you this as you can see it whenever we take a walk around. Most people spend their social grant on alcohol and not on food. What it means is that the government is paying us money to become alcoholics. As a chief, these are some of the things I would have loved to explain to authorities if they could just listen to us...</i></p> <p><i>...My son was a good boy when we came to Platfontein. But with time he started behaving strangely and one day he got into a street fight with somebody. The fight resulted into many bad things...and as we are speaking, he is in the care of correctional service. I don't know if he would ever come out again...</i></p> <p><i>...As for me the most painful thing is that I do not know if my son is still alive. He got influenced by a group of very hard boys and I do not know where he is right now.... But in nature we never had such painful experiences...</i></p>

Table 8: Possibilities of building Social Capital through the San Cultural Tourism linked to the UN-SDGs

Key Theme Revealed	Empowerment Model	Their Key Responses
Empowerment: Traditional Entrepreneurship linked to Social Capital and Cultural Tourism	The San handicraft	<p><i>...We can run business...we may not be used to managing large quantities of cash but we can count very well in our language...</i></p> <p><i>...We are talented in our Arts and Craft. We miss making our cultural products and performing our traditional dance. These are also the only ways for us to pass on our heritage to our children. If we do not teach our children and grandchildren our traditional ways of life, they have nowhere to learn them from...</i></p>
	The San Music and dance	<p><i>...we can dance and so we have our traditional dancing group but we don't know how to proceed with all our skills...</i></p> <p><i>...with the right education and access to resource we believe we can run our music businesses to support our families...</i></p>
	Agro-entrepreneurship	<p><i>...we can make our own farms and grow our traditional food and herbs...</i></p>
	Digital Inclusion	<p><i>...We are not afraid of technology so we want to learn about digital media and all the good things it comes with...</i></p> <p><i>...You can teach us about digital media and we will learn..., we trust you because you love us ...so you will not teach us something that will confuse our minds...</i></p>

See the complete summary responses in Tables 9 and 10 below

My Complete Notes from the Go-Along Interviews

Table 9: Cases 1 and 2: The main themes by open-ended and unstructured questions.

Open-ended/ unstructured Questions	Case 1 – with chief Kakenge. Most Reveling Responses included:	Case 2 – with Mandalena Most Reveling Responses included:
1. Where would you call home?	<p><i>...I don't feel at home here in Platfontein...</i></p> <p><i>...Our current place is not home for me and my family. I miss my environment and all that existed in it.</i></p> <p><i>...We are not used to their modern way of life...</i></p> <p><i>...We are not used to buying food from shops, we are hunter-gatherers and I don't think it is a sinful way of life...</i></p> <p><i>... authorities want us to live like they do and what does that mean?...</i></p> <p><i>... It is really hard but that is the stage we are - they always dictate to us...</i></p> <p><i>.....it takes so much time and a lot of money to build a modern home... but if that is one's choice then there is no problem. It becomes a big problem if</i></p>	<p><i>...I don't feel home here but I have no choice...</i></p> <p><i>...We are being moved around like we were not human beings, like we could not be on our own, like we do not have our feelings. It is hard to accept the way we are being controlled...</i></p> <p><i>...I have been relocated 7 times, starting from Angola all the way to our current location in Platfontein-South Africa. To me, home is not where I started life back in Angola and it is also</i></p>

	<p><i>you are forced to live such an expensive but boring life. First of all, it is very difficult to breathe if you sleep in these modern houses. There is very little light in them and in the night you cannot even see the stars from the rooms...everything about those modern houses is very uncomfortable. One always needs time to get use to them....</i></p>	<p><i>not my current place in South Africa either. To me, home is where we were recently moved from - Schmidtsdrift, 70km from Platfontein...</i></p> <p><i>....Schmidtsdrift is where most of my family members are buried. So everything there in the environment has meaning to me.....but I cannot go back there with my surviving family to live with our departed dear ones. I miss my departed family very much and they are just 70km away from us here in Platfontein...</i></p> <p><i>....The same way, the treated water they provided us with is tasteless compare to the river-water in nature...</i></p>
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<p>2. What other specific concerns do you want us to discuss about?</p>	<p><i>... Alcoholism and drugs have become the order of the day. I do not have to tell you this as you can see it whenever we take a walk around. Most people spend their social grant on alcohol and not on food.</i></p> <p><i>...We are very peaceful people but the frustrating situation is changing many things among us. For example, most of the boys you see around are very violent. They don't mind engaging in street fight. Stealing has become part of us here in platfontein. The thieves are not from Kimberley or any other place. They are our own children who are doing that...</i></p> <p><i>...I miss our relationship with home – in nature. Here, people call it nature but we call it home...</i></p> <p><i>...We knew our way around and we were confident that our environment would continue to tell us the truth about life...</i></p> <p><i>...Here in mainstream society, we are never sure what is the truth but we don't have a choice...</i></p>	<p><i>...I miss our traditional medicine and our native food...</i></p> <p><i>...For us, our food is our medicine so it is good to have good food and to also teach the children where to get good food...</i></p> <p><i>...There is so much wisdom back home in nature but it seems that we will never go back home...</i></p> <p><i>...I like this beautiful picture of the river. It reminds me of my mother who is no more. Revers provided us with more than just water. Whenever I visited a river with my mother, the flowing sound of the river and the happy songs the many birds would be singing by the riverside</i></p>
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	<p><i>...I wish I could go to Namibia to bring, at least, some of our native seeds and plants...</i></p> <p><i>...So the best way would be to set up our own small businesses..."</i></p> <p><i>...we have been receiving many researchers and officials here who would tell us that they are here to investigate our situation but nothing changes for one reason...they do not listen to us but they would bring us what they think are the solutions to our situation...</i></p> <p><i>.... Some foreign researchers have taken advantage of our situation and exploited us a lot. For example, Madam XX came here to write my autobiography. She made so many pictures of me and my family. Then she left and she never came back. Someone found out that she went around the world exhibiting our pictures at important cultural events and making money for herself. This is just one of such examples and reasons why we don't trust most of the people who come here as researchers etc...</i></p>	<p><i>were always good sources of very good music for us. Such good music comes with so much spiritual nourishment.....</i></p>
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<p>3. What are your impressions about digital media?</p>	<p><i>...You can teach us about digital media and we will learn....</i></p> <p><i>...Nothing is difficult if you put your mind into it...</i></p> <p><i>...So we know that it will be important to learn about it so that we can also use the computers and the phones like any other person...</i></p>	<p><i>..first of all, we trust you because you love us ...</i></p> <p><i>...So you will not teach us something that will confuse our minds...</i></p> <p><i>...When you are ready please come back to visit us. I will tell everyone to come and learn digital media from you...</i></p> <p><i>... I want to know more about digital media...</i></p> <p><i>... I will encourage my children and my grandchildren to learn from you...</i></p>
<p>4. What do you think about the fact that the relocation has made it possible for your children and grandchildren to be in school like any other South African child?</p>	<p><i>...nature is the best teacher...</i></p> <p><i>...I am not sure how this classroom way of learning can bring our grandchildren closer to relate with nature...</i></p> <p><i>...the children sit in classroom all day and the teacher tells them about his or her experiences... in our San way of education, we guard and guide the</i></p>	<p><i>...I do not know how my grandchildren are coping with this modern way of learning...</i></p> <p><i>...I wish they could learn from nature where they are no lies...</i></p>

	<p><i>children to experience things by themselves in nature...</i></p> <p><i>...Then we correct them based on how they may react to their feelings...</i></p> <p><i>...I know that it is the modern education which give people the power to dictate to us but that does not make it better than our traditional San education...</i></p> <p><i>...In our ancestral lands, our way of education would be enough for us to live there happily with nature ...</i></p>	<p><i>...My granddaughter showed me pictures of giraffes and other animals in here book which she is learning about...</i></p> <p><i>...But if she were to learn in nature she would interact with the real animals and in that way, she could also learn from them and not just about them...</i></p> <p><i>...Animals are also teachers in that sense...</i></p>
<p>5. What if there is another round of relocation. How would you feel?</p>	<p><i>....I don't know how I would feel if we have to be relocated again...It is always like that; we have to always follow what authorities tell us. Remember we have been relocated many times. So we can be relocated again. Of course, at some places life was better. For example, in Namibia we were closer to nature than here in Platfontein...</i></p>	<p><i>...Relocation is possible so I have decided not to develop relationship with the environment here. In that way it is easier to relocate...</i></p> <p><i>...Life is not good if you are disconnected from your departed souls; I miss our</i></p>

		<p><i>ancestral land. I wish they could take us back...</i></p>
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Case 3: Focus Group Discussions and the main themes by questions

The aim was to further explore the themes that emerged from the literature review, the survey results, cases 1 and 2 and linked to the research questions. Focus group participants were asked about their experiences and their wishes.

Table 10: Participant Action Discussions and the Main Themes by Questions

<p>Open-ended Questions</p>	<p>Most Reveling Responses.</p>
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<p>1. How would you describe your everyday life in your current home?</p>	<p><i>...we are not really keen on that topic because whether our current aluminum shacks or concrete houses, none would suites our preference – self built San traditional house...</i></p> <p><i>...We feel confined, and we are tired of not having anything to do...</i></p> <p><i>...We miss our daily routines including gathering. Why can't they bring us to where we were?...</i></p> <p><i>...We knew how to get what we wanted at our former places we lived...</i></p> <p><i>...there were times that some of us could no longer stand the tasteless treated pipe-water... and some family members had to go on foot, covering more than 70km, in search of free-flowing river water...</i></p> <p><i>...the modern toilet facilities are just uncomfortable. One needs time and patience to get use to them...</i></p>
<p>2. How would you improve upon your everyday lives as a group?</p> <p>(Empowerment)</p>	<p><i>...we can make our own farms and grow our traditional food and herbs...</i></p> <p><i>...We have skills in farming, handicraft and music...</i></p>
	<p><i>...please, come and teach us and also prepare us to start our small businesses...</i></p>

<p>3. How competent are you in running a modern business with all the cash flows management etc.? (Empowerment)</p>	<p><i>...So you just have to teach us a bit more about modern business and we would be glad to start...</i></p>
<p>4. How familiar are you with digital media potentials? (Empowerment)</p>	<p><i>...Most of us do not know how to use the phones. Besides, we are living with all our family members and we really do not have contacts beyond the village. So our main way of receiving and passing on information is through word-of-mouth....</i></p> <p><i>...They say that digital media is good for people with their mobile phones and computers...</i></p> <p><i>...We are not afraid of technology so we want to learn about digital media and all the good things it comes with...</i></p> <p><i>...Come and teach us and we will learn from you and practice everything that it comes with...</i></p> <p><i>...We believe that keeping in touch with other cultures by our own will would not destroy our identity...</i></p>
<p>5. What steps have you taken to preserve your culture and traditions all this while? (concerns)</p>	<p><i>...we also try to tell our children about life in nature where there is trust among living beings...</i></p> <p><i>...My son was a good boy when we came to Platfontein. But with time he started behaving strangely and got into a street fight and many bad things happened. As we are speaking, he is in the care of correctional service. I don't know if he would ever come out again....</i></p>

	<p><i>...look my son, I have two teenage daughters. Each has a second child but none has a husband. I help them take care of their children because they are my grandchildren. I am proud of that but as I am aging what would happen if I join my ancestors one of these days? Who would support them...?</i></p> <p><i>...sometime ago they told us that HIV/AIDS cases were on the rise in this our San community. That means it is a new development. In other words, we would have been better off if we were in our remote areas in our ancestral lands....</i></p> <p><i>...we are very peaceful people otherwise how could you keep militarized people under such a long term of humiliation and mistreatment and expect them to remain calm....?</i></p> <p><i>...they do not even know that such books are knowledge reservoirs...otherwise they would ask for our opinion on decisions that concern our wellbeing....</i></p> <p><i>...in fact, we were never jealous of our colonial people's education. But now we have no choice but to let them torture our children in the name of giving them education...</i></p> <p><i>...let me also add that we are intelligent and wise and that is why we could cure all kinds of ailments with our traditional medicine but right now we all know that it just a matter of time and we lose all our herbal knowledge...when our elders die that would be the end. The only way out is if we could get reconnected to our heritage. So we just wish authorities could listen to us as equals....and maybe you can help us</i></p>
<p>6. What support do you give to your</p>	<p><i>...We really do not know what they are teaching them there in the schools – are they teaching them how to read and write or</i></p>

<p>children/grandchildren to be in school? (concern)</p>	<p><i>they are turning them against their own San identity...It could be both...</i></p> <p><i>...Fortunately, or unfortunately, our children do not like going to the school...</i></p> <p><i>.... The children complain that they would have to learn in English which they do not understand...</i></p> <p><i>...We understand our children how difficult and embarrassing it would be to learn in a language you do not understand. That is why we don't want to force them to go to the school...</i></p> <p><i>...So our children only go to school if they want...</i></p> <p><i>...they say that we are not educated and that is why we cannot read or write. But they forgot that our books are deferent from their books. Our books include the bare sandy floors, stars, smell of our environment etc...</i></p>
<p>7. What if there is another round of relocation? How would you feel? (concerns)</p>	<p><i>...We would be ready to go. After all, we would not have a say in that...</i></p> <p><i>...Perhaps life would be better at the new place. We would have loved to go back to where we were once in Namibia...</i></p> <p><i>...We miss some specific plants and food there in Namibia...</i></p> <p><i>...Maybe one day we will go back there in Namibia...</i></p> <p><i>...Force-relocation is very humiliating and at the end you lose your confidence in many things...!</i></p>

See the complete field notes and dairies including pictures in appendix 6.

CHAPTER 9: CONVERGENT ANALYSIS

The aim in chapter 9 is to discuss and figure out areas for policy and stakeholders' intervention. Therefore, this chapter gives details of data triangulation technique that I used to analyze the data gathered in the study. The chapter will bring together an analysis of the data using interpretivist approach. Interpretive researchers use wide range of interconnected means to find better ways to read more meaning and understanding to cases they study (Denzin & Lincoln, 2008; Cohen et al, 2003; O'Neill & Perivolaris, 2015). As already discussed, the technical framework used included the data collection, data analysis, data validation by respondents, data triangulation, and data representation. Sub headings and categories were used to organize and reduce raw data into meaningful pieces and to transform the meaningful pieces into credible results of the entire study in order to make an impact in the research community.

The data gathered is of two sets - *quantitative* statistical results, *observations* and the *participants action* interviews in the *qualitative* phase. Several follow-up sessions were held to get clarifications and validation from the participants. The data collected was organized accordingly and attention was given to emerging categories that would help determine how cultural diplomacy linked to the UN-SDGs could safeguard the affected San people cultural heritage. The categories from each data collection were compared to identify urgent themes that would give detailed understanding of the targeted San people situation. The summaries of the findings in each method were tabulated, compared, contrasted and related in order to discover similarities and differences as key pattern and themes. The two data sets were then *converged* in some cases and *interpreted* to give a clear and credible overview of the targeted San people situation. A narrative format was also used to provide detailed descriptions of the San people situation as well as direct quotations to provide access to the thoughts of the participants.

On one hand, the discussions focused on the potential, skills and willingness of the affected San people to reconnect to their lost intangible heritage. On the other hand, the discussions highlight the disconnect between the affected San people and the

responsible policymakers in their forced relocation processes as the main issue revealed in the study. The discussions went on to propose a theory of change to implement the study outcome and to reconnect the San people to their lost heritage. A mediation and negotiation action plan to advocate for the San is put in place to give meaning to how the study outcome made a change in the lives of the affected San people in the Platfontein community. The success stories as the study impact linked to the theory of Cultural Diplomacy and the UN-SDGs policies are discussed and outline as the benefits of the study to the research community. The long-term monitoring and evaluation strategy to sustain the study impact is also outlined and discussed.

9.1 A Recap of the Quantitative Key Findings

In recapping the quantitative findings, although respondents were drawn from civil servants/government officials, individual cultural advocates, business executives from the private sector, cultural research was given less priority as 54% of the 375 responded that there was no need to research more about indigenous cultures, like the San ethnic group. Higher percentage of respondents (67%) believed that the indigenous way of life was a shame to the African identity. The survey further revealed that although 67% of the respondents believed that the indigenous way of life was a shame to the African identity, higher percentage (70%) of respondents wished that indigenous people should be integrated into mainstream society for “a better life”. In other words, some of the respondents (33%) who believed that the indigenous way of life is original, still wished that indigenous people should be integrated into mainstream society. However, the targeted San people who are being integrated into mainstream society at Platfontein thought otherwise as most of the respondents (74%) described their everyday lives at Platfontein as “hectic and depressive.” It then makes sense that 62% expressed that there was no future for preserving and promoting their heritage.

The survey also revealed that Digital governance competence levels among policymakers was very low. Only 3% of the 375 the authorities responded that their digital competences

in understanding the global digital infrastructure and ideologies and managing the related networks – at expert level, were above the basics. Digital literacy level among the targeted San people was also very low. Majority (92%) of the 77 surveyed San people answered that their internet skills were below the basics. This may be linked to the fact that most of the respondents (70%) answered that they could not read or write. It then makes sense that their main source of information exchange was through word-of-mouth, which however, has its social support functions as revealed in the qualitative phase. The quantitative facts then complimented and validated the following key issues revealed in the qualitative phase:

9.2 A Disconnect Between the Affected San and Authorities.

The study revealed a disconnect between authorities and the affected San in their integration process. The affected San family feels that authorities do not include them in policy decisions but would rather impose the decisions on them. The San then feel neglected for a very long time and therefore, there is no mutual trust and respect between the affected San and the responsible authorities. Although the San understand that their forced-relocation was enforced by their colonial masters in the 1960s, however, the San is disappointed that the postcolonial governments have not done much to restore their dignity and cultural identity as some expressed in the qualitative interviews that:

“...I personally do not blame our current authorities. I think the problems came from our colonial people..., they destroyed our culture, our life and turned us against our own people by recruiting us to fight against our own people...”

“...I also don't blame the currently authorities because we were both in the same kind of situation in the past...this means we have similar experiences. Therefore, I would have expected the current authorities to understand our situation better and involve us in their policy decisions because of our similar experiences...”

Such experiences and expressions have distorted effective communications between the San and authorities and eventually disconnected them. The disconnect then led to lack

of the San cultural awareness by authorities which then became the main cause of the San cultural erosion and the negative impact it has on the San cultural tourism and social capital. The specific consequences the study revealed include the following:

A Breach in the UN Human Rights

The detailed qualitative interviews and observations revealed that the lack of the San cultural awareness as indigenous people and the contribution they could make to cultural tourism and social capital led to a breach in UN Human rights on the part of authorities by taking away the targeted San people's right to traditional means of livelihood options and quality of life. Both mentally and psychologically, it is very hard for the affected San family to cope with the modern ways of life. For example, sleeping in government provided concrete houses instead of their self-made huts, using gas stoves instead of their usual open fire, shopping in modern shops instead of gathering/hunting in their ancestral lands, adjusting to the taste of new food instead of their staple food as their heritage. They were also not used to modern laundry and toilet facilities. For example, acacia trees were their most preferred places to hang their laundry instead of the modern drying lines. They preferred their self-built toilet facilities instead of the modern toilets the state provided them. It then makes sense when noted by various UN reports (UN, 2015; UN Chronicle, 2017) that indigenous people in most countries are sidelined in efforts to achieve the UN Sustainable Development Goals and that indigenous people commonly face additional disadvantages and discrimination in all aspects of their rights.

The San Cultural Erosion

The systematic forced-relocation process has eroded the San heritage. The affected San family has lost their connection with various parts of their cultural history and knowledge, their cultural practices and heritage that are connected to their ancestral lands. For example, they have been disconnected from their daily activities such as hunting-gathering, traditional ways of making a meal, crop cultivation, storytelling, setting up open

fire for rituals and socialization purposes which all have their cultural significance to the San people. They believe that their indigenous medicinal plants and staple food, as key aspects of the San intangible heritage, have disappeared as a result of the numerous forced relocations that they have experienced. In both the quantitative survey and the qualitative go-along discussions, it was revealed that the social amenities that authorities provided to the community did not necessarily make the community a home for most of the San people. They expressed that they would have preferred living in their ancestral land. The reason given by the oldest among the affected family was that their ancestral land was where most of their family members were buried and everything there in their ancestral environment had meaning to their existence. Therefore, converging the two data sets revealed that the affected San family members can no longer practice their traditions as part of their cultural rights outlined in the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous people (UN, 2007) and as linked to the SDG goals noted in SDGs 4, 10, 11 and 16 (Petti et al., 2020; ICCROM, 2018; UNESCO-Courier, 2017).

Word-of-mouth Communications in the San Community Distorted

The survey revealed that most of the affected San people (71.4%) main source of information was through word-of-mouth. This then raised curiosity to explore further, through observations in the qualitative phase, to know more about the word-of-mouth way of information exchange and perhaps its social importance among the targeted San people. The word-of-mouth way of information exchange may be considered less effective and slow compare to mainstream way of information exchange through digital means (GSMA, 2015; GSMA, 2014; Portland, 2016). However, through the go-along interviews with the San family, it was realized that the word-of-mouth way of transmitting information encourages physical movement and interaction among the people as they move from one compound to the other and allows for storytelling – sharing personal experiences as an enrichment of their past and a continuation of their cultural heritage through the different geographical locations, communities and generations. In the process, the San community members would provide physical support to one another, especially physical care for the elderly and the sick. However, the current situation of the San does not support the word-of-mouth mode of communication.

The San people situation then highlighted Minority Rights Group International (MRG, 2016) report that although indigenous people have an extraordinarily rich and diverse cultural heritage, their cultural values and norms are yet to receive adequate recognition or protection. Their situation is also in contradiction to the UN human rights and culturally sensitive policies outlined to achieve the SDGs (UN Chronicle, 2017; UN, 2015; Global Policy Forum, 2002; UNESCO World Report, 2009). Soft Power Experts (British Council, 2020; Cummings, 2009; Cull et al., 2015; Nye, 2017) emphasized the importance of local empowerment as the basis for cultural diplomacy through indigenous cultural heritage promotion and protection.

9.3 Empowerment Possibilities for the San Community

The emergence of the qualitative and quantitative sets of data gave direction to address some of the urgent issues revealed in the study, for example unemployment. The high unemployment rate, teenage alcoholism and social vices that participant in the qualitative interviews narrated could have been the reasons why most of the surveyed percipients (74%) described their life in the community as *Hectic and Depressive*. In order to address the unemployment situation in the community, the study explored the San people potentials and revealed that the San people traditional skills could play a crucial role in promoting national cultural tourism.

The study findings are in line with UNESCO beliefs that the intangible aspect of heritage contributes to daily quality of life among indigenous communities (Petronela, 2016; UNESCO, 2017; UNESCO, 2006). The San intangible heritage represents the San cultural wealth which may be complex but should be carefully preserved, as it could be in danger of disappearing (UNESCO, 2006; UN-IPMG, 2019). According to the South African National Heritage Council (2017) and UN-IPMG (2019) all forms of cultures, whether tangible or intangible, are the reflection of the people's unique ways of doing things. UNESCO (2017) then emphasized that the fragile nature of intangible cultural heritage and the important role it plays in maintaining cultural diversity in the face of the dynamic modern world call for global policy enhancement to save all aspects of intangible

heritage. This then implies that, the affected San people potential and resilience revealed in the study are in line with international standards and recommendations as soft power resources to be developed towards the realization of the UN SDGs (UN Chronicle, 2007; McPherson et al., 2017). As to which concept to adopt, soft power experts and cultural organization highlighted a need to mainstream the UN SDGs policies to reflect the importance of indigenous cultural heritage development as channels to promote cultural diplomacy (UNESCO, 2017; UN-IPMG, 2019; The South African National Heritage Council, 2017; British Council, 2018; McPherson et al., 2017; Portland, 2016; ICD, 2014; Cull et al., 2015; Nye, 2017; ICD, 2017).

Traditional Entrepreneurship linked to Cultural Tourism and the UN-SDGs Policies

As revealed in the qualitative study, the affected San people traditional skills and potentials in farming, micro-business management, music and dance are clear guidance to how interventions could proceed to design specific processes that could enhance the San people livelihood security and at the same time promote cultural tourism as well as the UN-SDG 11 policies. Many countries have embraced their indigenous cultures as their national asset linked to entrepreneurship as a means to eradicate extreme poverty, enhance social inclusion, eliminate inequalities and creating sustainable economic growth and thus aligning and embracing the UN SDGs 1 and 11 policies (ICCRUM, 2018; UNESCO-Courier, 2017; British Council, 2020). The success stories of the British Council's *Cultural Heritage for Inclusive Growth* programme which was embraced by Kenya, Vietnam and Colombia (British Council, 2018) worth sharing, as an example, with authorities and stakeholders responsible for the affected San people.

Possibilities to Cooperate and Build Diverse Capital

The study found out that cooperating with the San people in their integration process can save the responsible state and stakeholders more resources and build social capital for the San people. As revealed in the go-along interviews, if the affected San people had a choice, they would have preferred having their own ways of housing, cooking methods

and choosing their traditional household equipment instead of the government-built concrete houses and the gas stoves provided to some of the affected families. Such an imposed way of life by the authorities, from the human right point of view, did not only infringe upon the affected San people basic rights (OECD, 2020; UNESCO, 2017; Franchi, 2014; UNESCO, 2003) but might have also costed the state and stakeholders more money. It then makes sense when the UN SDG target 11.4 calls for collaborative efforts and resources to promote and protect the global cultural and natural heritage (Espeso & Carlisle, 2017; Petti et al., 2020; ICCROM, 2018; UNESCO-Courier, 2017).

Digital platforms can be used to create awareness about the importance of the San ways of life among policymakers.

Majority of the authorities and stakeholders (302 out of 375) responded that social media platforms were their main sources of information. It then makes sense that, on the average, 77% of the respondents go online every hour. The survey also revealed that 87% of the total respondents wished to get daily news updates on cultural related topics such as cultural events, music, sports and tourism. This then suggests that San advocates could use digital platforms to draw the attention of policymakers and stakeholders to the importance of indigenous ways of life. Although digital literacy level among the San people was low, they expressed their willingness and determination to acquire digital skills so that they could participate in online discussions and for self-advocacy.

9.4 Summation of the Research Key Findings linked to the Original Objectives

Table 11: Summary of Key Findings

Key Themes Revealed	Challenges in achieving cultural protection and preservation	Resolution measures
<p>1. A disconnect between the affected San people and authorities: Authorities lack awareness about the San culture as indigenous people and the contribution they could make to national cultural tourism and social capital.</p>	<p>A need to build trust and mutual respect in order to close the gap between the San and the responsible authorities</p>	<p>Advocacy/mediation through multi-stakeholder dialogue</p>
<p>2. A breach in the UN- Human Rights: Both mentally and psychologically, it is hard for the affected San people to cope with the modern ways of life.</p>	<p>A need to recognize the affected San entitlement to the UN basic human rights to practice and maintain their culture</p>	
<p>3. The San Culture has been eroded: The affected San people have lost their connection with various parts of their cultural history and knowledge, word-of-mouth communication, their cultural practices and heritage that are connected to their ancestral lands.</p>	<p>They need space/land where they can practice their culture, food and healing heritage, housing, farming practices, traditional housekeeping etc.</p>	
<p>4. Empowerment: The San people exhibited traditional skills that can play a crucial role in promoting national cultural tourism linked to the acceleration of UN-SDGs.</p>	<p>A need to fully explore and train their skills and competences linked to cultural entrepreneurship and national tourism</p>	
<p>5. A need for multi-stakeholder Cooperation: Cooperating with the San people in their integration process can save the responsible state and stakeholders more resources and could build diverse capital for the San people.</p>	<p>Networking and exposure/creating awareness about the importance of the San culture link to nation branding</p>	

The research aim was to investigate and explore sustainable and effective ways that would enhance a two-way approach - Cultural Diplomacy linked to Indigenous Cultural Heritage promotion. The three (3) main objectives which were explored in the research are concluded below:

- 1) *To investigate how the San Cultural Heritage can be aligned with the UN-SDGs, especially SDG 11, to protect their Heritage and used as a form of Cultural Diplomacy by the Nation.*

In exploring objective (1), the study uncovered a bias and a breach in UN human rights on the part of the local government and policymakers by taking away the targeted San people's right to traditional means of livelihood options, healing methods and quality of life. As discussed above, the emotional expressions of the affected San family in the qualitative go-along interviews were in contradiction to the UN SDG 11 which sought to resolve global cultural dominance and economic inequalities and therefore advocate for the protection of universal values of human rights, equality, mutual respect and shared responsibility for the conditions of all people (UN, 2015; UNESCO Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity, 2001). The study findings are also in contradiction to the human rights-based and culturally sensitive approach to the UN SDGs which insist on the need to engage indigenous people in sustainable development through culturally sensitive approach in regards to respect for and inclusion of indigenous people's world-views, perspectives, experiences, and concepts of development (UN, 2015; UN Chronicle, 2007; UNESCO Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity, 2001). This then calls for a theory of change through the two-way approach to heritage promotion and protection (British Council, 2018; McPherson et al., 2017; Portland, 2016; ICD, 2014; Cull et al., 2015; Nye, 2017; ICD, 2017) to resolve the issues between the affected San people and authorities through a dialogue.

However, it is equally crucial to note that based on what the study has revealed and supported by earlier arguments, (Said, 1978; Moosavinia et al., 2011; Shabanirad & Marandi, 2015; Cull et al., 2015; Iseke & Desmoulins, 2015), the two-way approach would only make sense if respect for human rights and cultural sensitivity would be prioritized in

the dialogue and not appropriation of the people and removal of their cultural beliefs and ways of life. The two-way approach requires policymakers to understand and appreciate indigenous knowledge systems and ways of life rather than requiring indigenous people to instantly leave their way of life and adopt to mainstream society for Western education and ways of life (UN Chronicle, 2007; Barnhardt & Kawagley 2005 referenced in Iseke & Desmoulins, 2015). For instance, the targeted San people experiences demonstrate the problem of policymakers dictating a top-down approach in integrating indigenous people. According to the survey results, policymakers believe that indigenous people should be integrated into mainstream society for a better life. On the contrary, the targeted San people did not welcome that belief as they explained that having access to social amenities such as electricity, treated water etc. do not necessarily make their life better. So, they were not in agreement that mainstream ways of life were better than their indigenous ways of life, but they were eventually imposed on them.

Despite the difficulties faced by the targeted San people, they exhibited skills in traditional handcraft and traditional farming methods. They also demonstrated potential in running micro-enterprises linked to their cultural products and produce to supplement their livelihood if they are empowered with enough resources. Although this provided local government and policymakers the means to link the San people potential to cultural tourism as a way of implementing the SDG target 11.4, the study result showed a disconnect between the affected San people and the policymakers. In order to close the gap between the affected San people and the local government and reconnect the San people to their lost heritage, *mediation* then became a key word in addressing the research objective (1).

- 2) *To investigate the awareness, by policy makers and stakeholders of the San cultural heritage as both tangible and intangible assets for promotion and protection by government.*

As discussed in the detailed literature review, the establishment of global reputable organizations such as the United Nations Permanent Forum on Indigenous Issues (UNPFII), Survival International, Indigenous Environmental Network, the World Council

of Indigenous People , and many national organisations along with series of declarations on indigenous issues by UN agencies and international groups, have influenced the case study assumptions that policymakers were well informed about the importance of indigenous ways of life. For example, the importance of indigenous people and their communities in development was recognized at the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development-*Earth Summit Conference* in Rio de Janeiro in June 1992 (OHCHR, 2012). Further study commissioned by the *Working Group on Indigenous Populations* on land rights and indigenous people “confirmed that access to land and resources is crucial for the survival of indigenous people” and therefore, recommended to “governments to consult with indigenous people” in their cultural resources’ management (OHCHR, 2012, p. 2). The UN Declaration on the rights of indigenous people also provided the minimal standard for member states to engage with indigenous people in developmental policies (UNESCO, 2019).

However, in addressing the study objective (2), the study revealed that policymakers did not see the need to adopt the San people viewpoint into policy framework but would rather impose decisions on them. Some of the surveyed policymakers described the San way of life as “primitive,” “backwards” and a shame to the African identity. As such, most of the surveyed policymakers did not see a need to prioritize indigenous cultural research in national cultural policy development nor in diplomatic relations. They would simply prefer integrating indigenous people into mainstream society for what they referred to as “a better life”.

Therefore, the key issue revealed, on the part of the policymakers was lack of awareness about the cultural values and norms of the San people heritage. On the part of the affected San people, they did not trust and did not also believe that the local government and policymakers would ever listen to their concerns or consider granting them their wishes to reconnect to their lost heritage. These outstanding issues then suggested how crucial it is to present the study outcome in the right context (cultural language) in order to transmit the cultural meaning of the San people situation to policymakers and possible stakeholders through a dialogue.

- 3) *To contribute to a growing body of theory that demonstrates the role of cultural heritage protection and promotion as a form of cultural diplomacy.*

The study outcome has provided a clear guide to bridge the gap between the local government and the affected San people and to reconnect the San people to their lost heritage. This then highlighted the relevance of the study outcome as a catalyst of positive change and therefore, a new dimension of scientific work that set a foundation for further development of a theory that promotes the two-way heritage inclusion linked to the UN-SDG target 11.

The study key findings discussed above could lead any affected indigenous cultures to the feeling of cultural dominance and mistrust (UNESCO, 2001; Conservation Watch, 2017: October 11; OHCHR, 2012; MRG, 2000; UN, 2009; Survival, 2014; Survival, 2017) as in the case of the affected San family. Edward Said (Said, 1978 and Moosavinia et al., 2011) then argued that any measures to convince natives and for that matter indigenous people of their inferiority – making them doubt themselves in representing their interest in developmental policies could be seen as a way of cultural dominance, originating from the concept of Orientalism. Such an approach in development may not be native to the San or indigenous populations. Orientalism is closely related to the concept of the *Self* and the *Other* which is at the heart of Postcolonialism (Moosavinia, et al., 2011; Said, 1978) and therefore, may not necessarily be a recommended concept for preserving and promoting the African indigenous cultural heritage but one that should be railed against and called out for what it is. Perhaps that was why UNESCO emphasized on a need for respect and recognition of indigenous cultures as cultures of equal rights and as part of the global universal cultures in cultural relations (UNESCO, 2001). Other cultural advocates also called for recognition of equality between cultures and the recognition that every tribe must be given equal access to fundamental rights (UNESCO, 2019; Survival, 2018; Portland, 2016; MRG, 2016; Prodi, 2002; OHCHR, 2012; Conservation Watch, 2017). The situation of affected San people also highlighted the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights advocacy that the progress of indigenous people's knowledge is based on centuries of their close relationship with nature, and therefore, needs to be protected for sustainable development (OHCHR, 2012).

As to how such rich cultures and their knowledge could be protected and promoted for national development, the African Commission on Human and People ' Rights (ACHPR) and the International Work Group for Indigenous Affairs (IWGIA) alongside the UN-SDGs 11, 1, 3 & 4 policies highlighted a need for policymakers to explore more about such varieties of rich resources as both tangible and intangible heritage for national development (ACHPR & IWGIA, 2006; British Council, 2020; UN, 2015; UN Chronicle, 2007). The South African National Heritage Council (2017) and the South Africa Department of Arts and Culture (2019) also emphasized a need to protect and enhance intangible cultural heritage in order to improve the living standards of indigenous people. Although the recommended theoretical approach comes with policies of the UN SDGs which could provide good means for policymakers to show engagement in cultural heritage promotion and at the same time enhance growth in cultural tourism, one would wonder whether the approach would be considered by authorities as the treatment given to the affected San people is not in line with the UN SDG policies.

Perhaps it is a lost opportunity to link to promote local cultural traditions as cultural diplomacy since they are going against the SDG policies. On the other hand, perhaps if I prove to the local government, policymakers and stakeholders with the study outcome, from the autoethnographic perspective, that the San heritage promotion and protection would be an investment in cultural tourism for the nation and towards the realization of the UN-SDGs (Nocca, 2017; McPherson et al., 2017; Nye, 2017; Moualla & McPherson, 2019; Lin & Hongtao, 2017) authorities may consider adopting the recommended concept and principles outlined by experts (British Council, 2018; McPherson et al., 2017; Portland, 2016; ICD, 2014; Cull et al., 2015; Nye, 2017; ICD, 2017). The British Council's programme, "*cultural heritage for inclusive growth as a catalyst for change,*" has provided African nations a crucial cultural lens to view indigenous cultural heritage as an asset and a crucial tool to develop a country's cultural tourism for soft power and cultural diplomacy (British Council, 2018). This worth sharing with authorities and linked to the research findings in my advocacy.

9.5 The Implemented Theory of Change

The implemented two-way theory of change - indigenous cultural heritage development as channels to promote cultural diplomacy and the UN-SDGs policies was recommended by soft power experts (British Council, 2018; McPherson et al., 2017; Portland, 2016; Cull et al., 2015; Nye, 2017; ICD, 2017). The theory would first and foremost bridge the gap between the affected San people and authorities and create awareness about the situation and related culturally sensitive issues that might have been left out in the San integration process. The evidence-based findings in the case study could play a key role in enhancing a balanced cultural policy framework (see figure 8 below). This would guide the responsible policymakers and stakeholders to realize that the San heritage promotion would be an enhancement of cultural diplomacy for national development.

Figure 8: A balanced cultural policy framework. (Adapted from British Council, 2018; GSMA, 2014; McClory, 2015)

In order to define my role in this concept with my research evidence, the British Council (2020, pp. 7) highlighted that it is crucial for promoters of the UN-SDGs policies to analyze “the UN SDGs through a cultural lens and the benefit of this to achieve the given goals, targets and indicators.” According to the UN Sustainable Development Goals Report (2019), although support for implementing the UN SDGs is gaining momentum, creative strategies in regard to commitments and policies from governments and the private sector still remain urgent. This makes it crucial for stakeholders to redefine and strategize policy approaches in the implementation of the SDGs so as to include the perspectives, concerns, experiences and world views of indigenous people towards the realization of the UN SDGs (UNDP, 2015; UNESCO-Courier, 2017).

My autoethnographic background which influenced my choice of methodology to carry out the study, would be an asset for me to translate the research key findings into a theory of change and linked to the UN-SDG policies. The process would lead to an informed policy framework to safeguard the affected San people and their heritage (see below).

9.6 Translating the Study Outcome into the UN-SDGs Policy Framework linked to Traditional means of livelihood

The UN-SDG11 policies have emphasized that inclusion through cultural resources should prioritize local empowerment as a sustainable approach in developing indigenous communities (UN Food and Agriculture Organization, 2019; United Nations Sustainable Development Group Report, 2019; UN Gender Snapshot, 2019). This then added meaning to Struthers & Nzika (2019) and OECD (2020) arguments that promoting indigenous entrepreneurship also means enhancing indigenous people’s livelihood through their own source of revenue from businesses that promote traditional knowledge and values. However, the affected San people situation shows otherwise. UNESCO policies then emphasized the need for policies to adopt an integrated approach which converge issues regarding indigenous people’s livelihood security and their cultural resource management as means to accelerate the SDGs (UNESCO-Courier, 2017; UNDP, 2015). The British Council and UNESCO believe that strategic and innovative

approaches in protecting and promoting cultural heritage should be targeted at empowering indigenous communities so that they can actively participate in sharing and protecting their heritage as their contribution towards an all-inclusive sustainable economic development of a nation (British Council, 2018; UNESCO World Report, 2009).

The UN SDGs aim “to ensure social protection for the poor and vulnerable, increasing access to basic services” for marginalized tribes by dignified means (British Council, 2020: p. 17). This means that arts and cultural oriented business activities could play a crucial role in addressing issues regarding skill development, sustainable and inclusive growth and employability as outlined by the SDGs policies (ICCROM, 2018; UNESCO-Courier, 2017; Moualla & McPherson, 2019; British Council, 2018). This suggests that the San people potentials that are documented in the research could enrich the nation’s cultural and creative industries, which if aligned with cultural tourism as a means to safeguard the San cultural heritage, could lead to job creation among the San people, poverty reduction and sustainable economic growth for the nation (Carlisle et al. 2021; UNESCO-Courier, 2017; Moualla, & McPherson, 2019; British Council, 2018; Nye, 2017; ICCROM, 2018).

However, developmental theories and policies need to be simplified through a cultural lens to make sense to local authorities and stakeholders. For example, my traditional and modern experiences made it possible for me to understand that hunting-gathering as means of securing livelihood in the San culture may seem very difficult and very dangerous to “outsiders” as policymakers. The outsider may then empathically recommend government handouts instead. The process involved in the San traditional cooking methods for example, on open fire etc., may be considered time consuming to an outsider and so, the outsider may recommend gas stoves instead.

On the other hand, I know that, to the San people, such traditional daily activities may not be about just survival means but rather the pride in holding onto their intangible heritage that was passed down to them from generations. Therefore, such cultural practices remain as the main bonds between the people and their departed loved ones. For example, not only did the affected San people argued that the food prepared through the

traditional methods tasted better but they also argued that their traditional ways of cooking were the only alternatives for them to keep teaching their children and grandchildren about the San food heritage and cultural identity.

In my interaction with mainstream African families, I realized that sometimes showing hospitality to a guest could start with offering the guest western food, the latest electronic means of entertainment and perhaps showing off with all that would tell the guest about how westernized the host has become. In rural communities, for example in my Ghanaian rural life and the related experiences, hospitality is all about taking the guest through cultural traditions which usually start from the traditional homemade food. In other words, any other food other than the specific traditional food would usually not be considered as “food” but as a sign of poverty, detachment from culture and betrayal of tradition. This specific Ghanaian cultural experience was found to be the same with the San culture. For example, as revealed in the study, when I requested to have traditional San food from my host family, chief Kakenge said to me that he was very sad that since I arrived, his family had not been able to welcome me with the San food culture. Almost in tears, he said to me,

“It is all because we do not have food ... What we eat is not our staple food so I am sorry but we simply do not have what we would call food...,”

However, Kakenge and the rest of his family were very happy to give me what they had and were proud of - a cultural entertainment, as a present for my birthday; a celebration that touched the hearts of invited policymakers and stakeholders and led them to meditate on the San people situation.

A Critical look at the San Means of Transmitting Information

In the San community, the social benefits that comes with the word-of-mouth way of transmitting information may not be underestimated. Although the word-of-mouth way of transmitting information may be seen less effective to an outsider (GSMA, 2015; GSMA, 2014; Portland, 2016), the process involves movement which then enhances physical

social bonding as community members would go around and provide physical support to one another, especially physical care for the elderly and the sick. Such interactions also make it possible for community members to observe and note many things about their communities which may need communal attention. For example, community infrastructural development projects such as maintaining shrines, heritage sights, or sharing ideas for the benefit of the community (Survival, 2018; Antoine et al. n.d.; Mulwafu, 2004; Gumo et al, 2012; Blackstock, 2007). For instance, experienced elders would predict weather forecast or would warn community members ahead of possible dangers by just observing what nature presents to them at any giving time. For example, to an outsider, the bare sandy floors may not mean anything other than just a sandy floor (Gumo et al, 2012; Blackstock, 2007). But to an experienced indigenous person, the bare sandy floors are more than printing press; they may depict important information such as migration of animals and all that might have gone unseen within and around their village but may concern their lives (Antoine et al. n.d.; Mulwafu, 2004; Gumo et al, 2012; Blackstock, 2007). Therefore, the significance of word-of-mouth way of information exchange among the San people has multiple community support functions and should be encouraged and ties in precisely with the UN SDG11 & 16 which promote respect for cultural diversity, human rights and cultural understanding (UN, 2017; UNESCO-Courier, 2017).

Merging Formal and Informal Education

The interdependence between nature and humans is acceptable to African indigenous communities (Mulwafu, 2004; Rusinga et al, 2010; Gumo et al, 2012). To indigenous communities, the values and practices within their natural environment are linked to their spiritual and close relationship with their ancestral land which helps them to maintain their identity and make things possible for survival (Rusinga et al, 2010; Gumo et al, 2012; Survival, 2018; UN-Indigenous People, n.d.). In other words, the understanding of indigenous people's social structure - the interdependence between indigenous people and their ancestral environment should be considered crucial in any plan to integrate them into mainstream society (Gumo et al, 2012; Survival, 2018). For example, in Western educational approaches, spirituality may not make sense in the classroom but in

indigenous cultures, spiritual dimensions could be very necessary components in the process of acquiring knowledge (South African National Heritage Council, 2017; Survival, 2018; Antoine et al. n.d.). Although learners may not necessarily be subjected to hold onto any specific religious denomination or practice, the spiritual aspect in learning and development among indigenous people may not be ignored in a policy framework to integrate them (Survival, 2018; Antoine et al. n.d.; Mulwafu, 2004; Gumo et al, 2012; Blackstock, 2007). According to Blackstock (2007), the executive director of the First Nations Child and Family Caring Society of Canada argued that the interconnected perspectives of emotions, spirituality, reasoning and physical existence in indigenous ways of acquiring knowledge are crucial in universal human development and wellbeing. This means that, in the process of integrating indigenous people, it is crucial for policymakers to note that just as Western knowledge in development is valuable and worth constant improvement, indigenous knowledge which is more of enhancing spiritual development, emotional growth, self-awareness, social growth and human connectivity should be of equal importance for national development (Blackstock, 2007; Nakata et al., 2012; Areli, 2015).

Perhaps if the specific situations and definitions of the targeted San people ways of life, as described above, are adequately narrated and presented from the sociocultural and autoethnographic point of view to authorities, they may fully realize and appreciate the link between the San heritage promotion and the SDG 11 policies. This could be a starting point for both parties to build mutual trust, respect and transparency towards good relationships in order to close the gap between them and at the same time reconnect the affected San people to their heritage. As outline in the study findings, the mediation efforts would focus on reconnecting the affected San people to their food and healing heritage, their traditional handcraft link to micro-entrepreneurship as important areas of social and economic inclusion (see below sections).

9.7 Key Impact of the Study Outcome – Original Contribution to Practice

My advocacy and mediation plan to reconnect the targeted San people to their heritage was very successful as summarized in Table 12 below. The study made a huge impact on the lives of the San people in the community. This success was due to the fact that I developed participatory approaches, as a theory of change discussed (section 9.5), using the research evidence-based data linked to my local knowledge to engage authorities and stakeholder in a participatory manner.

In order to maintain ethical standards, I had to first of all, discuss the identified issues further with the affected San people to get their consent. Then we agreed to proceed as a team to collaborate and work with cultural intermediaries, NGOs and other stakeholders to discuss the research findings in detail, focusing on the main areas explored; the need to re-enforce the San People's food and healing heritage and empower them in their traditional skills (handcraft) linked to micro-entrepreneurship as possible means to restore their heritage as well their livelihood.

I then initiated a mediation process (see action plan in Table 12) together with the South African local NGO, Diamond Creative Vision Hub (DCVH) as my main collaborator to present the study outcome to some influential officials at the local government in the Northern Cape Municipal Assembly in South Africa. The action plan was a roadmap I used to engage the affected San people and the responsible authorities and stakeholders in a dialogue to reflect on the study evidence linked to the theory of change. The aim was to discuss the need to close the gap between authorities and the San people and then reconnect the affected San people to their heritage as well as their livelihood. Therefore, evidence of the key issues revealed in the study were the focus. The process involved presentation sessions in various forms, feedback sessions, open discussions and exhibition of the San handcraft.

Table 12: Advocacy Action Plan to Engage Authorities and Stakeholders

The Responsible Persons	Targeted Authorities, Stakeholders/Industry/Institution
<p>Edward Matiwane, the Director of DCVH, and his team; +27 81 544 3464</p> <p>Francis Adams as the principal researcher/policy advisor francisadams2004@yahoo.com</p> <p>Peter Kakenge (San representative) +27 79 863 1081</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Northern Cape Municipal Assembly • The various ministries: Ministry of Economic Development etc. • Sol Plaatjie University-Kimberley • Platfontein Communal Property Association (CPA) • Houses of Traditional Leaders • The South African National Defense Force (SANDF) • Airports Company South Africa (ACSA), Kimberley
Key Activities	Outcome
<p>1) Reminded authorities and stakeholders of the urgency of the SDG 11.4 policies and a need to revisit government policies which have led to loss of the San traditional livelihood practices, traditional knowledge, cultural and spiritual practices all of which contribute to severe poverty, social disintegration, and loss of the San dignity and cultural identity.</p> <p>2) In simple terms, I explained the two-way approach concept to cultural heritage promotion to authorities, highlighting how the San cultural heritage acts as a vehicle for cultural diplomacy and thus it should be important for policymakers to recognize the cultural potential of the San people and</p>	<p>1) The affected San people handcraft project was registered as an official business co-operative. This gave them the chance to officially produce the San handcraft products for their livelihood.</p> <p>2) The management team of Airports Company South Africa (ACSA) was inspired to allocate a space at the Kimberley airport to be renovated (on the ACSA cost) for the San Handcraft Co-operative to use as a retail shop for their products. This would help the co-operative to sell their products to a large range of tourists. DCVH has since negotiated a lease agreement draft with the ACSA and returned for edits.</p> <p>3) The Platfontein Community Property Association (CPA), as custodian of the Indigenous People’s land, released fifteen (15) hectares of land to the affected Automover extended family in the outskirts of the Platfontein community to relocate.</p>

repackage such potential into innovative ways towards the realization of the UN-SDGs.

3) Reminded authorities and stakeholders that States could use the San cultural heritage as soft power to showcase their compliance to achieve the UN-SDGs, their commitment to adhere to international human right standards and transparency in an all-inclusive governance.

4) Advocated that empowerment of the San people, as means of soft power enhancement, plays an important role in realizing the UN-SDGs as well as nation branding.

4)The affected San people were also given permission to start building their traditional houses on the new land as part of their cultural right. This success from my advocacy approach was an enhancement to the UN human rights and culturally sensitive policies outlined to achieve the SDGs implementation.

Pictures 37-38: The San family building their traditional house on the new land

5) The South African National Defense Force (SANDF) has come on board through their “*Project Koba Tlala*” which is an initiative headed by the SANDF to ensure and promote food security in the country. Arrangements have been finalized with DCVH to engage the San people through agro-entrepreneurship to supply six military bases in the region with fresh indigenous farm produce including various types of native vegetable; an enhancement to the San people sustainable livelihood security in the community.

Content redacted due to uninformed consent for publication from the photographed subjects. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

6) DCVH Northern Cape intermedia literacy and digital skills among the youth and learners in the research community. work with the elders/cultural to enhance

As outline in table 12 above, I have demonstrated that in order to make real change, the importance of developing a cultural relationship alongside a clear theory of change is paramount for any cultural diplomacy benefits for government and industry. I have made a unique contribution to the lives of the San people and the understanding of policymakers; in part beyond my expectations at the start of the study.

9.8 Insuring Sustainability of the Study Impact

My intervention strategy has provided some guidelines for stakeholders to sustain the study impact on the San community. These guidelines included a need for continuous dialogue between the San people and stakeholders, continuous awareness about the San people cultural needs and issues regarding their empowerment linked to their heritage promotion and protection. Therefore, I advocated for a continuous monitoring and evaluation system that would involve diverse stakeholders to ensure the long-term impact of my intervention on the lives of the San people. My strategy to have such a monitoring and evaluation system in place was a reflection on British Council (2020, p. 5) belief that although the 2030 Agenda was signed by the UN member states by national governments, “its implementation relies on the contributions from the local, regional and national governments, international organisations and development agencies, civil society organisations, and the private sector.”

As the outcome, progress-monitoring agreement was concluded between the local government (Northern Cape Municipal Assembly) and DCVH. In the agreement, DCVH responsibilities would include monitoring progress and follow up on any outstanding issues between stakeholders and the affected San people. Progress would be communicated periodically among all stakeholders and lessons learned would be shared for the purpose of further improvement. Outstanding issues would be discussed, and experts’ advice would be called for as a way of focusing on the two-way approach to the San heritage protection and promotion. As a follow-up input, I was invited to South Africa by DCVH to give an input in a form of creative policy advice to policymakers, traditional leaders and some NGOs in the Northern Cape Municipality (see detailed invitation letter

in appendix 7). This was seen as an enhancement to the study impact on the San people in the research community.

Although uncertainties about long-term sustainability of the study impact may exist, more than one and half years after the projects were initiated, everything has been sustained with progress. Therefore, I feel I have made an outstanding and original contribution to the lives of the targeted San people and to the understanding of policymakers in promoting and protecting indigenous cultural heritage. I feel I have scientifically demonstrated that in order to make real change in indigenous people's lives, developing cultural relationships is key to cultural diplomacy alongside a clear theory of change (road map) linked to the UN SDGs policies is crucial for any cultural diplomacy strategies for national development.

CHAPTER 10: RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

This chapter outlines summaries of the research achievements including the impact made on the lives of the targeted San people in Platfontein, South Africa. Key findings and achievements are reviewed and summarized to give meaning to how the study contributes to original knowledge. Key achievements in the study are reflected on as a buildup on previous scientific studies. The importance of evidence-based research linked to practical approaches in policy advocacy are outlined and discussed as the study key contribution to original Knowledge. The study contribution to global and local policy and practice as well as the UN-SDGs policy development are also discussed. Recommendations, self-reflection and proposed areas for future research are also outlined as conclusion of the chapter and the study.

10.1 Summary of the Research Key Findings and Contribution to Original Knowledge

The study adapted critical theory from the perspective of cultural diplomacy (Nye, 2017; ICCROM, 2018; UNESCO-Courier, 2017; British Council, 2018; Horkheimer, 1982; Said, 1978) to find a balance in cultural policy in order to protect forced-relocated San people and in South Africa. The study findings and outcomes are firstly a build-up on academic studies by Cultural Organizations as well as Critical Theory Experts (British Council, 2018; McPherson et al., 2017; Portland, 2016; Cull et al., 2015; Nye, 2017; ICD, 2017; Putmans, 1993; Horkheimer, 1982) to develop a theory that promote the two-way approach - indigenous cultural heritage development as channels to promote cultural diplomacy. The exclusion of indigenous people in policy decision (UN-IPMG, 2019; UNDP, 2015) is of concern to the study outcome. In other words, the majority of national policies and indigenous research to date are yet to adopt mechanisms that would focus on the contribution of indigenous values and norms to national development (Putmans, 1993; Said, 1978; Horkheimer, 1982; Nye, 2017). This then resulted in a gap between indigenous people and policymakers. The existing gap between indigenous people and policymakers then calls for a concern as it does not support the implementation of the UN-SDGs policies (Petti et al., 2020; ICCROM, 2018; UNESCO-Courier, 2017).

On the other hand, the study theoretical contribution to knowledge and development was intended for practical implementation. The emancipation-focused nature of the research led the study process to Putmans (1993) emphases on bonding and bridging capital for understanding and transitioning change; making it possible for the study outcomes to bridge the gap between policymakers and the affected San people and then reconnected the San people to their heritage. Table 13 shows the key themes and the participatory advocay approach that led to the research immense impact on the targeted San and their community.

Table 13: A participatory approach guide to engage authorities and to advocate for the UN-SDG11 policies

Key Theme	Relevance	Required Actions
<p>Evidence-based Research Findings</p>	<p>To motivate authorities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to review and re-negotiate policy framework that would include indigenous people view point etc. 	<p>A phenomenological in-depth study:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • preferably by or including a lead seasoned native researcher with similar cultural background as the target group
<p>A Need to Guide Authorities and Stakeholders to Read Meaning to Research Evidence</p>	<p>To enhance mutual respect and trust:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to appreciate opinions of the San people and put the San cultural heritage on the frontline of policy development. • provide policy implementers a toolkit for similar intercultural negotiations <p>To promote indigenous entrepreneurship:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to enhance traditional sources of decent revenue and livelihood security • employment creation through cultural exchange and cultural tourism 	<p>Empowerment – Build Diverse Capital and link to cultural exchange and cultural tourism:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplify and explain developmental theories linked to research evidence (cultural resources) and nation branding concepts <p>Clarify contradictory developmental policies and donor expectations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • highlight Indigenous people rights to participate in political debates and self-advocacy

My unique approach to go-along interviews working with both the tribe and policy makers allowed for relationship building to take place and demonstrated that the theory of change that I followed and implemented, directly led to a change in policy and practice for the San community but could be used as a longitudinal model for others. The importance of my role and ability to fit in with the group by embedding myself and living with them on various visits allowed for a level of trust and empathy, that could not have been achieved by standard research interviews etc.. as summarized in the below sections.

10.2 The Impact of Evidence-based Research on Indigenous Cultural Heritage Promotion linked to the UN-SDGs Policies

The study evidence-based findings were the key catalysts that led to the study achievements. In the presentations and discussions, I reminded stakeholders with the research evidence that the targeted San people were skilled in traditional handcraft and traditional farming methods to make their traditional products and produce for their livelihood. The research evidence showed to authorities and stakeholders were very practical: I had invited key influential policymakers to witness the San Music and dance and the harvest from the community farming project. Samples of the San people art and craft products alongside their registered co-operative documents were exhibited as evidence showing that the affected San people were well prepared to start their business co-operative. These then became huge motivation to management of ACSA to give their support by leasing out the retail space at the Kimberley Airport for the San people to get access to both local and international markets to grow their business co-operative.

In exploring possible digital means for the San cultural heritage to act as a vehicle for cultural diplomacy towards the realization of the SDGs, it was very crucial to refer authorities to the low digital literacy level among the affected San People as the study revealed (see part 2-Table 2: **Q3 & Q4**) and linked to some themes that emerged from the literature review. For example, 92% of the surveyed San people responded that they do not have internet skills. This motivated authorities to task DCVH to find out strategic

ways to enhance literacy and digital skills among the youth and learners in the research community.

The San Music and Dance as a Key Evidence

One key evidence I capitalized on in my advocacy discussions for the San, was the San music and dance and how urgent they needed space in order to practice and maintain such important forms of the San intangible heritage. The San dance event was one of my practical and strategic data collection approaches in the study. It was an impactful strategy as the invited guests told me that my approach to the San people issues was very unique and they were very interested in the research final findings and recommendations as my input in the San people issues.

Therefore, I reminded stakeholders of the San dance event and highlighted that the affected San people were rich in cultural entertainment. I explained to them that Nye (2017) and Lin et al. (2017) believed that popular culture, which focuses on cultural entertainment such as the San music and dance, provides vital channels through which cultural heritage promotion could empower indigenous people. The San family members were still holding onto their traditional dance as their intangible heritage despite all the cultural challenges they have been through. They expressed their wish to promote their traditional dance and have since formed a dance group, ready to bring the dance to the general public as a way of promoting the San heritage. The San dance is an important part of their culture as it can be in a form of a prayer to the spirits of their ancestors and to the gods for spiritual healing and guidance (Exploring Africa, 2019; Drum Connection, 2017). The San in this study are willing to bring such an important aspect of their heritage to both local and international audience in a form of cultural entertainment. This then creates an opportunity for policy interventions that could focus on empowering the targeted San people to promote their intangible heritage for their livelihood as outlined by earlier studies (Exploring Africa, 2019; UNESCO, 2017; British Council, 2013; UN-IPMG, 2019; The South African National Heritage Council, 2017; British Council, 2018; McPherson et al., 2017; Portland, 2016; ICD, 2014; Cull et al., 2015; Nye, 2017; ICD, 2017).

The UK Approach as an Example

It then worth reminding the stakeholders and authorities that “music is a major UK export, worth around US\$2 billion annually” (British Council, 2013, p. 8). In analyzing how the UK success in promoting music heritage could be a model for Africa and its indigenous music promotion, it worth noting that African music through the Atlantic Slave Trade, has had a profound effect on the music of the Western World, shaping the music culture of the Western World to become what it is today (Drum Connection, 2017; Ikoro & Ekevere, 2016; Portfolio, 2013; Clarence, 2016; Barbados Tourism Encyclopedia, 2017; UNESCO World Report, 2009; International Capoeira Angola Foundation, 2016).

As part of the African cultural identity from the historical point of view, I reminded the stakeholders that archaeologists have noted that the oldest human bones were “unearthed on the continent of Africa, and so it follows then that the first music must also have emanated from the expressive and rhythmic limbs and dark countenances of the African people,” (Lincoln, 2016, para. 3). This then supported earlier arguments that the rich diversity of the African continent and its many traditions including music have spread throughout the western world through the African cultural curiosity and by colonial era interactions (Portfolio, 2013; International Capoeira Angola Foundation, 2016; Capoeira-World.com, 2015; Goncalves-Borrega, 2017; UNESCO World Report, 2009; Almeida, 1996). Perhaps that was why UNESCO emphasized the need to enhance the transfer of indigenous African creativity in music to the rest of the world for mutual cultural benefits (UNESCO-The Slave Rout, 2017). This then makes it meaningful to promote the San music and dance for mutual cultural benefits. Therefore, the resilience of the affected San people in holding onto their heritage and their passion to promote their dance has provided an opportunity for policy interventions that should see decisionmakers and stakeholders across sectors, working together to empower and promote the San dance group as part of the SDG1, 8, 11, & 17 policies (UNESCO-The Slave Rout, 2017; UN Economic and Social Council, 2017; UN Gender Snapshot, 2019).

I have also embraced the need for the San people to have their own traditional houses as their cultural right and linked my research evidence to a theory of change in *The*

Culture White Paper from the UK's Department for Digital, Culture, Media and Sport (British Council 2020, Open Government Licence, 2016) and the UN SDGs which maintained that cultural diversity enhances quality of life and well-being of indigenous communities. In other words, embracing cultural diversity would set a platform for diverse cultural practices which would allow people to do things differently and add value to quality of life and national development (British Council 2020, Open Government Licence, 2016; UNESCO, 2018). This then makes cultural diversity a crucial tool for development as it “contribute to addressing divisive narratives, fostering human experiences, supporting skills development and building empowerment” (British Council 2020: p. 11).

The San Dance as Means of Cultural Exchange

In relating to modern-day mutual cultural exchange and the related mutual benefits, although Ikoro & Ekevere (2016) and Arowolo (2010) believed that the African indigenous beliefs suffered a long history of suppression by colonists, leading to the loss of a number of indigenous songs and musical instruments through western Christian churches, others (Drum Connection, 2017; UNESCO-The Slave Rout, 2017) maintained that the modern Africans could also boast of a number of musical styles and instruments that were made possible through the colonial era interactions. Therefore, cultural exchange through the San traditional music would not only add value to the global cultural diversity and expressions but would also serve mutual learning purpose for the San to be more creative in their music and dance.

The San people might have been known to the international community through other forms but cultural exchange programs that would include the San traditional music and dance stand a high chance of changing the global public opinion about the San culture and identity (UNESCO-The Slave Rout, 2017). This then required authorities to engage the affected San people in a dialogue to define roles that should lead the dance group to enough resources and appropriate platforms to showcase their music and dance to the general public as means of heritage inclusion.

My ability to practicalize the theories linked to the research findings then motivated the authorities to release the 15-hectare land for the affected San family to fully practice their

culture and preserve it. The San family got the necessary support and encouragement to go ahead with putting up their preferred San traditional houses on their newly demarcated land. This then became one of my study key achievements as it has made a difference in the lives of the San people and serves as a new dimension of study that could be further developed to accelerate the SDGs policies.

Picture 40: The proud San cultural display at Platfontein-South Africa, January 2019.

10.3 A Need to Guide Authorities and Stakeholders to Read Meaning to Research Evidence

My advocacy presentations and feedback sessions were focused on simplifying theories of cultural diplomacy linked to social inclusion and embracing Said's (1978) belief that if I didn't advocate for the group, then I was no better than any other western researcher trying to use the group as a research object rather than research with them for a better shared understanding that could lead to mutual respect, trust and change as key elements of cultural diplomacy action. Therefore, I thought I had a moral obligation to use

the research key findings to guide authorities into the beauty of the San heritage and the need to protect and promote it.

From the theoretical point of view, I aligned my research findings to the South Africa Department of Arts and Culture (2019) and the South African National Heritage Council (2017) advocacy for indigenous cultures that trade in indigenous cultural goods and services would be an investment in developing the South African local and international markets. This would also contribute to the empowerment and inclusion of the San people as well as accelerating the UN SDGs policies (UNESCO, 2018, British Council, 2020; Moualla & McPherson, 2019). In the appropriate cultural language, the research findings were used to draw the attention of authorities to the SDGs policies highlighted by British Council (2020: p. 17) that “Culture has the potential to address the economic and social dimensions of poverty and fight against it. Arts and cultural engagement can broaden the opportunities for and agency of vulnerable groups, foster resilience, enable citizen participation and community empowerment, enable intercultural dialogue, and advocate for equal rights.” However, I had to adopt practical approaches in my advocacy to present and guide authorities and stakeholders to read more meaning to the research evidence linked to the affected San people and the role they could play in national development. In other words, some of the key research findings were presented to authorities as a reflection on developmental policies of cultural organizations (British Council, 2018; UNDP, 2015; UNESCO World Heritage Centre, 1992-2017; OHCHR, 2012; UN, 2019) which highlight a need for people-centered developmental strategies whereby cultural diversity and the rights of all people to enjoy and promote their heritage should be prioritized in national development plan. UNESCO and the British Council have both highlighted a need for nation states through their developmental programmes to safeguard cultural heritage in all its forms, ensure access to cultural spaces and promote diversity of cultural expressions (UNESCO World Heritage Centre, 1992-2017; British Council, 2020, British Council, 2018). Specific emphases were put on a need to protect “the rights of all people to enjoy and share their culture free from fear” (British Council, 2020: p. 11). Specific examples from the broader literature review linked to the study findings were used to practicalize the theory of change in the discussions as outlined below:

Entrepreneurship linked to Cultural Exchange and Cultural Tourism

I reminded stakeholders and authorities that supporting the San people to produce their cultural products for commercial purposes was an important area to explore further for a possible intervention that could lift the image of the San culture and contribute to the beauty of cultural diversity as well as the realization of the UN-SDGs policies (OECD, 2020). It was crucial to stress on the study evidence that the targeted San people were skilled in making their traditional handicraft and so they expressed their interest in engaging in any income generating activities through their traditional skills. This suggests that they could produce and sell their traditional products beyond their cultural borders. They also highlighted that the production process is the only alternative left for them to teach and pass on greater part of their heritage to the younger generation. This then provided an opportunity for intervention that could see decision makers and stakeholders across sectors, working together to empower the effected San people through their traditional trade.

As a way of giving direction, I then linked the concept to the UN-SDGs policies and approach that highlighted a need to enhance indigenous people's participation in their community development as a sustainable way of accelerating the SDGs (Mwangi, 2019; UN Economic and Social Council, 2017; UN Food and Agriculture Organization, 2019; UN Gender Snapshot, 2019). This would mean engaging the San people in discussions to eliminate inequalities and increase their access and rights to resources in efforts to promote their heritage as highlighted in the UN-SDG 1 and 11 policies (UN Economic and Social Council, 2017; UN Gender Snapshot, 2019; Mwangi, 2019). It was also worth highlighting that trade in cultural products is a crucial means of cultural exchange (Espeso & Carlisle, 2017; UNESCO World Report, 2009; UN Gender Snapshot, 2019). UNESCO World Report (2009, p. 39) noted that cultural exchange in a form of trade in cultural goods strengthens "a common trading framework" that ensures relatively peaceful relations between all the people involved. Trade in cultural goods also foster genuine receptiveness to differences, which benefit the cultural development of the populations concerned and enable significant cultural transfers to take place across large geographical areas (UN Economic and Social Council, 2017; Mwangi, 2019; UNESCO

World Report, 2009). Trade between different cultural regions has contributed to the mutual enrichment of humanity and to the interconnectedness between cultures (UNESCO World Report, 2009).

Historically, archive information provided by PortCities Bristol (2017) noted that there is a long history of successful cultural exchange through trade between Africa and the rest of the world. The traders involved in such a trade process could be termed as cultural diplomats as they would exchange ideas, values, traditions and other aspects of culture or identity, whether to strengthen relationships, enhance socio-cultural cooperation or promote interests and beyond (Portland, 2016; ICD, 2014; International Trade Council, 2016; Cull et al., 2015; Nye, 2017). This enhances innovative cultural exchange as such cooperation would involve common cultural activities such as art, sports, literature, music, leading to improvement in intercultural relationships (McPherson et al., 2017; British Council, 2018; ICD, 2017).

In recent terms, the International Trade Council (2016) and OECD, (2020) believe that cultural exchange programs through trade in cultural products would promote cross-border understanding and long-term problem resolution by increasing peaceful personal connections. Therefore, it was important for authorities and all stakeholders to meditate on my research evidence I presented to them and see if the San heritage protection and promotion “is a shame” or rather an opportunity to develop cultural tourism. I then cited Kenya as an example, which has since embraced the British Council Programme to develop aspects of its heritage sites as well as promoting tourism for inclusive growth linked to employment creation for the locals (British Council, 2018).

This then became huge motivation to management of ACSA to give their support by leasing out the retail space at the Kimberley Airport for the San people to get access to both local and international markets to grow their business co-operative as a means to accelerate the UN-SDGs.

Clarifying Contradictory Developmental Policies with Authorities

One would wonder how any African state could use indigenous cultures as means of soft power if there is a gap between policymakers and the indigenous cultures, as revealed in this case study. The targeted authorities want the San to be integrated into mainstream society for national development but might have not considered adopting the San people's world-view in the process and therefore, contradicting state policies by going against the UN convention on human rights in some cases. As the study uncovered a bias and a breach in UN human rights on the part of the local authorities by taking away the targeted San people's right to traditional means of livelihood options, healing methods and quality of life, it was important to give policy advice on how some of the South African government human-centered projects could come on board. For example, the South African National Defense Force project *Koba Tlala*, could come on board as a reflection of the UN-SDG 17 policies which calls for collaborative efforts to promote and protect indigenous cultural heritage (Espeso & Carlisle, 2017; Petti et al., 2020; ICCROM, 2018; UNESCO-Courier, 2017).

During the feedback and discussions sessions with some of the soldiers, I summarized and simplify the SDGs 1, 3, 11, 17 policies to reflect my research evidence and the crucial role the project could play in the San heritage promotion and protection. I reminded stakeholders that it was revealed in the study that the affected San people were very concerned about their food and healing heritage. The farming project I had with the San people as part of the study data collection approach, which was also witnessed by some of the soldiers, has enhanced the San people farming skills and also inspired them to take the farming project further as a way to supplement their livelihood and to also reconnect to their food and healing heritage.

From the cultural and good environmental management point of view, I aligned my advocacy to the British Council (2013), Survival (2014) and Nye's (2017) belief that traditional food plays a crucial role in creating cultural experiences across societies. The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (2019) and Hitchcock (2019) also believe that strengthening indigenous ways of food production is crucial in reducing

hunger and malnutrition among rural communities. As means of achieving the SDGs, indigenous people's food production methods should be seen as crucial means in the fight against unemployment, hunger as well as promoting sustainable agriculture practices (Hitchcock, 2019; Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2019). Perhaps it was for this reason that the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) and Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) teamed up to strengthen policies that give guidance to indigenous farmers in order to improve their food security, nutrition and income (Hitchcock, 2019; IFAD, 2019; Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2019).

Although Notsi (2012) argued that indigenous farming methods may have a risk of low yield, others (IFAD, 2019; Hitchcock, 2019; Survival, 2014; Nakashima & Roué, 2012; UNESCO, 2001), on the other hand, believed that besides the support indigenous methods in food cultivation has provided for the survival of many people in fragile habitats, the methods are also environmentally friendly. UNESCO also argues that traditional ways of farming have proved highly durable in providing livelihood for distinct cultures in the arid regions of Africa and in fragile ecosystem in the Amazon and the forests of South-east Asia (UNESCO, 2010). This then implies that traditional ways of crop cultivation may remain a sustainable economic system that need not harm the environment and is the most commonly means of survival among indigenous people that provides them with a certain level of economic independence and cultural integrity, (Shiva, 2000; UNESCO, 2001; Hitchcock, 2019; IFAD, 2019). Further highlights were that traditional knowledge in soil management, diversity of plants and animals, water conservation and erosion control ensure effective agricultural practices among indigenous people in Africa (Hitchcock, 2019; UNESCO, 2010; Millar, 2004). It then makes sense that the Food and Agricultural Organization saw the need to promote traditional agricultural systems through its Globally Important Agricultural Heritage Systems (GIAHS) which is engaged in multi-stakeholder support for indigenous farming methods, agro-tourism and market opportunities for indigenous people (IFAD, 2019; FAO, 2018). In other words, promoting indigenous food as means of enhancing cultural tourism could create opportunities for the San to use their cultural heritage to project themselves for what they are (Hitchcock, 2019).

In general, Hitchcock (2019) believed that in recent years, indigenous people in Africa are more engaged in food production and trade of domestic crops and livestock for their livelihoods. Therefore, I emphasized to stakeholders including the soldiers that reconnecting the San people to their food and herbal healing heritage through national project could serve a crucial measure in restoring a great deal of the San cultural integrity and identity as part of the UN-SDGs targets.

The army officers were inspired to review the discussions and then initiated a contractual process through DCVH for the San people to supply six military bases with fresh traditional farm produce. In other words, my advocacy approach through good cultural relationship and the research evidence made it possible for authorities to see the need to collaborate with the San to secure their livelihood and promote their food and healing heritage.

Some of the emotional benefits of my success was what a San woman expressed during a feedback session with some of the soldiers:

“As the military was behind our inhuman relocations, a business collaboration with them through this project would not only connect us to our heritage but the good relationship we are developing with the solders would also help us heal our painful wounds...”

Digital Inclusion Linked to the San Self-Advocacy

I reminded stakeholders that it was crucial to note that social activities including trade and means of cultural exchange processes in both developing and advanced economies have gone digital (International Press Institute, 2013; Portland, 2016). This suggests that although digital cultural diplomacy at this stage may not make sense as the targeted San people were yet to fully reclaim parts of their disappearing heritage, it may make sense to note that a balanced cultural policy framework should include digital-media component (Munatsi, 2011; Azi, 2012; GSMA, 2014; McClory, 2015; Portland, 2016). Digital platforms

have made trade, including indigenous commodities, and strategic cultural exchange programs for example, through music and food heritage to become easier (Rainie & Anderson, 2014; Portland, 2016). Such an upgrade in intercultural interactions would not only enhance global connectivity that would promote relationships and less ignorance, but the process would also enhance intercultural dialogue and global peace (Portland, 2016; Rainie & Anderson, 2014).

As online social networks may remain the recent means by which people connect socially (Statista, 2017), the internet in the information age provides for the vast majority of the global youth to interact globally on issues of mutual interests (Lenhart, et al., 2005; Spies & Margolin, 2014). Public interests among citizens of nations are expressed through web activity, including online chats and forums and news gatherings, making the internet an important means of bypassing the official media checkpoints (Statista, 2017; Krotoski, 2011; Kim, 2011). In other words, it is possible for an individual or a group of people, including the San people, to take advantage of the global digital platforms to promote a nation within and beyond its national borders through mutual cultural exchange (Krotoski, 2011; Spies & Margolin, 2014; GSMA, 2014).

In order to ensure self-reliance and cultural emancipation among the San people, I reminded authorities of the key role that globalization with its digital infrastructure in promoting and protecting International Human Rights plays (UNESCO-Dakar, 2017; GSMA, 2015; GSMA Mobile Economy 2017; GSMA, 2017; Pew Research Center, 2015; Odendaal, 2015; World Economic Forum, 2015; The Discussant, 2015). For example, Digital Experts believes that digital platforms such as Facebook, blogging and Twitter etc. have played great part in political mobilization and generating public protest against human rights violations such as suppression, exploitation and attempts of restricting freedom of expression and speech (Pew Research Center, 2015; The Discussant, 2015; UNESCO-Dakar, 2017; GSMA, 2015; GSMA Mobile Economy 2017; GSMA, 2017; Odendaal, 2015; World Economic Forum, 2015). In recent years, social media platforms have enhanced mainstream media of public communication which has influenced and changed the patterns of communication, interaction and advocacy for human right issues

(UNESCO-Dakar, 2017; GSMA, 2015; GSMA Mobile Economy 2017; GSMA, 2017; Pew Research Center, 2015; Odendaal, 2015; World Economic Forum, 2015; GSMA, 2014; The Discussant, 2015). Digital platforms, which made it possible for online awareness creation, have empowered and motivated organizations, activists, defenders, and some journalists to reach global audience and raise the issues of human rights violations, which are often ignored by mainstream conventional mass media (BBC News, 2018: May 12; The Discussant, 2015; Pew Research Center, 2015). An example of such motivation in terms of creating awareness about vulnerable people like indigenous people could be the *#MeToo*. Although the *#MeToo* campaign against sexual harassment and abuse began with one film executive, several of such allegations have since been waged against high-profile people across professions; an action that might have reminded society about some neglected human right issues (Gray, 2014; US Department of State, 2017; The Internet Society, 2015; UNESCO Education for All Global Monitoring Report, 2006; BBC News, 2018: May 12).

The detailed discussions and feedback then motivated the local government to collaborate with DCVH and other stakeholders/cultural intermediaries in South Africa to find out strategic ways to enhance literacy and digital skills among the youth and learners in the research community and other provinces in the country.

In summary, a key outcome of the study linked to the positive impact on the lives of the targeted San people is a significant contribution to theory that promotes the UN-SDGs Policy Development through heritage resources. The two-way concept alongside the South African National Heritage Council (2017) advocacy for heritage inclusion provided greater understanding for a need to develop the San cultural heritage to secure their livelihood. Therefore, this study provides a practical new dimension for academia, local government and policymakers to further develop a theory that would emancipate and secure indigenous people their livelihood linked to cultural heritage protection and national cultural tourism promotion objectives. As such, the study key findings and experiences would be shared with the various San researchers I was in touch with throughout the study fieldwork. They include Sol Plaatje University and McGregor Museum in South Africa, the San Research Center in Botswana, University of Zimbabwe and the Kalahari People's Fund.

10.4 Contribution to Global and Local Policy and Practice

The study's outcomes and impacts on the research community has already had many positive implications for cultural heritage practitioners and policymakers with the progress made with the San people, policymakers, the army and industry. Some of the most important issues that emerged from this study included:

- 1) **The study turned out to be the first of its kind – Cultural Diplomacy linked to Indigenous African Cultural Heritage promotion tied in with the UN-SDGs policies.** As the study has directly led to a change in policy and practice for the San community, it could be used as a longitudinal model for donor organizations like the World Bank, the UN, IMF etc. to further develop and adopt to fit their specific projects for Africa.
- 2) **It was revealed that, in order to accelerate the implementation of the UN-SDGs, competent and charismatic individuals are needed as advocates so that they can guide authorities and stakeholders to read meaning to scientific findings.** In other words, finding out the underlining social issues that affect the San people is as important as finding strategic ways and means to link authorities to the research findings.
- 3) **The study has revealed a need for global research institutions targeting Africa as their research destination to prioritize diversity in their staffing processes by recruiting and training native Africans to take strategic leadership positions in their operations.** I demonstrated in this research that an experienced and competent native researcher has a lot more to offer in mining evidence-based data and communicating the data to make a positive change.
- 4) **The study has provided guidelines for International Development Corporations on how to minimize planning level errors in their developmental projects for Africa.** As demonstrated in the study, minimizing planning level errors - starting from the research phase, plays a key role in the successful implementation and sustainability of such developmental projects for African communities.

- 5) **The study has outlined a new dimension of how international cultural and the UN-SDGs policy advocates could change global public opinion and mindsets if they adopt their advocacy strategies, bottom-up rather than top-down, to cooperate and collaborate with authorities and stakeholders.** However, as demonstrated in the study, mutual trust and respect would be the most crucial motivational factors to voluntarily build good relationship with one another, share opinion and experiences and to finally find a meeting point as a common ground to operate.
- 6) **The combination of informal and formal approaches in cultural research turned out to be more effective and result oriented.** I adopted an informal approach to set up my Local Advisory Team which guided me through culturally sensitive topics and also led me to the right San community. My integration approach to the San community was also informal. My networking/relationships with authorities started with informal small talks and conversations which set the grounds for formal meetings and discussions to agree on and to implement projects of common interests - preserving and promoting the San heritage. The informal approach focuses more on sharing the individual intercultural experiences which is the catalyst of cultural diplomacy.
- 7) **There is a need for global collaborative work to find a balance between academic work, human rights advocacy and journalism.** This would be an effective and productive way of creating cross-cultural awareness about critical issues in regards to indigenous people. Such collaborative work would provide reliable data of high ethical standards for result-oriented advocacy that would receive various forms of publicity. I demonstrated this in the study by successfully placing my advocacy strategies across seven countries in three continents (Germany, USA, Scotland, South Africa, Zimbabwe, Botswana and Namibia).
- 8) **There is a need for international cooperation towards building mutual trust and understanding between policymakers and indigenous people; the key competent and symbolic skill in cultural diplomacy.** The importance of mutual trust and understanding in cultural policy development has been emphasized by various cultural organizations and expert (ICCROM, 2018; UNESCO, 2001; Said,

1978; Putmans,1993; Carpiano, 2009; Conservation Watch, 2017; OHCHR, 2012; MRG, 2000; UN, 2009; Survival, 2017). This was practically demonstrated in this study that, mutual trust and understanding between indigenous people and policymakers would not only create awareness about indigenous cultural values and norms but could also bridge the gap between indigenous communities and policymakers in efforts to realize the UN-SDGs.

- 9) **There is a need for collaborative work between cultural practitioners and policymakers.** In other words, if policymakers, cultural researchers and donor agencies would approach indigenous people as partners in development, then heritage resources could be aligned towards the acceleration of the SDGs in a more dignified way. Such collaborative work would make it possible for indigenous cultural advocates and local governments to reach consensus on developmental issues on the grounds of transparency and accountability. This would then set the ground for creative and innovative ways of managing the San heritage resources through cultural tourism as a way of securing the San people their livelihoods. This would be an enhancement of the UN-SDGs target 11.4 policies.

- 10) **Another crucial issue that emerged from the study was a need to promote indigenous micro-entrepreneurship as Heritage for Inclusive Growth.** In the two-way approach to cultural heritage promotion and protection, it is crucial to find out what set of traditional skills and potentials among indigenous communities could be enhanced and linked to heritage recourses to promote cultural tourism as well as economic inclusion.

- 11) **In promoting traditional entrepreneurship among the San people however, meeting other needs such as enough land for them to engage in their traditional farming and healing methods, access to retail shops to trade in their traditional produce and products, specific capacity building trainings and basic capital to start their businesses are crucial.**

10.5 Recommendations

The study recommendations are intended to enhance practical implementation of the knowledge revealed in this study linked to the UN-SDGs policy development strategies. The study objectives were achieved and then highlighted that it is possible to create awareness about the San cultural values and norms among policymakers and local governments. It was also revealed that the San Cultural Heritage can be aligned with the UN-SDGs to protect the San Heritage and used as a form of Cultural Diplomacy by the Nation. These achievements serve as a build-up on existing concepts and recommendations by previous studies (The South African National Heritage Council, 2017; British Council, 2018; Moualla & McPherson, 2019; Petti et al., 2020). However, before these concepts can be achieved, strategic research methodologies and practical new policy initiatives are needed to enhance the existing policies. Therefore, the study recommends the following:

- 1) **I recommend University of the West of Scotland (UWS) promote the study as a new dimension of research excellence in relation to African Cultural Diplomacy linked to the UN-SDGs policies.** The study has already established a unique collaborative network and platform that consist of the diplomatic society, industry, the army, academic institutions, NGOs, traditional leaders, broadcasting houses etc. and has created a unique pool of experts from diverse backgrounds across Africa, the UK and the USA. This then serves as a unique or one-time opportunity for the UWS to strengthen its international cooperation as a champion in cultural research and UK-Africa partnerships. Therefore, I would suggest UWS to present the study achievements to partner institutions, international organizations including the British Council, the World Bank, UNCTAD, UNESCO and the other UN agencies.
- 2) **I recommend the study serves as evidence of UWS commitment to the UN SDGs Accord signed in 2021 to lead the SDGs research beyond the UK borders. Therefore, the study could not have come at a better time.** I would recommend that the **UWS Centre for African Research on Enterprise and**

Economic Development (CAREED) present the study transformational change that has both theoretical and tangible positive impact on society in South Africa to partner institutions like the UN, IMF as evidence and success stories of UWS commitment to the UN SDGs Accord signed.

- 3) In the African context, the study has fully demonstrated and provided innovative approaches that promote sustainable micro-entrepreneurship in African. **Therefore, I recommend the study for CAREED, as it leads research in African enterprise and economic development, to adopt various components of the study into its vision and mission statements and present it as evidence to partners like UNCTAD, FAO, IFAD, IMF, the World Bank, the African Development Bank and the Commonwealth Secretariat.** This can lead to new dimensions between me as the researcher, CAREED and all the collaborating organizations.
- 4) **Local governments as well as the UN-SDGs policies need to adapt measures to intensify awareness creation among policymakers and the general public about the importance of the San Heritage.** This study recommends digital platforms as means to create such awareness. This is due to the fact that majority of the survey respondents (policymakers) use digital media platforms as their main sources of information (see **Q7 and Q8** in survey **Part 1**).
- 5) **Strategic means of building diverse capital and cultural tourism should include innovative means of promoting the San heritage aligned with national sporting events, musical and traditional food festivals and any other tourism promotion events.** This is due to the fact that majority of the surveyed policymakers were interested in getting daily updates about cultural related topics such as music, sports and cultural events linked to tourism (see **Q9** survey **Part 1**).
- 6) **Word-of-mouth way of transmitting information in San communities should be encouraged.** The word-of-mouth way of transmitting information encourages physical movement and interaction among the people as they move from one compound to the other. This allows for storytelling, enrichment of the past and a

continuation of their cultural heritage through different geographical locations, communities and generations.

- 7) Classic anthropological researchers may recommend that the Researcher lives together with the target groups in order to study and understand their ways of life. However, I found out in this study that **short periods of multiple visits to research target groups proved to be more effective in mutual trust building and more effective in data collection than a single period of long visit.** The short visits allowed for self-reflection and assessment of the other (s), a process that was very crucial in mutual trust building and the evidence-based data collection in this study and allowed the researcher to keep some independent distance.
- 8) **Strategic anthropological data collection techniques should be linked to profitable activities for the research target groups.** Engaging research target groups in profitable and entertaining activities such as farming, artwork, housekeeping activities, cultural entertainments etc. as means of data collection techniques were found to be helpful in building mutual trust and regaining self-confidence among the target group. This is a key issue for government policy makers but also for cultural institutes and agencies who need to keep arguing for and funding long term sustainable projects that take time to demonstrate the theory of change, gain trust, understanding and mutual respect and that organizations such as the British Council and UNESCO suggest can happen with time.
- 9) **Go-Along interview methods, due to their flexible nature, proved to be more suitable and effective in data collection among the targeted San people.** It is important to structure interview sessions or meetings in a way that suits the San people everyday life. This then make the go-along interview methods crucial options in similar anthropological studies that require an element of trust and flexibility to research data gathering.

- 10) **Informal and unstructured meetings proved to be more effective in motivating the San people to share their experiences.** Otherwise, they would become tense and reluctant to talk. Even daily field notes should be memorized and documented in private and not during the interactions. However, follow-up meetings to record feedback or to verify recorded data should be formalized. The complete formalized paperwork for the groups' focal persons would allow the groups to discuss all recorded points, in their own pace, and respond to each point accordingly.
- 11) **In order to keep to the required ethical and moral standards, it is very important to meet target groups when they are sober.** In a situation whereby the target groups may depend on monthly social grant from the state, meetings should be timed and scheduled to avoid the first week in which they would receive their social grants. This is the week that most people would drink alcohol beyond their limits and their consent may not meet research ethical standards.

10.6 Self-reflection

As I reflect on the study process and the impact on the lives of the San people, it occurs to me that although evidence-based recommendations from qualitative in-depth study could provide authorities authentic directions to promote indigenous cultural heritage, scientific results and recommendations alone may not be enough to influence willpower of authorities to include indigenous viewpoint in policy decisions. Evidence-base data needs to be linked to mutual trust and respect in order to change mindsets and influence willpower. The experience gathered in this study tells me that the process involved would require an independent entity to act as a mediator who would interpret the scientific data to touch hearts and minds of authorities.

I was an independent neutral entity, as the researcher in this study, working between the two "rivalry" target groups (as the San people and the authorities). As the Researcher, it was my academic research interest to find out the realities of the situation and make

scientific recommendations. In other words, the further efforts I made to close the gap between the San people and the authorities was my moral obligation; my passion to witness positive change in the lives of the targeted San people as the ultimate goal of my research mission rather than just see them as subjects of my research.

My success stories in the mediation process were based on not only my academic knowledge but also my extensive intercultural experiences and the fact that I chose the right methodology - autoethnography. The ability to understand and appreciate the target groups cultural values and norms was crucial in the mediation process. I had gathered from my rural experiences in Ghana as well as in this study that community life in rural set up is usually about support (emotional, physical, psychological etc.) for one another. Formal agreements and processes are usually not needed to build trust and love for one another but rather, appreciation for one another's contribution to community life, which are guided by the cultural values and norms. This then makes indigenous values and norms key contributors to their livelihood and quality of life and should therefore be prioritized in any kind of policy mediation and negotiations towards their empowerment and liberation. It is crucial then that this is not forced or artificial, this would just be another example of colonialism but look at what can be achieved, when the right tools, people and skills are used to create a theory of change, work at the grassroots, but have the ability to engage policy makers and help secure the change identified by the UN through their SDGs. This research has contributed to the long-term sustainable change in the cultural protection of the San People's tangible and intangible cultural heritage, it has led to their economic sustainability and security and recognized their culture as an area of national importance to the government, army and industry.

10.7 Areas for Further Study.

There is a need for further in-depth studies to find out more about the lost heritage of the San people as well as the best possible ways to reconnect them to such lost heritage. The UN-IPMG (2019) and the South African National Heritage Council (2017) believe that all forms of cultures, whether tangible or intangible, have both material and

creative values as they are the reflection of the people's creativity and uniqueness. In other words, the foundation of intercultural dialogue is rooted in understanding intangible cultural heritage of different communities as a way towards mutual respect for other ways of life (UNESCO, 2017, Petronela, 2016). However, it emerged from this study that the multiple force -relocations of the targeted San people have eroded significant aspects of their intangible heritage. This suggests their story may not be different from the other San families regardless of their location within the continent.

As the San people are located at various parts in southern Africa (Hitchcock, 2019), it is very important to note that their communal needs linked to their heritage resources may differ. Therefore, the creative and innovative ways that emerged from this study to manage the targeted San people heritage resources are just important guides that require detailed phenomenological in-depth study to find out more about the San cultural resources at their specific locations and how to link such resources to their communal development.

The general guidelines, as gathered from this study, suggest that critical issues to consider in such an in-depth study would include: possible human rights issues, the specific San people's ability to cope with change in a dignified way without losing their identity – ability to adapt to newly provided modern accommodation and household equipment instead of their self-made huts and traditional cooking methods, shopping in modern shops instead of their traditional ways of survival, adjusting to the taste of new food instead of their staple food as their heritage. Orientation time period needed for the specific group to adapt to any possible change should be given particular attention. This would resolve many issues and would also enhance efficiency and effectiveness in utilizing resources.

There is a need for the countries which host the San people to collaborate and cooperate in their academic and policy efforts to preserve and promote the San Heritage. This study revealed that the San people depend on informal local network to

retrieve parts of their intangible heritage, such as indigenous crop seeds and medicinal herbs.

As the San people are spread across the Southern African region, it would be a good idea for SDGs advocates and San research institutions such as the San Research Center in Botswana, the University of Zimbabwe, Sol Plaatje University and McGregor Museum in South Africa, the Kalahari People's Fund, etc. to have collaborative studies and knowledge sharing events. Such collaborations could help in finding out the best possible means and strategies to establish and encourage local and cross-border network for the San people to recover and preserve their endangered heritage that individuals might still be holding onto. The outcome of such collaborative academic work would inform the various national policy decisions in heritage promotion and empowerment of their indigenous people. The related benefits would include the recovery of several indigenous crops and medicinal plants. This would then be an immense contribution to biodiversity and conservation as outlined by the SDG targets 11 and 13 policies and could also strengthen social bonds, geographical borders which could all add cultural meaning to being a citizen from the San origin.

10.8 My Personal Next Steps

The great effort and passion that I put into the PhD research work from the beginning till the end brought me into contact with many people around the world. The hard work made it possible for me to keep presenting my research motivation to people from diverse cultural background across three continents – USA, Europe and Africa. In other words, my research work was a two-way communication channel between me and audiences in at least seven countries in three continents: USA, Germany, Scotland, South Africa, Botswana, Zimbabwe and Namibia.

I also believe that my motivation and the extra effort I put into the study gave my Research Director more opportunities to analyze whatever might have appeared to be my weaknesses and strengths so that together with the supervisory team, we were able to align my entire life experiences with my PhD knowledge acquired. As the outcome, hardly

did I submit my final thesis than receiving two job offers: One with Global Winns Consult in Berlin and the other offer to implement a project sponsored by the German Social Welfare Office for African Immigrants in Berlin. As an era of the covid-19 pandemic with the related high levels of global unemployment, I believe that my research work was a great success and therefore worth every investment that went into the process.

After my viva voce phase, I would expect more job offers from other parts of the Globe where I would continue to demonstrate my passion for social change linked to my PhD success stories. I also hope to find a publisher for my autobiography - an updated version of the first book *Francis: An African Story*. In this second book would be a deeper reflection on my 27 years journey to be part of knowledge seekers up to a PhD level without any financial resource or family support. My meditations on my PhD research motivation, my role and the research impact on my native continent, Africa, as well as the related challenges that I fought hard to overcome in order to get to where I am today would be shared with interested readers. My passion for academic work linked to social change through diplomatic means will always remain high and I hope to publish from this my PhD thesis as well. Therefore, I would welcome any collaborations in this field very much. I am happy that I studied for my PhD at the University of the West of Scotland, UK.

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Appendix 1: Survey questionnaires

Part 1: Table1. Target group: Stakeholders/ Policymakers**Q1. How would you describe your profession?**

A. Civil servant /government official		
B. Private Sector		

Q2. Do you think there is the need to research more about indigenous cultures e.g. the San/Bushmen in order to maintain their way of life?

A. Yes		
B. No		

Q3. How would you describe the indigenous way of life as an African tribe?

A. Original		
B. A shame to the African identity		

Q4. What is your wish for indigenous people?

A. Integrate them into mainstream society for a better life		
B. Maintain their originality and promote their heritage		

Digital media**Q5. How would you describe your competence level in managing the global digital infrastructure/ideologies and networks?**

A. None		
B. Basic		
C. Expert		

Q6. How would you describe your internet skills?

A. Basic - email/SMS exchange		
B. Good - manage online information		
C. Expert level		

Q7. Do you often go online - every hour?

A. Yes		
B. No		

Q8. What is your main source of news update?

A. Television		
B. Social Media platforms		
C. Word-of-mouth		

Q9. What updates would you wish to get every day?

A. Culture/Music		
B. Tourism/Sports		
C. Politics		
D. Food Commodities		

Part 2: Table 2. Target group - The target San people at Platfontein, South Africa.**Q1. How would you describe your everyday life at Platfontein?**

A. Good		
B. Hectic and Depressive		

Q2. How would you describe the future of your heritage?

A. There is hope for our heritage		
B. There is no hope for our heritage		

Q3. How would you describe your literacy level?

A. None		
B. Basic		
C. Good		

Q4. How would you describe your internet skills?

A. None		
B. Basic		

Q5. What is your main source of news update?

A. Television		
B. Radio		
C. Word-of-mouth		

Appendix 2: Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Study title: Promoting and Protecting Indigenous African Cultural Heritage through Digital and Diplomacy

Cultural

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to explore the cultural issues that the San/Bushman Ethnic Group is facing as a result of donor-funded conservation projects and tourism development.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because your community has been identified as having encountered cultural issues as a result of donor-funded conservation projects and tourism development.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason.

What will happen to me if I take part?

The research will be conducted in a form of face-to-face interviews and discussions, which will take about 45 minutes to complete. If you agree to take part in it, the principal researcher and his team will arrange the face-to-face interview time and place with you and your answers would be recorded in writing.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no known risks or disadvantages of taking part, as we strive to protect your confidentiality, unless you explicitly agree that your name can be mentioned in publications arising from the research.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

In taking part, you will be able to reflect on the cultural and communal issues you have experienced, which can lead to finding solutions to promote and protect your cultural heritage.

If you take part in this interview, we would discuss together as a team to come out with recommendations on how to use social and digital media to enhance the beauty and meaning of being a citizen, an artist, a writer, an advocate etc. of the San Ethnic Identity through an increased awareness creation using the global media. We intend to maintain contact to a local networking through which we would give feedback to all participants on the results and publication.

A copy of the research analysis, in a form of the entire study documentation presented to the University of the West of Scotland, would be presented to the local contact for all those who would take part in the face-to-face interview and their community for future references.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Andy Connor and he can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be [the provision of your consent.] You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you.

Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. If we are able to anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provide we will undertake this and will endeavour to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible. Or we will anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provide by the 15th January 2019.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

Detail any intended recipients of personal data if not explained elsewhere, and also advise if any personal data will be transferred outside the EEA, and if so to where.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

We will publish the results in academic papers and at academic conferences. Primarily however, the principal researcher aims to engage possible stakeholders and the general public with the results. Thus, we may communicate the results of this research through social media and other forms of communication channels when necessary.

Who has reviewed the study?

MCS Ethics Committee

Contact for further information

Personal details withheld.

Personal details withheld.

Thank you for taking part in this study.

Appendix 3: Informed Consent Form

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Promoting and Protecting Indigenous African Cultural Heritage through Digital and Cultural Diplomacy.

Case Study of the San Ethnic Group in Southern Africa.

Investigator(s): Francis Adams

Researcher Email:

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

I, Mr. Kakenge Automover, on behalf of my family, confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

Initials

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.

Initials

I consent to the processing of my personal information (age, ethnicity, sex, nationality, opinion, experiences, pictures, family status, educational background, voice recordings and videos) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.

Initials

I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any publication resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me.

I agree to having my voice/likeness digitally recorded.

I freely agree to participate in this study.

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the MCS Ethics Committee by email at: mcs.ethics@uws.ac.uk. Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Media, Culture and Society, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

Signatures:

Personal details withheld.

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the MCS Ethics Committee by email at: mcs.ethics@uws.ac.uk. Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Media, Culture and Society, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

Appendix 4: Ethics Committee Approval

04/06/2018

Dear Francis Adams,

Your application 4881: PhD Research Ethics Application, submission 3678, has been approved by the Media Culture and Society SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Christopher O'Donnell

Appendix 5: Correspondence - San Researchers

On Monday, March 26, 2018, 4:34:25 PM GMT+2, Edward Dakora <Edward.Dakora@spu.ac.za> wrote:

Dear Francis,

It's good to hear from you and that you arrived safely. I am equally glad to hear that your visit here and Botswana was fruitful.

Wow! You are indeed very busy. You are always welcome, and thank you for sharing your ideas with me and my colleagues. I have spoken to [REDACTED] about the possibility of providing you with space to sit in the School of Humanities when you come back and he is keen to help.

So, we will deal with that when you are ready to come.

All the best,

[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

[REDACTED]

From: Adams Francis [REDACTED]
Sent: Monday, March 26, 2018 2:18 PM
To: [REDACTED]
Subject: Thank you: Francis in Berlin

Personal details withheld.

Dear [REDACTED]

I have arrived in Berlin safely and I am writing to thank you for your support in everything during my visit to your university!

I really thank God for your presence at the Sol Plaatje University.

My trip to Botswana was very successful and I ended discussions with a presentation at the University of Botswana in Gaborone. Please see some pictures attached.

I am at the moment working very hard on my trip-report for my University along side my second book. My visit to the USA and academic trip to Norway are expected to take place between April and May. Then I will let you know my expected date back to Kimberley to continue with the next stage of the research and the project I set up at Platfontein. So I will keep you updated.

Thanks a lot once again.

Francis

[redacted]

[redacted]

[redacted]

On Thu, Mar 21, 2019 at 10:48 PM Adams Francis [redacted]:

Dear [redacted]

As soon as my drafts are ready, I will update you for your comments. At the same time, I am working hard to get in touch with funding institutions that I may want to apply to at a later stage to implement any projects that would come from my research work. I will update you on that if I find such possibilities.

Thank you very much.

Francis

On Monday, March 11, 2019, 4:21:14 AM GMT+ [redacted] > wrote:

Dear Francis,

My humblest apologies, I somehow missed your email. I was on leave at the time trying to get a paper completed.

I am sorry not to have seen you as I am interested in the work you are doing. Do please let me have an update and let me know if there is any way information you think I can assist you with.

With every good wish

[redacted]

[redacted]

Personal details withheld.

[redacted]

[redacted]

DEPARTMENT OF AFRICAN LANGUAGES AND LITERATURE UNIVERSITY OF ZIMBABWE

8 May 2019

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This letter serves to confirm that Mr. Francis Alhassan Adams, a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland in collaboration with the Institute for Cultural diplomacy – Berlin has visited our Department of African Languages and Literature, University of Zimbabwe. The reason for his visits was to engage in discussions about the San Community in Zimbabwe, commonly referred to as the Tshwao group since the scope of his research covers this indigenous community. Apart from generating data through these visits, his visits also provided a platform for negotiating collaborations and useful links for developing strategic partnerships between the University and his host University and Institute for leveraging knowledge-sharing, resource mobilisation for the advancement of innovative research, outreach and teaching in the area of Indigenous Communities and people with a strong bias towards the Tshwao people.

Please feel free to contact us should you need any further details.

Personal details
withheld.

20th June, 2018

To Whom It May Concern

This letter is confirmation that Francis Alhassan Adams, a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland in collaboration with the Institute for Cultural Diplomacy – Berlin is expected to visit our Centre in Gaborone, Botswana. The reason for his visit is to follow up on the discussions from our last meeting with him in April this year. This will also include a visit by Francis to one of the Indigenous communities in Botswana.

Thank you,

Personal details withheld.

May 13, 2019

TO: To Whom It May Concern

RE: Support Letter for Francis Adams

Ladies and Gentlemen:

Francis Adams contacted the Kalahari Peoples Fund in early 2019 about the possibility of supporting his work and serving as mentors for his work on indigenous issues and cultural heritage, with specific reference to San/Bushmen Cultural Heritage.

The Kalahari Peoples Fund, which has worked with San and other peoples in Southern Africa for over 45 years, is deeply interested in the work that Francis Adams is proposing to do, and we wish to endorse it. We feel that his combination of the use qualitative and quantitative methods, his work with digital media, and his involvement at the community, district, national, and regional levels holds significant progress for advancing the cultural heritage of the San.

Mr. Adams wishes to collaborate with regional researchers, policy-makers, and indigenous and other organizations in Southern Africa. We have provided him with some assistance in this area. We feel that his work is definitely very useful.

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 6: Field Notes and Dairies including Pictures

Appendix pages 1 - 8 redacted due to uninformed consent for publication from the photographed subjects.

Education

⊗ MOST of them can't read or write

⇒ Very few can speak English

⇒ They don't like formal writing

⇒ I will make spontaneous appointments

⇒ engaging in activities??

⇒

⇒ taking a walk?

How:

Test

cleaning the backyard

go gathering??

Farming/gardening

On Education

② "Africanities don't understand us"

"-We can read; only that

⑦ we cannot read this book
"-but reading is reading..."

Note:

Should follow-up on this next week!

Why is the San education so important to them?

① Please tell me more about San way of education!
② Or: Teach me about San education...

AROMASIN®
Exemestan

Educ.

⇒ Targets Groups are very sensitive about their educational background:

⊗ Engage in small-talks just ((inform Grayle!))

⇒ politymakers !!

⇒ Very suspicious

⊗ ⇒ "I will not sign anything..."

⊗ ⇒ " - - don't record our conversation!"

⊗ ⇒ " - - please keep your phone away - - don't bring it here - - I don't want to be recorded..."

!! Develop New Strategy: IF it works, then continue otherwise call Grayle!!

⊗ ! don't ask about educational bgd.

!! education

① ⇒ Get their recommendation to proceed to others

② ⇒ approach them for small talks during the morning breaks

~~and~~

③ ⇒ Get answers in the evening after the heavy meals and drinks

④ ⇒ Thank them for "teaching me" and ask for their recommendation e.g. where/when is the next workshop etc.

⑤ ⇒ Get as many email addresses as possible and stay in touch.

education ⇒ the San people

Any specific trainings??

- eg. on-the-job
- vocational train.

Empowerment/
Development
explore ⇒ Get possibilities
!!

⇒ Health care:

- Awareness creation for the youth
⇒ eg. HIV/STIs etc.

⇒ Family planning

⇒ reproductive health for mothers/girls

⇒ FGM (check ~~ask~~ literature/ask the leader)

⇒ contracep. for young mothers.

education - San

Health

⇒ They are not keen on "white man's medicine"

Some Reasons ⇒ not patient

⇒ long process

⇒ expensive

⇒ lacks psychological healing ?? (check)

⇒ embarrassing experiences at clinics

⇒ "just not for us..."

" (X) San medicine is his food and his food is his medicine -- "

(X) "It's very hard here in this village -- "

notes

Will let them explain further during the next meeting when we are around

(X) Postponed meetings

Observations · Platform

Social Issues: get answers!

- + Drugs =>
- + Alcoholism =>
- + Stealing /
- + Teenage pregnancy.??
- => Municipality ??

This will still take time => they are not willing to talk about it.
Talk to Gayle about that ??

meeting at the municipality next week before I go to University of Zimbabwe

=> Research about the MCE?

=> let Edward update me

=> check on Sharon - contacts/her ideas??

Are they willing to meet-up with the Jan chief??

If yes

If NO

Proceed and propose dates!!

call Gayle immediately for discussions for the way forward.

Observation

Will discuss with Edward: ~~the week~~

- Many pregnant young women??

- They drink a lot of beer-

- They have very little food

- Joseph's wife emetics?

Find out more

- did she lose a child.

- lack of medical care?

- since when

Mandalena

⇒ Hagola ⇒ since when

- how old was she etc.

- Any specific places??

- the "Ebenia people"

get more info

military

- how often ~~use~~ the re-loc.??
- Any advance notice..?
- compensations
- SWAPO - Namibia
- 1975 → Angola
- 1994 - South Africa
- ⇒ and. so??

Mandela ⇒ The land?

- Farm land or just a "free" land for Armed Forces?

Compensations

⇒ Any specific benefits?

⇒ End of Service Benefits

⇒ Employment Assurance?

⇒ child care / disability etc.??

In South Africa

||| Grant them SA citizenship?

= special pension?

⇒ Social grant

⇒ Handouts: How?

⇒ → no of children, grand, Hoja etc?

Culture

- * "Why should we all be the same?"
- * "They should think of how we can all fit into the modern world"
- * - "We don't envy their modern world with their electricity"

They have issue with modern education way of life...

Will follow up on that in our next meeting!!

Culture

- x - "we believe in the world of the dead"

death is not the end
of life --- we love
of our departed souls²³

- x "There are so many
painful things that
disturb us..."

- x - all we need is a
bit of respect"

x " Culture - that may be true "

x " - why did they recruit us
to the military... "

x " it's very funny. "

x - we can read - -

x we know everything - -

- - we used to teach them
in the military. - -

Culture

= They are very worried (thin home)

=> They want to go "HOME" - - (??)

=> "It's "hectic" here..." get more info!

=> we are tired of relocation

=> our food => "the San food"

=> African Traditional Medicin !! (check...)

=> "We miss home..."

!!
 ⓧ Get more info. about what is HOME!

HOME
 open discussions when
 suitable (after the
 naming ceremony)

→ Where is home?
 to you?
 - (NATURE!) ✓

→ What are some of
 your great memories
 about home?
 - time with NATURE! ✓

I do not have a home so I do not miss home.
 please share with me why you missed home?
 - (NATURE!) ✓

ⓧ -- NATURE is where we call HOME... everything
 there has meaning to us... "

⇒ Explore more and fill in table...

Dr. Edward / Dr. Morris / check with them

Most neglected group? Why?? (Ward 27) @counselor?

⊙ Angola

⊕ Integration

⊗ Representatives

~~⊗ CO~~

* These people need space, material to erect their own structures. They were not yet formalized in their mind to live in formal structures. e.g. pictures:

- ⊕ Action plan for the project:
 - Business plan
 - Applications
 - Baseline Survey

⊕ Why were the 7 ethnics moved from Midstath to current location?

- ⇒ What was the agreement in place?
- ⇒ was it followed as planned for all the batches??

⊕ The last batch that were evicted 2016 after - 3 huts + a church. - NO formal structures

← even with the second and 1st first batches that were relocated the state delayed in providing

⊕ Representatives: Fakes representatives / individuals / ASSOCIATIONS

⊕ Create awareness

⊕ Midterm presentation to SA government - Start for DECO?

* My local Team is made up of natives and activists sympathetic 2018

⊕ Decision making (Cultural Res)

counselor has no contact with the locals. what does the counselor present for decision making?

Relocation 2003 under CPA → Military came with SA Military → 7 huts with after

⇒ Military camp closed, 1994 they became "trespassers" minneest conservation

⇒ last batch 2016

2003-2015 under CPA

since 2016 ⇒ Municipal / guid

① Origin: 5 Kings? trace them to find their claim

* SKA organization?

② Traditional land maps the story authentic: Identity lose, story lose,

*Appendix 7: Follow-up input – Invitation
to South Africa to give Policy Advice*

Diamond Creative

VISION HUB, NPC

DEAR SIR/MADAM

Diamond Creative Vision HUB is a non-profit business development social enterprise that provides emerging and aspiring entrepreneurs with basic entrepreneurial resources, skills and tools to start, manage and grow an enterprise. Our goal is to inspire a culture and mind-set of entrepreneurship through our core entrepreneur development programmes and innovative business development services. Our services and public benefit projects are driven by the needs of the community and are easily accessible by our target audience.

We have been working with the Platfontein community on skills development initiatives in order to empower the local community to sustain themselves through job creation. DCVH is writing to officially confirm that Mr. Francis Alhassan Adams, born on 15.01.1980, is our invited guest and we at Diamond Creative Vision Hub are looking forward to hosting him in Kimberley, Northern Cape, South Africa any moment from 30th January till 13th March 2020. As the principal PhD researcher in our collaborative efforts to protect and promote the San People cultural heritage at Platfontein, Mr. Adams' has since made many successful follow-up visits to Kimberley on our invitation.

For this time, we are inviting Mr. Adams to come and give Dada-driven Policy Advice to stakeholders within the Northern Cape Municipality based on a groundbreaking collaborative research work we carried out at Platfontein near Kimberley in a period of two years. Please see the schedule of his activities for this visit attached.

Diamond Creative

VISION HUB, NPC

DCVH motivations to collaborate with Mr. Francis Alhassan Adams: Since January 2018, Diamond Creative Vision Hub has been collaborating with Francis Alhassan Adams (a PhD Researcher in Cultural Diplomacy and Public Policy at the University of West of Scotland in collaboration with the Institute for Cultural Diplomacy, Germany) in his field research work at Platfontein. The aim is to improve the lives of the San people DCVH was already supporting at Platfontein. Mr. Adams' research and policy advice in our collaboration are unique in many ways:

- 1)** By birth, Mr. Adams is of similar tribe and had similar cultural experiences (hunter-gathering) as the San peoples so it is easy for the targeted San group to trust him and relate with him better than it would have been with other researchers.
- 2)** We at DCVH need Mr. Adams' technical research skills in a form of recommendations during and after the research phase to enhance indigenous entrepreneurship in South Africa.
- 3)** His approach is based on high ethical values as requirement for European research standards.
- 4)** He is playing a key role in linking DCVH up with a broad network of experts in NGOs and creating discussion platforms for us and other research institutions including local and regional Universities, etc.

Diamond Creative

VISION HUB, NPC

Being able to collaborate with Mr. Adams has provided us an opportunity to think creatively, built up a unique teamwork and innovative approach/methodology that have already brought practical socio-economic change in the Platfontein community. Through our success stories, we have managed to get various stakeholders including the Executive Mayor of Kimberley (Mr. Patrick Mabilo), Sol Plaatjie University, Kimberley Houses of Traditional Leaders, and many civil and cultural industrial leaders who are all interested in Mr. Adams' research findings and policy advice on promoting and protecting indigenous cultural heritage in the Republic of South Africa.

In other words, our collaborative research work is now at the center of policy interest - made it possible for DCVH and other stakeholders to close the gap between the targeted San people and policymakers within the Northern Cape Municipality in order to enhance heritage inclusion in developing the municipality. The methodology would surely be recommended for similar projects in other municipalities within South Africa and partners institutions in neighboring countries.

Feel free to contact us if you have any questions: